

A Technical Guidebook for
**GEOHERMAL
DIRECT USE**
Development in Africa

Technical Guidebook for
Geothermal Direct-Use
Development in Africa

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Contents

Foreword.....	i
Acknowledgments	ii
Acronyms.....	iv
Executive Summary.....	vi
CHAPTER 1: BACKGROUND	1
1.1 Introduction.....	2
1.2 Rationale for the technical guidebook	2
1.3 Global perspectives in geothermal resource utilisation.....	3
1.4 Geothermal Energy Resource Utilization in Africa.....	7
CHAPTER 2: GEOTHERMAL RESOURCES OCCURRENCES IN AFRICA	15
2.1 Eastern branch of the East African Rift System	16
2.2 Red-Sea and Gulf of Aden	19
2.3 Western branch of the East African Rift System and Southern Rifts	23
2.4 Geothermal resources in sedimentary basins	26
2.5 North Africa (Mediterranean collision zone).....	29
2.6 Oceanic and continental mantle plumes (Comoros, Cape Verde & Sudan).....	30
2.7 Other geothermal occurrences	30
CHAPTER 3: EXPLORATION METHODS FOR SHALLOW GEOTHERMAL RESOURCES	31
3.1 Steps in Direct-Use project exploration and development	32
3.2 Exploration methods for volcanic systems.....	38
3.3 Exploration methods for Fault-controlled systems	40
3.4 Exploration methods for Sedimentary basins-hosted systems.....	42
3.5 Surface engineering and development on site	44
3.6 Site management, maintenance and global costs	45
CHAPTER 4: DIRECT USE DEVELOPMENT APPROACH.....	47
4.1 The direct use development approach enabling uptake	48
4.2 Geothermal utilisation in high temperature systems	50
CHAPTER 5: DIRECT-USE DEVICES AND TECHNOLOGIES	53
5.1 Key components and system design	54
5.2 Local population’s traditional knowledge.....	64
CHAPTER 6: CASE STUDIES OF DIRECT-USE APPLICATIONS	69
6.1 Caves and mushroom cultivation	72
6.2 Aquaculture.....	73
6.3. Greenhousing.....	75
6.4. Crops, fruits and vegetables drying	77
6.5 Milk pasteurisation and cheese processing.....	82
6.6 Fruit, wine and cheese maturation.....	84
6.7 Fish processing.....	84
6.8 Abattoirs and other agro-industrial processes	87
6.9 Washing, peeling and blanching	89
6.10 Health applications: baths, swimming pools, hydrotherapy and spas.....	89

6.11 Derived sanitary products	91
6.12 Chemical extraction.....	91
6.13 Bottled mineral water	92
6.14 District and buildings Heating/Cooling	93
6.15 Direct use for circular economy	93
CHAPTER 7: SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS MODELS	95
7.1 Community-driven models	96
7.2 Government-driven models	96
7.3 Private sector-driven: PPP/IPP	97
Chapter 8: ENABLING INSTITUTIONAL AND LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORKS.....	99
8.1 Project Management (with an illustration of community-owned DU initiative in Afar)	100
8.2 Need for a specific support system	102
8.3 Policy, Legal and Regulatory Framework	104
CHAPTER 9: RESEARCH, INFORMATION AND CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT	107
9.1. Current situation and identified needs.....	108
9.2 Components of the DUGD and manpower optimisation.....	108
9.3 Examples of financed projects: Research and Development.....	110
9.4. The need for specific R&D and innovation effort in African public policies.....	114
CHAPTER 10: SUPPORTIVE FINANCE FOR DIRECT USE PROJECTS.....	117
10.1 DUGD: A site-specific economy	118
10.2 Funding sources for Africa.....	120
CHAPTER 11: SPECIFIC ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL DIMENSIONS.....	121
11.1 How DUGD differs from classical geothermal projects	122
11.2 Project implementation	122
11.3 Holistic environment.....	123
11.4 Sustainability and resilience	123
11.5 Inclusion in National Strategic Policies, especially Climate Policies	124
11.6 DUGD answering Sustainable Development Goals	128
CHAPTER 12: CONCLUSION	129
REFERENCES.....	135

Foreword

UNEP Africa office is responsible for implementation of UNEP's Medium Term Strategy (MTS) and Programme of Work (POW) in Africa in line with the country's National Development plan that responds to the Global and continental Development Agendas: SDG 2030; AU Agenda 2063 and Paris Agreement On climate action 2015. The UNEP MTS focusses on resolving the three Plenary Crisis i.e. Climate change, Nature/Biodiversity loss and Pollution and waste and create "Climate stability, Living with Harmony in Nature and Pollution Free planet".

In order to achieve this objective, UNEP Africa office works very closely with government institutions such as Ministry of Environment and other relevant organizations and partners. Further, the Africa office works closely with each of the UN Country team in African countries under the coordination and leadership of the UN Resident coordination offices.

In line with this, UNEP Africa Office through its Energy Unit provides technical and professional support in development of renewable energy resources that can significantly contribute to the socio economic development of the continent. Among others, UNEP supports African countries, through its African Rift Geothermal Development Facility Programme (ARGeo), in exploration and development of geothermal resources that can be used for electricity generation and direct use applications.

This technical guidebook on geothermal direct use development has been developed by UNEP in response to the request and recommendation of stakeholders who attended the seventh African Rift Geothermal virtual Conferences (ARGeo-c7) held in Kigali, Rwanda in 2018. The meeting noted

that besides electricity generation which was the main focus for countries of the East African rift system, there was a need to change track and consider exploration and development of direct use of geothermal resources in Africa. This was due to the fact that the existence of diversified nature of the geothermal resource in the East African Rift System (EARS) with well-developed high temperature, volcano hosted geothermal resources along its eastern branch and on the other hand dominantly fault controlled systems along the western and southern branches of EARS.

In line with this, UNEP in collaboration with ARGeo member countries and partners developed this technical guidebook on direct use application value chain that could benefit and empower the local communities through utilization of the indigenous resources. In this process, the geothermal energy resource would be a driver to achieve multiple Sustainable Development Goals including SDG 7.

The objective of this technical guidebook is to provide a tool that would be made available as such (in paper form or through the Web) translated in local languages and produced in various forms (Power Point Presentations, recorded lectures, booklets, etc.). The guidebook and its products could then be used anywhere in Africa for information, education, practical study by all concerned parties, such as individuals, local populations, private sector, public enterprises, NGOs, development agencies, financial agencies, banks as well as local, regional and national authorities. The first edition of the guidebook will be disseminated with the aim of generating feedback from the field, thus facilitating its successive improvement derived from the benefit of more local experiences. Case studies, success stories, etc. Will be progressively added in the guidebook and its annexes.

UNEP AFRICA OFFICE

Acknowledgments

UNEP thanks all member states and partners engaged in geothermal exploration and developments in Africa for their contribution and review of this technical guidebook. This guidebook widely used existing relevant case studies, publications and reports as a reference. Presentations and Publications in various conference proceedings, journals and books on the subject were also widely used, including sources like WB-ESMAP, IRENA, FAO, GRC and many others which cannot be all cited, but are referred to in the bibliography.

UNEP Africa Office Energy Unit team in collaboration with relevant member states took the lead in a continuous coordination and organisation of a series of review meetings with relevant stakeholders to receive technical input. The guidebook was improved and benefited from regular consultations of concerned stakeholders at national regional and international levels.

Contributors

The rationale to produce this guidebook is the result of the resolution of the 7th African Rift Geothermal (ARGeo) Conference (ARGeo C7) held in Kigali in 2018, which underscored the need for ad-hoc information and measures of public support for the subject of DU for geothermal development in Africa.

In line with this UNEP, through its ARGeo programme, hired a consultant Dr. Jacques Varet, Ressources Géologiques pour le Développement Durable¹ (Géo2D), to develop this guidebook in consultation with relevant member states. Susan Onyango edited the final version for language and coherence, contributed to the first draft's content, and wrote the gender section of the guidebook. Based on works with local populations along the EARV scientific papers have been published on the perspective of local geothermal development in Africa for several years now, contributing to the emergence of the subject at local, regional and national levels in the African region. The resulting first-hand experience, interactions with these local populations and data collected during these activities has informed the successive drafts of this guidebook, enriched by numerous contributions relating research and projects being acquired and developed in Africa.

The draft outline of the guidebook was prepared by a small group of experts led by UNEP (Meseret Zemedkun) assisted by Africa Geothermal Association (Peter Omenda) and reviewed by representatives of member states. The Energy Unit of UNEP Africa office is the main coordinator of preparation of this guidebook. The draft outline of the Guidebook was presented during the virtual eleventh steering committee meeting of ARGeo Development Facility

Programme's held in November 2020, back-to-back to the 8th ARGeo conference to which the respective countries' representatives and financial partners provided their input and comments.

The first draft was then revised taking into account the comments and input received from various stakeholders. It was then circulated among stakeholders and remarks and contributions were received and taken into account in the present version of the guidebook, including illustrations (figures, photos and tables). All relevant partners and member states interested to contribute were invited to take part in the implementation of the project from conception to final edition.

In its present form, the guidebook is validated and endorsed by the representatives of ARGeo member countries, and will be distributed to potential stakeholders including respective local populations through UNEP and other relevant stakeholders.

The first version is to be published in English. It will be given to the respective ARGeo member countries to produce editions of local declinations of the guidebook in other languages as deemed appropriate, eventually with formats adjusted to suit respective target groups (rural communities, pastoralist groups, crop farmers, peasant of fisheries, co-operative societies, cities, etc.).

With time, new editions will be edited, benefitting from the enhanced knowledge from the field experience and new stakeholders' contributions.

¹In English, translates to Geological Resources for Sustainable Development

Acronyms

AFD	Agence Française de Développement	GEF	Global Environment Facility
AfDB	African Development Bank	GGA	Global Geothermal Alliance
AFREC	African Energy Commission	GHPs	Ground-source Heat Pumps
AGA	African Geothermal Association	GJ	Gigajoule 10 ⁹ Joule
AGAP	Afar Geothermal Alternative Power Company (Ethiopia)	Géo2D	Ressources Géologiques pour le Développement Durable (SARL, France)
AGCE	African Geothermal Centre of Excellence	GJ	Giga Joule (1 GJ = 277,8 kWh)
AOC	Appellation d'Origine Contrôlée	GPA	GeoPower Africa (project supported by USAID)
ARGeo	African Rift Geothermal	GPS	Ground Positioning System
ARGeo C7	7th African Rift Geothermal Conference	GRC	Geothermal Resource Council
ARGeo C8	8th African Rift Geothermal Conference	GRMF	Geothermal Risk Mitigation Facility
AU	African Union	GSO	Geological Survey Organisation
AUC	African Union Commission	GWh	Gigawatt hour
BMU	German Ministry of Environment	EHESS	Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Sciences Sociales
BOP	Blow out preventer	HP	High Pressure
BOPE	Blow out prevention equipment	HT	High Temperature
BP	Before Present	HHGCBO	Homa Hills Geothermal Community-Based Organisation
BRGM	French Geological Survey	ICEIDA	Icelandic International Development Agency
CBO	Community-Based Organisation	IDB	Islamic Development Bank
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	IEA	International Energy Agency
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (France)	IFC	International Finance Corporation
CTCN	Climate Technology Centre and Network	IGA	International Geothermal Association
DEM	Digital Elevation Model	IGAD	Intergovernmental Authority for Development
DFID	Department for International Development (Great Britain)	IPs	Indigenous Peoples
DRC	Democratic Republic of Congo	IPP	Independent Power Producer
DU	Direct-Use (non electrical use of energy)	IPCC	International Panel for Climate Change
DUGD	Direct-Use Geothermal Development	IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
EARS	East African Rift System	J	Joule
EARV	Eastern Africa Rift Valley	JICA	Japan International Cooperation Agency
EDCL	Energy Development Corporation Limited (Rwanda)	KDF	Kuwait Development Fund
EDF	European Development Fund	KFW	Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau Bank for Reconstruction (Germany)
EEA	Ethiopian Energy Authority	kg	Kilogramme
EGA	Ethiopian Geothermal Association	KRV	Kenyan Rift valley
EIA	Energy Information Administration	kW	Kilowatt
EJ	Exajoules	kWe	Kilowatt electrical
EJP	European Joint Programme	kWh	Kilowatt hour
ESMAP	(WB) Energy Sector Management Assistance Programme (World Bank)	ky	thousand years
EU	European Union	l/s	litres per second
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation	MER	Main Ethiopian Rift
GAK	Geothermal Association of Kenya	MORs	Mid-Oceanic Ridges
Gcal	Gigacalorie	MT	Magnetotellurics.
GCV	Gross Calorific value	MW	Megawatt
GDC	Geothermal Development Company (Kenya)	Mwe	Megawatt electrical
GDP	Gross Domestic Product	MWth	Megawatt thermal
		My	Million years

NDF	Nordic Development Fund	UNIDO	United Nations Industrial Development Organisation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation		
NSF	National Science Foundation (USA)	USA	United States of America
ODDEG	Office Djiboutien de Développement de la Géothermie	USAID	United States Agency for International Development
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation & Development	USD	United States Dollar
ORC	Organic Rankin Cycle		
PJ	Petajoule (10^{15} Joule)		
PPI	Purchaser Price Index		
ppm	part per million		
PPP	Public-Private Partnership. Also used for: Purchasing Power Parities		
RAP	Resettlement Action Plan		
R&D	Research and Development		
RD&D	Research, Development and Demonstration		
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation		
RE	Renewable Energy		
REs	Renewable Energies		
RES	Renewable Energy Sources		
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations		
SARL	Société Anonyme à Responsabilité Limitée		
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals		
SEFA	Sustainable Energy Fund for Africa		
SEM	Société d'Economie Mixte		
SRREN	Special Report on Renewable Energy Sources and Climate Change Mitigation		
STP	Science and Technology Park		
t, kt, Mt	Metric ton=tonne=1000kg, kilo ton, Million ton		
TDEM	Time-Domain Electro-magnetics		
TEM	Transient Electro-magnetic Method		
TEM	Transient Electro-magnetics		
TFC	Total Final Consumption		
TGDC	Tanzania Geothermal Development Company		
TGH	Temperature Gradient Hole(s)		
TGW	Temperature Gradient Well		
TJ	Terajoule (10^{12} Joule)		
toe	tonne of oil equivalent= 10^7 kcal		
TPES	Total Primary Energy Supply		
TW	Terawatt (10^{12} watt)		
TWh	Terawatt hour		
UHT	Ultra-High Temperature (Ultra-Heat Treatment)		
UN	United Nations		
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme		
UNDRIPs	United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples		
UNEP	United Nation Environment Programme		
UNFCCC	United Nation Framework Convention for Climate Change		

Executive Summary

This technical guidebook is prepared in response to the request of the ARGeo member countries to UNEP to provide information and guidance on the exploration, development and utilisation of the shallow and of low to medium geothermal resources i.e. the heat naturally produced by our planet earth for direct use (DU) applications that contributes to sustainable development in Africa.

It was necessary to start the guidebook with a focus on geothermal energy resource utilization in Africa, as strangely, and shown in chapter 1, the resource utilisation in the African region is low compared to other continents. This focus made it necessary to re-examine the whole energy context in Africa, and also to highlight the geothermal energy resource development which have occurred historically and those that have been developed recently in Africa. As a result, it was possible to establish a current status of Direct Use Geothermal Development DUGD in Africa in this guidebook.

This was followed by indicating the geothermal resources occurrences in Africa. This newly undertaken survey allowed to distinguish the various geological and geodynamic conditions which determine the characteristics of the geothermal resources: the most promising being located along the Eastern branch of the East African Rift System (EARS), due to its high volcanicity in a context of crustal thinning and mantle uprise and partial melting. The guidebook goes on to show that such conditions also prevail along the Red-Sea and Gulf of Aden, with eventually even stronger heat flow releases, particularly in the Afar triangle where the oceanic rifts can be seen on the earth's surface. The Western branch of the EARS and Southern Rifts are considered separately, given that their characteristics differ with dominantly tectonic-controlled resources, and have rare, deeper sourced and less differentiated volcanic systems. The document then points out that the numerous sedimentary basins, of large size as found in stable parts of the continent, as well as in more localised grabens also have geothermal potential in these normal gradient areas where anticlines, domes, horsts or fault zones may offer geothermal resources conditions of interest. The so-called "Alpine" zone of North Africa, resulting from the continental collision of the Eurasian and African continents results in folded and eventually seismically active zones in which geological conditions provide geothermal opportunities whose value has been identified as such since time immemorial, exploited for baths by the Romans and by the Arabs as hammams. These areas also have resources at depth that can be valorised for DUGD, with significant developments already engaged in Tunisia, Algeria and Morocco. More localised and less considered are the oceanic and continental mantle plumes that provide locally hyper-thermal opportunities of geothermal value, and a few other specific geothermal occurrences that have been identified in this document in addition to the existing major contexts that have just been described herein.

The guidebook explains the specific exploration methods for shallow geothermal resources that are generally cheaper than for deep-seated geothermal systems. All steps in resource and DU project exploration and development are described including preliminary data collection, followed by

project planning. Suitability studies (at geothermal site level) imply the use of different methodologies depending upon the geological system considered. Volcanic, fault-controlled and sedimentary basins-hosted systems are successively considered and in each case, the specific geological, geochemical and geophysical methods are described allowing to produce the necessary geothermal conceptual model that will help to plan for the geothermal drilling, in some cases, the need for slim holes or geothermal gradient drilling. Feasibility studies can then be engaged, with drilling and surface engineering followed by development on site and site management. DUGD is particular in this respect as it generally allows for local spreading, given that geothermal sites, once identified can be expanded at limited costs. The local community benefiting from the resource acquire both skills and financial resources resulting from the initial production and resulting sales.

A few specificities of the DUGD are further underlined, in particular indicating how the approach enables uptake by the local community. The advantage offered by the cascaded utilisation of high temperature systems: A perspective just starting to be developed in Kenya. The different commercial and industrial developments allowed by DUGD are also underlined, particularly for shallow low to medium temperatures geothermal systems, which is open for a variety of applications that need to be known, demonstrated and spread at continent's scale.

Direct Use Devices and Technologies are then explained, starting with the key components and system design, first for the geothermal fluid production in cases of low to medium temperature as well as shallow steam resources. Although shallow geothermal fluids frequently allow for a direct use of the fluid itself in the whole geothermal device, heat exchangers are frequently necessary for environmental or health reasons, or justified for increased production capacities. The various possible options are presented and discussed. As DUGD projects will frequently concern isolated, off-grid sites, the opportunity to engage in electricity off-grid production and use is considered with a few specific options including small- sized ORC plants described. Noticeable is also the fact that DUGD – an advantage compared with other RE options - also allows for water production answering local needs in the most arid areas deprived of drinkable surface water (as only salty lakes are present, or open faults and highly permeable terrain induce immediate percolation at depth). At present, surface steam vents are frequently engineered with artisanal devices that allow for water condensation. The tradition therefore exists to exploit these resources but the systems could be improved with a high added value when ad-hoc modern solutions will be offered.

Another perspective for DUGD is to consider its possible introduction and development in Africa, particularly in the urban and peri-urban contexts, facilitated by technologies now spreading fast in the Northern hemisphere, that is, the introduction of heat pumps, either for heating purpose, but also – and more justified even in some hot places like Djibouti or Mombasa in Kenya – for cooling and air conditioning. When a large part of the electricity production is devoted to air conditioning, the geothermal heat pump solution

offers an option that will reduce the energy consumption by a factor of 4 to 6, the last highest figures being found for cases in which reversible heat pumps are used allowing for production of both heat and cold. The perspective of such technologies also concerns the improved cascade use of the geothermal resource including ORCs and successive thermal applications at decreasing temperatures using the same fluid with successive heat exchangers. The option to install technological parks and business incubators specifically devoted to geothermal R&D and deployment is also described.

An illustrated chapter (Ch. 6) is devoted to case studies of various DUs of geothermal energy successfully experienced world-wide, in view of introducing and spreading such development in Africa. The highlights start with caves and mushroom cultivation, which allow to directly benefit from the regular thermal and humidity conditions for food production of social and economic interest. Two major cases of aquaculture options are also described with the various kinds of fish farming that are open for geothermal development favoured by stable and precise thermal water conditions, or the cultivation of high protein content algae that can be dried and efficiently sold, with the example of Spirulina, as human or animal food. Various options of greenhousing are also described, either for local consumption or exports, as in the cases of flowers from Kenya or tomatoes and melons from Tunisia. The next option to be considered is crops, fruits and vegetables drying; an advantage with respect to the issue of production losses and added-value sales and exports. Similarly, dairy applications for milk pasteurisation, cheese production and concentrated or powder milk processing are also described in view of responding to specific conditions within the African continent. The option of fruit, wine and cheese maturation in geothermal caves is shown to be an option for high-added value products as developed in France with the AOC (appellations d'origine contrôlées²), which allows to valorize specific terroirs production processes. Fish processing is also an added value option for Africa where fish production and sales is eventually high in coastal and lake regions, where geothermal resource particularly allows for related economic developments. It is a paradox that geothermally dried fish imported from Iceland is sold in Africa, where until now, no such devices have been installed as yet! Abattoirs and other various agro-industrial processes can be made available, owing to geothermal resources available in pastoralist areas with eventually high production of herds, in poor preservation and sales conditions. Washing, peeling and blanching fruits and vegetable using geothermal fluids is also an advantageous option for local consumption and added value sales. A few geothermal health applications, like baths, swimming pools, hydrotherapy and spas developed rather early in Africa with for instance the various roman baths and hammams in North Africa, traditional steam bath and the establishing of Addis as the new capital of Ethiopia in a hot-spring area, or the development of hot-spring resorts in South Africa in the same 19th century period. But huge perspectives are open at present which are described, with some details provided for specific possible development of hot-spring resorts in link

with "geothermal village" implementations. When considering these perspectives, the option of valorisation of derived sanitary products should be considered having in mind the success of trademarks like Vichy or Blue Lagoon. In a more industrial perspective, chemical extraction is also to be considered as geothermal fluids generally contain chemical elements of specific economic interest, like silica, lithium, carbonic gas or hydrogen. One case of high added value is the business of bottled mineral water. For instance, the Ethiopian Ambo water is sold in various countries worldwide, as is the case for Vichy, Perrier or San Pelegrino products. Housing and district heating and or cooling is also shown to bear specific potentials due to climatic conditions prevailing in various places in Africa. To summarise this important chapter the last section explains how DU geothermal can be considered as an advantage for Circular Economy, an ecological perspective now favoured by financial agencies.

Sustainable Business Models for DUGD are then described. It is shown that Community-driven models should be favoured, as the resource is local and frequently used locally although artisanally. The engagement of local stakeholders in Community Based Organizations (CBOs) or specific enterprises owned by concerned partners on sites, as experienced by the Afar Geothermal Alternative Power Company (AGAP) are options which necessitate specific training and capacity building. Government-driven models are more easily implemented, with skilled personnel, as well as management and financial capacities. But the challenge here is to make sure the local community living on site benefits from the opportunity offered for private investors. The private sector driven option, implying Public-Private Partnership (PPP) and/or the engagement of Independent Power Producers (IPP) driving investments on site is also described.

A necessary condition for a successful development of DU in Africa (as everywhere else in the world) is to establish at national and/or regional level(s), enabling clear and coherent policy, institutional and legislative frameworks. On the side of the stakeholders, this implies demonstrated project management skills, which in turn underlines the need for a specific support system on the government side, with a specific Policy, Legal, and Regulatory Framework. Two African countries' cases are examined: Ethiopia where a specific cadre was established and Kenya where general rules apply for various renewable energy sources (RES) including geothermal. Both frameworks require adaptations as they are still lacking at present successful applications for DUGD³.

Given the institutional framework which obviously needs improvements in all African countries, the guidebook then examines the various key components required for efficient public policies. This includes the need to implement Research, Information and Capacity Building. The proposal presented here is based on the examination of the major components of the DUGD and the related manpower optimization and skills development. This in particular requires taking necessary measures to develop the African Engineering domain. In

²Appellations d'origine contrôlées (AOC) are delivered by public authorities to ensure the consumer on a well-defined and renown local origin of a product of defined quality, hence ensuring better sales.

³Except under state-owned enterprises initiatives (GDC and KenGen)

turn, this also necessitates the implementation of specific programs to generally share information with the public and for education, through media, schools, and also relevant political systems and structures (like parliament audits). Examples of EU financed projects in the field or R&D are described, hoping the programme being newly implemented will be sustained allowing for strong R&D African capabilities to further develop in universities, enterprises and CBOs.

A chapter is also devoted to economic and financial conditions (Ch. 10) in order to help implement Supportive Finance for DU projects. While it is shown that DUGD should always rely upon a Site Specific economy, funding sources for Africa are successively examined, including international as well as bilateral fundings opportunities. Most sources appear to be open for such developments, but adapted implementation means are still requested for these projects that are at rather small scales and not necessarily favoured by the currently existing financial procedures.

The last chapter of this guidebook is devoted to specific Environmental and Social dimensions prevailing for DUGD. First it is shown how DUGD differs from classical geothermal projects, as social considerations come first, even before geoscientific investigations, as it is the nature of the demand which determines the geothermal resource to be looked for. The specificities of these project implementations are underlined. It is also shown, in a global and even ethical perspective, that such choices are typical components of a holistic environment, implying friendly interactions between geosphere, hydrosphere and biosphere including of course human beings. They are exemplary cases of sustainability and resilience. As such they justify priority inclusion in National Strategic Policies; in particular, Climate Policies.

The guidebook ends with a conclusion that is worth reading.

A list of references includes both early reports and most recent publications on the subject.

*A hot spring at Lake Bogoria, Kenya.
Photo credit: Valentina Storti/flickr*

CHAPTER 1:

BACKGROUND

1.1 Introduction

This technical guidebook is prepared in response to the request of the ARGeo member countries to UNEP to provide for DU applications; information and guidance on the exploration, utilisation and development of the shallow and of low to medium geothermal resources i.e. the heat naturally produced by our planet earth that contributes to sustainable development in Africa.

This request was made on the basis of the identification of the nature of geothermal resources existing in the Western branch of the EARS during the UNEP technical workshop on the Western branch of the EARS held in Kigali, Rwanda in 2016. This workshop has been recognised by all member states and partners as a game changer where it distinctively acknowledged the different nature and methodology of exploration of the geothermal resources of the Western branch compared to the Eastern branch of the EARS (Omenda, et.al, 2016). The recommendation of stakeholders who attended the ARGeo C7 held in Kigali, Rwanda in November 2018 and the virtual ARGeo C8 transmitted from Nairobi, Kenya in November 2020 requested UNEP and partners to focus on mainstreaming the DU application further to power generation in Africa. These conferences noted that besides electricity generation which was the main focus for countries of the EARS, there was a need to change track and consider exploration and development of DU of geothermal resources in Africa. This in fact considering the wide and fast development of this type of geothermal application worldwide, and also the diversified nature of the geothermal resource in the EARS with well-developed high temperature, volcano-hosted geothermal resources along its Eastern branch and dominantly fault-controlled systems along the Western and Southern branches of EARS.

Considering the geological setting and also the socio-economic characteristics of the demand, this guidebook therefore illustrates: (i) the variety of geothermal resource exploration for low-medium geothermal systems; and (ii) possible DU applications in the African context and analyses the conditions for their success. The guidebook considers development at local, community, national and regional levels taking into consideration the requisite enabling environment. The role of the private sector, as well as the need for a specific engineering and local equipment construction offers are discussed. The report further analyses the need for information dissemination, awareness creation, education and capacity development initiatives among concerned populations as determinants for successful DU projects. It is also noted that DU applications are climate-friendly energy alternatives which offer the best solutions for low carbon, climate resilience and resource efficiency, particularly in the most arid areas where geothermal can provide both energy and water independently of the degrading meteoritic conditions. This technical guidebook therefore is meant to be used by all stakeholders who aim to utilise geothermal resources for DU application in order to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Geothermal resources due to their possible diversified applications that range from electricity, heat, water, and food production is a good model in the frame of the ecological transition in which various numerous parties are engaged in the present century.

1.2 Rationale for the technical guidebook

DU geothermal devices imply short-circuit, locally installed, and eventually off-grid systems in which the natural geological resource is used on site for a variety of applications answering the needs of the population living there. It provides a solution of resilience improving the population's livelihoods. There are numerous local populations living around geothermal resources in the African region. It so happens that while these local inhabitants around geothermal resources in Africa, happen to live in far-flung, often difficult-to-access, remote areas, a good number of them are also known to be inheritors and practitioners of unique cultures, and to have developed their ways of relating in close symbiosis with their natural environment. Some of them fit the characteristics of IPs as stipulated in various documents such as the UNDRIPs or The Indigenous Peoples Commission of the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights.⁴ Surface geothermal resources are part of their natural environment and these local populations generally use them artisanally; however, without knowing the extent of their depth or the technology that could be used to improve and adjust the resources' production to meet some of the population's socio-economic needs.

Facing the challenge of undertaking the kind of geothermal resource development that would respond to the socio-economic needs of the populations that reside along geothermal sites in Africa (as in other parts of the world with a similar context) requires a specific approach, radically different from the one prevailing currently in geothermal energy development, which is , based on the objective – generally implemented by large public or private companies - to feed the electric grid under contract with electricity off-takers. In the case of DUGD, a holistic approach is required including knowledge of: the resource characteristics even at shallow depth, as well as the diversity of technologies available, and even more important, to master the anthropological, social and economic dimensions of the project, as it always implies a direct involvement of the actors living on site who this approach considers should be the first beneficiaries. The political and administrative background in this approach also differs from the large-sized projects (with a major role played by the co-operatives, NGOs, CBOs and local public entities at the municipal, county or the country's regional level).

Basically, such development relies first upon the local population's knowledge, involvement and ownership of a given initiative, but at this point in time, still requires technological capabilities to be hired from outside of the enterprises, development aid and financial agencies. Multilateral and bilateral organizations are also primarily concerned, as the targeted groups are in fact victims of climate change which they are not responsible for, but for

⁴See for example Report of The African Commission's Working Group of Experts on Indigenous Populations/Commissions submitted in accordance with the Resolution on the Rights of Indigenous Populations/Communities in Africa dated 2005; Adopted by The African Commission on Human and People's Rights at its 28th ordinary session. See also UNDRIPs adopted by the UN General Assembly on Thursday, 13 September 2007

which geothermal development offers mitigation, adaptation as well as low carbon, resource efficient and climate resilient solutions. In the driest parts of the EARV, the only viable alternative option to deal with climate change effects is often mitigation.

It is against this backdrop that UNEP in collaboration with ARGeo member countries and partners developed this technical guidebook on DU application value chain that could benefit and empower local populations through utilisation of the indigenous geothermal resources. In this process, the geothermal energy resource would be a driver to achieve multiple SDGs.

1.3 Global perspectives in geothermal resource utilisation

At present, geothermal resource is being utilised by more than 90 countries globally for both power generation and DU applications. Geothermal power plants are operating in 24 countries with a total installed power generation capacity of 15,400 MW in 2019. Based on installed capacity, leading countries are the USA, Indonesia, Philippines, Turkey, New Zealand and Mexico. With on-going development in Africa where countries like Kenya and Ethiopia are fast-tracking their geothermal projects and the global upsurge in geothermal projects, the situation will change in the next decade. The global figure, therefore, exceeds 28,000 MWe, out of which 4,500 MW could be added in 2020-2025 (IGA, 2020).

Table 1.1: Ranges of technical potential (yearly availability) of RES
Source: IPCC (2011). EJ = exajoules

No.	Source	EJ/year
1.	Hydro power	50 – 52
2.	Biomass	50 – 500
3.	Solar Energy	1,575 – 49,837
4.	Wind Energy	85 – 580
5.	Geothermal Energy	128 – 1,421
	Total	1,888 – 52,390

These local geothermal solutions, once generalized in Africa, will provide a major contribution in attaining global and African development initiatives, i.e. the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and "2063: The Africa We Want".

Relative to the global energy sector, the contribution of geothermal is rather low at less than 1 per cent; a percentage that should be increased in 2050 when renewables are expected to take over 90 per cent of the global electricity generation, according to the road map for the global energy sector published by the IEA (2021).

In the present era of energy transition, the potential use of geothermal resources remains high, compared to other RES such as hydro, solar and wind. However, the question arises of which part of the technical potential can be harnessed in a way that is acceptable economically, environmentally and socially.

Geothermal energy displays some noticeable advantages compared to other RES as indicated below:

- High capacity factor of more than 90 per cent for geothermal energy compared to 55 per cent for bio-energy; 44 per cent for hydropower; 23 per cent for wind energy and 13 per cent for solar energy.
- The diversity of its application is possible on a given site, including electricity, heat and other DUs in addition to water and mineral extraction.
- A modular growth at local level, both quantitatively and qualitatively, with improving economic conditions due to the risk reduction with time.

However geothermal projects suffer from a handicap: high geological risks (despite improving exploration methods); high upfront investment costs for geoscientific investigations, drilling well costs, transmission lines, steam gathering system and power plants. These costs are, however, reduced in case of utilisation of shallow resources for DU applications that require low to medium temperatures.

Geothermal resources have been developed to a very small extent until now worldwide, and particularly in Africa. There

Fig. 1.1: Ranges of global technical potentials of RES. Note the figure is presented in logarithmic vertical scale due to the wide range of assessed data (IPCC SRREN, 2012).

is ample space for engaging new and innovative solutions and accelerated use of geothermal energy both for DU applications such as ground-source heat pumps for space heating or cooling and for electricity generation. Table 1.2 indicates the range of estimates of global technical potential in the world.

Table 1.3 shows the number of geothermal countries in each of the groups defined by the World Bank, from high income to low income and the number of the top 15 using geothermal for electricity production and DU (heating and cooling), respectively. It appears that electricity production with geothermal is relatively evenly spread between countries of different economic categories, whereas only one UMC (Turkey) and one LIC (China) are featuring in the top 15 of the list of DU. This kind of categorisation can signal the areas in which the most scope for capacity development initiatives in developing countries lie.

In terms of growth during the past decade and forthcoming years, Bertani (2015) analyzed the data taken from country update reports and from other sources at the occasion of the successive World Geothermal Congresses, showing a linear growth of 400MW/year in terms of installed capacity, and

Table 1.2 Range of Estimates of Global Technical Potentials
Source: IPCC (2012). EJ = exajoules

No.	Energy Source	Max (EJ/yr)	Min (EJ/yr)
1.	Geothermal	1,109	118
2.	Hydro power	52	50
3.	Ocean Energy	331	7
4.	Wind Energy	580	85
5.	Geothermal	312	10
6.	Biomass	500	50
7.	Direct Solar Energy	4,937	1,575

Table 1.3: Top 15 countries producing and using geothermal energy sources
Source: Data on electricity from Bertani (2010) and on DU from Lund et al. (2010).
GWh/year = gigawatt hours per year.

No.	Country	Geothermal electricity production, 2010 (GWh/year)	Country	Geothermal DU, 2009 (GWh/year)
1.	USA	16,603	China	20,932
2.	Philippines	10,311	USA	15,710
3.	Indonesia	9,600	Sweden	12,585
4.	Mexico	7,047	Turkey	10,247
5.	Italy	5,520	Japan	7,139
6.	Iceland	4,597	Norway	7,001
7.	Japan	3,064	France	3,592
8.	Kenya	1,430	Germany	3,546
9.	El Salvador	1,422	Netherlands	2,972
10.	Costa Rica	1,131	Italy	2,762
11.	Turkey	490	Hungary	2,713
12.	Papua New Guinea	450	New Zealand	2,654
13.	Russia	441	Canada	2,465
14.	Nicaragua	310	Finland	2,325
15.	Guatemala	289	Switzerland	2,143

a sharper increase in terms of energy produced (Fig. 1.2).

The total number of countries generating electricity is 24. Two of them; Kenya and Ethiopia are in Africa. (Fig. 1.3). Kenya appears in position 5 for MWe installed in 2020 (Table 1.5 from Hutterer, 2020). Among other countries with the highest percentage share of geothermal in their national electricity production, one can notice four from Latin America (Costa Rica, El Salvador, Guatemala and Nicaragua and one African; Kenya), all with potential for harnessing much more. The EARS, where a divergent type of plate boundary allows for exceptionally high heat flows in a continental environment (most rifts zones are unfortunately sub-oceanic) should become a major zone of geothermal development, similar to the Gulf region for oil (Varet, 2010). Table 1.6 summarises the DU data worldwide by region and continent in 2019 (from Lund & Toth, 2020). The same authors also show that no African country appears at present among the worldwide leaders in DU of geothermal energy, either in terms of total power or relative to population (Table 1.6)

It is interesting to note that the type of electricity generators used worldwide vary and include back pressure, dry steam, single flash, double flash, triple flash, binary and hybrid. Binary plants, although developed in the market more recently than other plants tend to increase in percentage, although the average capacity (in MWe/unit) and average energy produced per unit (GWh/unit) is the smallest (Fig. 1.4). This results from a technology that allows using wide temperature range from high to medium temperature fluids for electricity generation, and also fits the needs of local communities eventually utilising shallower (hence less costly) geothermal resources.

Meeting less than 0.5 per cent of global heat demand, geothermal is at present the smallest renewable heat source. Bathing and space heating are the prevalent applications globally, with development remaining limited to a few

World Geothermal Electricity

Fig. 1.2: Installed capacity from 1950 to 2015 (Bertani, 2015)

Fig. 1.3: Installed geothermal capacity in the world, per country (Bertani, 2015)

Table 1.4: Number of countries in different economic categories using geothermal for electricity production and DU in 2010
Source: Fridleifsson (2012).

*As defined by the World Bank.

No.	Economic category*	Number of countries	Electricity production	DU
1.	High-income OECD	29	5	14
2.	High-income non-OECD	3	-	-
3.	Upper-Middle (UMC)	22	4	1
4.	Lower-Middle (LMC)	21	6	-
5.	Low Income (LIC)	4	1	1

Table 1.5: Ten nations having the most installed geothermal power generation in 2020
Source: Hutterer (2020).

*Corrected for Kenya according to Omenda et al. (2020)

No.	Country	MWe Installed in 2020
1.	USA	3,700
2.	Indonesia	2,289
3.	Philippines	1,918
4.	Turkey	1,549
5.	Kenya	865
6.	Mexico	1,105
7.	New Zealand	1,064
8.	Italy	916
9.	Japan	550
10.	Iceland	755

Table 1.6: Summary of DU data worldwide by region and continent in 2019
Source: Lund & Toth (2020)

Region/Continent (#countries/regions)	MWt	TJ/year	GWh/year	Capacity Factor
Africa (11)	198	3,730	1,036	0.597
Americas (17)	23,330	180,414	50,115	0.245
Central America and Caribbean (5)	9	195	54	0.687
North America (4)	22,700	171,510	47,642	0.24
South America (8)	621	8,709	2,419	0.4545
Asia (8)	49,079	545,019	151,394	0.352
Commonwealth of Independent States (5)	2,121	15,907	4,419	0.238
Europe (34)	32,386	264,843	73,568	0.259
Central and Eastern Europe (17)	3,439	28,098	7,805	0.259
Western and Northern Europe (17)	28,947	236,745	65,762	0.259
Oceania (3)	613	10,974	3,048	0.568
Total (88)	107,727	1,020,887	283,580	0.300

countries. China and Turkey alone account for more than 84 per cent of geothermal heat consumption world-wide (Tracking SDG7: The Energy Progress Report, 2020). DU of geothermal resource increased by 6.8 per cent in 2017, contributing just over 0.6 EJ to the RE supply.

Although encountering a fast growth during the past decade due to the spreading of GHPs, DU application is less known and hence less developed worldwide and particularly in Africa. The development was facilitated by improved technologies, hence more efficient and cheaper due to mass production, but also because these technologies utilise groundwater or even dry ground-coupled temperatures for space heating and/or cooling and may operate anywhere in the world regardless of the geology. Of course, this development relates to the demand for heating of buildings in the Northern hemisphere, which frequently represents 30 to 50 per cent of the total primary energy consumption. But these and other technologies also allow for cooling, which represent an important part of the energy budget in many African countries. In a city like Djibouti, up to 70 per cent of the total electricity consumption is for cooling of the buildings (offices or housing). Therefore, even for Southern countries, this is a sector in which there is the most potential for development, as space and water consumptions form significant parts of the energy budget, owing to the fact that the potential in this sector still remains largely untapped.

The potential for geothermal DU is very large because such applications are significant parts of the energy budget in many parts of the world, a budget that should increase to address the adaptation to climate change, and more generally to contribute to better livelihoods and consequently, improved well-being. Even in Africa, the perspective for DU geothermal resource development is very important, and can be used in activities such as bathing, greenhouse cultivation, aquaculture, milk pasteurisation, food preservation (for example grains, fruits, vegetables, meat, fish through drying), to improve people's diet and nutrition thus people's quality of life. In addition, tourism is often a substantial source of income at geothermal locations, for thermal baths or spas, particularly in the case of ecotourism and balneotherapy, inclusive for local communities, allowing for mutual economic and cultural benefits. This will directly create social, economic and environmental impacts in the context of achieving the global (Agenda 2030) and continental (AU Agenda 2063) and Paris Agreement on climate change (2015) goals.

According to the IEA (2021) special report Net Zero by 2050, geothermal electricity generation should grow from 94 TWh in 2020 to 330 in 2030, 625 in 2040 and 823 TWh in 2050 reaching then 1 per cent in the total share; whereas the installed capacity would rise from 15 TW in 2020 to 52 in

Type	Average energy (GWh/unit)	Average capacity (MWe/unit)
Binary	31	6.3
Back pressure	76	7.0
Single flash	179	30.4
Double flash	231	37.4
Triple flash	500	90.8
Dry steam	253	45.4

Fig. 1.4: Type of plant used for electricity production in the world (A: total power installed and B: average size and capacity). Bertani (2015)

2030, 98 in 2040 and 126 TW in 2050. However, according to the same road map, it is in the DUs that geothermal should experience the fastest growth, reaching for instance 12 per cent in the building heating sector in 2050 (compared to 2 per cent in 2020). Geothermal should in particular play a major role in "zero carbon buildings" (or so called "positive energy buildings"). Similar increases in DU should be reached by geothermal for the industry sector.

1.4 Geothermal Energy Resource Utilization in Africa

1.4.1 The energy context in Africa

The energy consumption per capita in Africa, and sub-Saharan Africa in particular, remains low compared to the rest of the world, and its access to electricity is the lowest in the world (Fig. 1.5). In 2018, the energy consumption was only 6.7 Giga Joule (GJ)⁵ per capita in sub-Saharan Africa compared with 15 for the whole of Africa, 56.4 for South and Central America, and 60.2 for South and East Asia. It was

higher in industrialised regions like Europe (127.4) and the Community of Independent States (CIS = 160.9) as well as in the Middle East (148.5) and the highest in North America where it amounts to 239.8 (British Petroleum, 2019). With time, the tendency has not shown improvements for Africa in the last 35 years (Fig. 1.6). Within Africa, the highest deficit is seen in Eastern and Central Africa (Fig. 1.7). In the scenarios developed by the International Energy Agency (IEA, (2020), the electricity demand will increase in Africa in 2040, however remaining low compared with other regions of the world (Fig. 1.8).

In the case of RE, besides a very irregular situation across the continent and large geographical areas (with the exception of North Africa), in sub-Saharan Africa, Southern, Central and Eastern Africa have the best average indicators (Fig. 1.9). At first glance, these parts of the continent appear to be a leader in the number of population members /size of population that have /has access to RE compared with developed countries in the north and many Asian countries. However, the analysis shows that this leadership is linked to a very high use of traditional biomass (Fire-wood and

Fig. 1.5: Planisphere showing the access to electricity (per cent of population) in the world. The 20 countries with the largest access deficits are labeled with black icon (IEA, IRENA, UNSD, World Bank, WHO. 2022)

Fig. 1.6: Evolution of the energy consumption per capita (in Giga Joules per head) between 1985 and 2018 in various regions in the world. (British Petroleum, 2019)

⁵GJ = 277,8 kWh

Fig. 1.7: Map of Africa showing the state of population without access to electricity (average per country in per cent of the population). Source: The Economist, 2016)

Fig. 1.8: Electricity demand (total and per capita) in thousand TWh for in the future (2040) according to scenarios of the International Energy Agency (IEA, 2020)

charcoal) for cooking (Fig.1.10) coupled with low electricity consumption (many tens of millions of Africans do not have access to electricity).

Analysis reported by Sene (2018) shows that the Rio Summit of 1992 was marked by an increase in development aid for RE projects. However, since then, following the Kyoto Conference in 1997, the Kyoto Protocol Agreement and its ratification in 2005, rather reversed this trend. The market indicated a gradual decline in the price of RE technologies and a real perspective of the increase of RE production and consumption in Africa in the future, despite the present temporary low prices for fossil fuels.

The special report of IPCC on REs published in 2012 shows that REs have competitive advantage over fossil fuels, both for electricity and direct heat production, with geothermal among the most competitive for both kinds of applications (Fig. 1.1).

It however appears that the African continent is also a large consumer market for RE products from abroad rather than a real producer, despite its huge potential for RE such as

wind, solar, hydro, bio-energy and geothermal energy. There is therefore a real challenge for Africa, not only to increase its RE production and consumption, but also to increase RE products and management know-how.

1.4.2. The on-going geothermal energy resource development in Africa

When thinking of energy development in Africa, what immediately comes to mind, and is also in most of the literature, is solar energy. Wind and hydro are also frequently quoted. However, there is still a considerable knowledge gap when it comes to geothermal energy (Fig.1.12), particularly in Eastern Africa where geological conditions are exceptionally favourable for both power generation and DU applications (Varet, 2014; Teklemariam, 2016; among others).

Despite this knowledge gap, geothermal energy is at present gaining credibility and momentum in Eastern Africa with large-sized plants producing electricity and feeding the national grid. Besides, existing power plants in Kenya with installed capacity of more than 865MW as of 2020

Fig. 1.9: Renewable energy consumption (% of total final energy consumption) (World Bank, 2022)

Fig. 1.10: proportion of total population primarily using clean cooking fuels and technologies for cooking in 2020 in Africa. (World Bank, 2022)

Fig. 1.11: Range of recent levelised cost of energy for selected commercially available RE technologies in comparison to recent non-RE costs. Technology sub-categories and discount rates were aggregated. Geothermal electricity includes both condensing flash and binary-cycle (ORC) plants, whereas geothermal heat includes greenhouses, uncovered aquaculture ponds, district heating, geothermal building heating and heat pumps. (IPCC, 2012).

and Ethiopia about 7.3 MWe, numerous projects are now emerging. This is due to the quality of the natural resource in the region's rift valley, where geothermal gradients are far above the average and well-developed convective systems exist allowing steam to reach the surface. The technically as well as economically successful initiatives in Kenya have further encouraged emergence of new projects in the rest of the African countries in the region. The on-going development also results from the efficiency of the regional facilities and procedures implemented during the last few years (among others); the UNEP ARGeo programme and Geothermal Resource Mitigation Facility (GRMF) managed by the Africa Union Commission with the support of EU and European countries (German BMU, British DFID),.

The on-going developments - although efficient and eventually spectacular with large-sized plants feeding the national grid (Fig. 1.13) – however, provide relatively, lower benefit to the local economies where the plants are located, particularly when located in remote areas. Even on the sites being developed, the situation created by the developers may turn to a situation in which local populations develop the feeling that the related energy infrastructure eventually passes “over their heads”, or may get negatively impacted by being involuntarily resettled. This unsustainable approach appears as a paradox when one observes that the geothermal

resource in the region is in fact located along the rift floor, in low-land areas, which are drier, and where often, pastoralist populations, generally fitting the description of IPs live. Heavily affected by climate change, they are more and more vulnerable to drought and famine.

1.4.3. Current status of Direct-Use Geothermal Development in Africa

As indicated above, geothermal has a versatile use where it contributes not only to the production of electricity for the grid, but also allows for a variety of DUs at the local community level through the utilization of small-sized geothermal devices. These uses include production of water, sanitary use, agronomy, and diversified energy uses at various levels (including thermal and electricity). Whereas, as seen above (paragraph 1.1) DU systems devices are the most developed worldwide, strangely enough though, they are not widely used in Africa (Fig.1.14). This gap and the need for specific efforts to utilise the resource so as to drive the socio-economic aspects of the African countries were considered in various regional conferences (see for instance: ARGeo C7, Kigali, Rwanda, 2018; Virtual ARGeo C8, Nairobi, Kenya, 2020). Various institutional actors such

Fig. 1.12: Share of renewables in total gross capacity additions by region in the New Policies Scenario 2018-2040. The share for Africa is far from being the highest. Solar, hydro and wind are dominant and Africa shows the best figure for “other” (which includes geothermal). IEA (2020)

Fig. 1.14: Installed capacity of geothermal DU by regions worldwide in 2020. DU of geothermal energy is widespread worldwide, but still rather ignored in Africa (Lund & Toth, 2020)

Fig. 1.13: Partial aerial view of the Olkaria geothermal site in the Central Rift Valley of Kenya, serving the electrical base-load of the whole country's inter-connected grid. Note the wells, drilled at circa 2500m depth, the fluid-gathering system for steam directed towards one of the electric production units (140MWe), and the separated brine which is re-injected in the geothermal reservoir (Photo credit: J.Varet, 2013).

as the AfDB, the AUC- GRMF and ESMAP of the World Bank (Tryggvadóttir et al. 2020) and the USAID (2013), with Power Africa (2014); IRENA (2018) are engaging actions to support this specific energy sector.

In North Africa (Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, and Egypt), there are numerous examples of natural hot-springs used for water and steam baths in traditional hammams of roman-built spas (see below Fig. 2.28 & 2.29). Some of them have been modernized in order to increase the visit from external users (tourists or medical cares). In addition, a few examples of DUGD have recently been developed in North Africa under government policies, for agro-industrial developments, particularly through large green-housing farms (Fig. 1.15) devoted to vegetable production for local consumption and export.

In South Africa, there are 87 documented hot-springs, out of which at least 20 are converted into thermal resorts. One of the best known (since 1873) is called Bela Bela meaning "the boiling pit" in Towana people's language who have managed the place for centuries for various traditional uses.

The only examples of operational DUGD in Eastern Africa are located in existing electricity production sites at Olkaria, Eburru and Menengai and for recreational and heating in Filweha, Ghion, Hilton and Sheraton hotels in Addis Ababa, and along the rift in Sodere, Boku, etc.. in Ethiopia.

In Ethiopia, the presence of natural hot-springs was among the reasons for the choice of location of the capital city of the country, Addis Ababa, in the 19th century by Emperor Menelik II and his wife Empress Taytu Betul. The Empress

Fig. 1.15: Installed capacity of geothermal DU by kind as at 2020, worldwide (A) and in Africa (B). (Lund & Toth, 2020)

established her house near the hot-springs in 1886; prior to the establishment of Addis Ababa as the capital of the country by Menelik II in 1889. The location was called Finfinne meaning hot-springs in the Oromo language. The compound of the Palace included Ghion hotel which still use thermal water as sanitary hot water in the guest rooms (Fig. 1.16). Nearby Hilton and Sheraton are more recent hotels that also use the natural hot water for open air baths and therapy purposes. The popular Sodere hot-spring resort near Adama along the Awash River was built in 1963, whereas Filwoha baths were established in 1966 in the Awash National Park, both under Emperor Haile Selassie.

In Kenya, the earliest documented DU of geothermal resources was at Eburru in the central part of the Kenya rift where a dryer was installed in 1939 and is used to date by local farmers for pyrethrum and grain drying. However, the system is currently used to dry mainly maize as pyrethrum is no longer an important cash crop in the area (Ndeti, C. 2021). At Naivasha, near Olkaria (Kenya), geothermally powered large flower greenhouses are owned and managed by Oserian Development Company (Knight et al., 2006) for flowers production (roses), while KenGen has developed a spa and thermal bath managed commercially, with plans to develop a platform for other DU applications (Mangi, 2013). At Menengai, GDC installed a demonstration pilot system for a variety of DU applications including green-housing, milk processing, laundry, aquaculture and a semi commercial grain dryer (Lukmana, 2020; Njuguna, 2020).

Hot Springs are used for popular baths and tourist attractions in several places in Uganda, the most popular being Kitagata, in Sheema District with a temperature up to 80°C. It is said to have been used by the King of Ankole. Other reknown thermal sites in Uganda are, among others, Sempaya, Rwagimba, Amoropii, Buranga, Ihimba and Kiribo.

Songwe geothermal project is located in South western Tanzania, near the south-Eastern tip of Lake Rukwa. The site is about 10 km from the Tanzania-Zambia tarmac road, 40 km from Mbeya Airport, and about 40 km from Mbeya Tazara railway station. The temperature at Songwe main spring is between 55°C to 82°C; flow rate is 50-75 l/s, estimated reservoir temperature is 112 ± 16 °C. Besides agro-industrial developments, like Hatchery and greenhousing, tourism provides local employment, brings forex into the economy and enhances foreign exchange balance. For the purpose of diversifying tourism attractions in Tanzania, TGDC is implementing a pilot geo-tourism centre at Songwe centre. The aim is to utilize geothermal water (mineralised hot water) for recreation, wellness and balneotherapy. Construction of geothermal swimming pools, hot tabs, and soaking pools is underway.

Fig. 1.16: Swimming pool fed by thermal water at the Olkaria Geothermal Spa
Photo credit: Benedict Steingrimsson/flickr

CHAPTER 2:

GEOHERMAL RESOURCES

OCCURRENCES IN AFRICA

The African continent is traversed by a major, exceptional geodynamic structure, which is unique on the planet earth: the EARS; an active plate boundary, which despite the spreading of the sea-floor has however not yet reached the stage of continental separation. A progressive increase of the spreading rate, from 1 to 6 mm/year is seen from South to North due to the slow motion of the Somalia plate towards East, whereas in Afar the spreading rate reaches 2 cm/year due to the separation of Arabia from Africa towards North East with the production of a basaltic crust created along spreading segments showing volcanological and petrological similitudes with MORs and sea floors (Barberi et al., 1970, 1972; Tazieff et al., 1972; Barberi & Varet, 1975; 1977). Northern Afar, still largely below sea level was in fact under the sea in the recent Holocene period (Fig. 2.1).

2.1 Eastern branch of the East African Rift System

The Eastern branch of the EARS, crossing through Eritrea, Djibouti, Ethiopia, Kenya and Tanzania is the most spectacular, with plateaus at high altitude, having developed agricultural areas, thanks to favourable climatic conditions (periodical rainfalls), and bordering with a low-land valley where active volcanic and tectonic conditions favour the development of high temperature geothermal sites. These are particularly

dominant in places where large volcanic units developed along local discontinuities of the rift system (Fig. 2.2).

As a result, with an average interval of 40 to 60 km coinciding with sites of Quaternary volcanism, in the KRV and MER, high temperature sites allow for large-sized plants to produce power feeding the electrical grid. But so far, only a few of them have been explored and even less produce power as yet (Fig. 2.3).

The geothermal sites are characterized by shallow magma chambers – frequently related to calderas and recent silicic domes - and the development of reservoir conditions at temperatures of 150 to more than 300°C, thanks to fractured brittle rocks at depth of 1,000 to 3,500 metres, covered by an impermeable clay cap (Fig. 2.4). Olkaria and Menengai in Kenya are references for such sites.

Besides these high temperature sites, normal faults and open fissures allow for convective systems to develop at other sites, with hot-springs (Fig. 2.5 and 2.6) or even steam vents at the surface (Fig. 2.7 and 2.8). With the capture of the fluid at the surface, or better through shallow drilling, small plants will allow for DUGD, answering local socio-economic needs and various kinds of developments described below with low investment costs.

Fig. 2.1: The EARS, with major fault systems (in red), major earthquake location (white dots for $M > 5$), manifestations of Quaternary volcanism (in yellow) and plate-motion vectors with GPS velocities (black arrows, with numbers in mm/y). Note the progressive increase of the spreading rate from South to North along the EARV (from 2 mm/y in the KRV5 to 7 mm/y along the MER and up to 2 cm/y in Afar). Calais (2016)

Fig. 2.2: Map of the volcanoes along the EARS. While only a few are located along the Western branch, the Eastern branch is characterised by the high number of volcanic centres (red triangles are quaternary volcanoes).

Map from: www.riftvolc.geos.ed.ac.uk.

Fig. 2.3: Geothermal resource sites for electricity production identified (A: Left) in Kenya and (B: Right) Status of Geothermal Exploration and Development in Ethiopia (from Omenda, 2012; 2018).

Fig. 2.4: Schematic model of a volcano hosted geothermal system. Source: Hilman et al., 2020

Fig. 2.5: Hot-springs along a fault affecting trap-basalts North of Fantale volcano in Awash National Park, Filowa resort, Southern Afar, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia
(Photo J.Varet, 2014)

Fig. 2.6: Hot-springs along fault bordering Lake Bogoria (Kenya), the site, where hydrothermal deposits developed, attracts fishes and flamingos
(Photo J.Varet, 2013)

Fig. 2.7: Steam vents along a fault affecting basaltic lava flows in central Afar (Ethiopia), a kind of manifestation that is quite frequent along the EARS, and Afar in particular, where these have a local name: "boina". A shallow geothermal resource presently essentially untapped.
(Photo J.Varet 1969).

Fig. 2.8: Steaming fault affecting a rhyolite flow near Olkaria, Kenya
(Photo J.Varet, 2014)

As a whole, the Eastern branch of the EARS allows for DUGD in 3 types of scenarios:

- As a by-product of high temperature geothermal sites, using the temperature of the brine produced after steam separation and before re-injection;
- Along active fissures affecting the rift floor away from the volcanic centres;
- Along normal faults bordering the rift system, particularly within marginal grabens as seen all along the Nubian escarpment in Ethiopia (Fig. 2.9).

Note that – as seen in Fig. 2.1 - the spreading rate increases from South to North, and therefore higher geothermal conditions will progressively be encountered from Southern Tanzania to the Northern part of the MER.

Fig. 2.9: Left: Google map showing the limit of the Nubian plateau: On the right (West) the Nile hydrographic basin, on the left (East) the Afar depression and the Awash River basin (Ethiopia); marginal grabens developed along the escarpment. Location of major hot-springs sites, circa 100°C (from North to South: Harbu, Shekla, Borkena and Shewa Robit) are shown in yellow. Also shown, the nearest steam vents in the Afar depression (in red). The border between the Amhara and Afar regional states is also drawn (white dotted lines). Right: Geological interpretative section of the hydrogeological system feeding the geothermal systems (respectively hot-springs and steam vents) in the marginal graben - affecting the pre-Miocene "basement" made here of trap-basalts from the Nubian plateau - and Southern Afar volcanic ranges built along faults and dikes of NNE-SSW (MER) direction. Appropriate geophysical methodologies are being developed to properly map in 3D, the convective geothermal plumbing system to be tapped by shallow drilling for local developments. (Onyango & Varet, 2018)

2.2 Red-Sea and Gulf of Aden

Along the side of Oceanic Rifts: favourable geothermal conditions are found thanks to convective systems that have developed along normal faults, showing thermal springs all along the Red Sea shore in Egypt, Sudan, Eritrea, and along the Gulf of Aden in Djibouti and Somaliland.

The Afar triangle displays specific geodynamic conditions as it does not result from the slow-spreading separation of the Nubian and Somalian plate, but from the respective separation of the Arabian plate from the African plate (as seen in Fig. 1.14 & 2.1). With a much higher spreading rate of circa 2 cm a year, compared to 2 mm a year in the KRV. In this area of the Afar triangle (found in Ethiopia, Eritrea and Djibouti), the MOR system, elsewhere found at the bottom

of the ocean floor, is exceptionally emerged enabling the existence of very remarkable geothermal conditions that are found on earth in only one other place; Iceland, but with a rather different climate. The whole Afar triangle is rather arid due to a very low pluviosity compared with nearby plateaus. As shown in Fig. 2.10, these nearly "MOR" conditions are particularly well expressed along the Axial Volcanic Ranges first described by Barberi and Varet (1972; 1975), where the tectonic, volcanic and hydrothermal activity concentrates (Fig. 2.11), but also within central silicic volcanoes developed at the favour of transverse fracture zones (Varet, 2008).

But away from these units, suitable for high temperature developments, all along the Afar floor as well as its Nubian margin (Fig. 2.12 and 2.9 above), amagmatic geothermal systems (steam vents on the floor and hot-springs on the

Fig. 2.10: Geological sketch map of the Afar triangle (Ethiopia, Eritrea, Djibouti, from CNR-CNRS, 1973; Varet, 1975; Beyene & Abdelsalam, 2005, modified) showing the location of Era Boru (violet rectangle) and the volcanic units of Afar (from Miocene to present). Miocene units (earlier continental rift type) are located along both sides of the now stabilised margins of Eastern and Western Afar. Most of the Afar floor is covered by the dominantly basaltic stratoid series (rose). During the last million year, all along the Afar floor, the activity concentrated in Axial ranges, oriented NNW-SSE and NW-SE, as well as in marginal centres and transverse units. Similarly, along the MER (seen here in SW Afar), the recent activity concentrated in basaltic fissural lava fields and central silicic volcanoes along NNE-SSW faults and dikes.

Fig. 2.11: View of the HailiGub volcanic axis, in the Southern part of the Erta Ale range (Northern Afar, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia) showing a typical spreading axis, with symmetrical normal faults on both sides, and young recurrent volcanic activity resulting from the injection of basalt along a single dike axis. A: Left: Oblique view from the South; B: Right: vertical air photograph. Fumaroles can be seen all along this axis (in Varet, 2018)

Fig. 2.12: Thermal spring near Erepti, along the foot of the Nubian Escarpment in Northern Afar, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia. The spring emerges at 72°C from a normal fault affecting tilted Jurassic limestone (seen at the back). Note the spectacular travertine deposits in front. . . (Photo J.Varet, 2017)

foot of the escarpment) develop along normal faults and open fissures, suitable for various kinds of DUGD including electricity generation through ORCs.

Such various geothermal conditions – and related kinds of geothermal sites - are found in Eritrea along the axis of the Gulf of Zula and at Alid, as well as in Nabro caldera which is part of the Bidu-Dubbi transform fault zone (Fig. 2.13). These are even more developed in the Afar Regional States and bordering Regional States of Tigray and Amhara of Ethiopia as well as in Djibouti, along the margins of the

Gulf of Tadjourah and the extension of the Aden ridge inland at Asal-Ghoubbet and Manda-Inakir, as well as in many non-magmatic sites in the Western part of the country (Fig. 2.14). In the otherwise arid and apparently poor-in-natural-resources Afar Regional State of Ethiopia, geothermal resources are so abundant that they should become a solution of resilience providing both DUGD options and drinking water for this pastoralist society deeply affected by climate change. Noting that, all over Afar, except along the Awash River basin, water is frequently more available in the form of steam vents than liquid spring and is currently used as such through traditional devices (Fig. 2.15, 2.16, 2.17).

Fig. 2.13: Extracts from the CNR-CNRS 1/500.00 geological map of Northern Afar (1973) showing the two major geothermal sites in Eritrea; Alid (left) and Nabro (right).

- A: Left: The Alid volcanic range South of the Gulf of Zula trending NNW-SSE at the Northern extremity of the Afar triangle.
- B: Right: The Nabro caldera located along the Bidu-Dubbi NE-SW transverse volcanic axis.

The pre-Miocene formations are mapped in pale brown, the polychromatic detrital unit is pictured in brown, the Afar stratoid series in green, recent quaternary basalts in blue and rhyolitic pyroclastic products in orange. Recent quaternary sediments are pictured in yellow, and white for the flat-lying floor of the Afar depression.

Fig. 2.14: Geothermal sites in the Republic of Djibouti. Magmatic sites located along active spreading axis, whereas a-magmatic sites are shown with circles. The base map is the Geological Map of Central and Southern Afar (Varet, 1975). The two magmatic sites of Manda Inakir (North) and Abhé (South) could benefit from a joint investigation with Ethiopia as they extend on both sides of the border. But on Djibouti side possibilities of DUGD exist, and developments are under feasibility study. Map established by Géo2D for ODDEG (2018)

Fig. 2.17: Steam vent along a fault affecting basaltic flows along the Northern side of Ghoubbet, in Djibouti Republic. A chimney was built to condensate the steam and produce drinking water used domestically and for watering the herds by the local population (Photo J.Varet, 2019),

Fig. 2.16: Stone-built water collectors by steam condensation along a hydrothermally leaking fissure affecting the arid surface (basalts of the stratoid series) near Elidaar, Western Afar, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia). Photo J.Varet, 2012

Fig. 2.17: Steam vent along a fault affecting basaltic flows along the Northern side of Ghoubbet, in Djibouti Republic. A chimney was built to condensate the steam and produce drinking water used domestically and for watering the herds by the local population (Photo J.Varet, 2019),

2.3 Western branch of the East African Rift System and Southern Rifts

As shown by Omenda et al. (2016), the geothermal conditions along the Western and Southern branches of the EARS radically differ from the ones prevailing in the Eastern branch. This is due to rather different lithospheric and geodynamic conditions underlined earlier by Barberi & Varet (1977) and Demissie (2010). In fact, the Western branch affects an older, much thicker and more rigid lithosphere (Fig. 2.18). This results in a dominantly tectonic behaviour, shown by a much stronger and deeper seismic activity than in the Eastern branch (Fig. 2.19), with rare volcanic units producing magmas issued from a deep-seated mantle (Fig. 2.20) having limited settlements in magma chambers and rare occurrence of differentiated products (Fig. 2.21).

As a consequence, high-temperature geothermal resources linked with shallow magmatic systems are rather rare, at least, so far not yet demonstrated. Therefore, most geothermal resources will be of a-magmatic type (Fig. 2.22). This kind of geothermal system, controlled by hydrothermal convective circulations along normal faults in zones of extension allows for shallow, low-to-medium temperature resources, hence are essentially suitable for DUGD. However, some of the rift zones display – eventually recurrent - magmatic diking along their axis. This for example, is the case for Lake Kivu where gases of mantellic origin are produced from deep sources on the lake floor (Rutagarama & Varet, 2018), as well as the active volcanic axis linking Lake Kivu with Nyiragongo volcano (Fig. 2.23 & 2.24) along the DRC-Rwanda border (Varet, 2018). A new eruption along this axis in May 2021 confirmed this hypothesis.

Fig. 2.18: Distribution of low-volume melts (alkaline rocks, carbonatites, and kimberlites) and Mesozoic to Cenozoic rifts overprinting the velocity structure of cratonic blocks of Africa. Low velocities in blue to black, high velocities in red to white. Blue polygons = rifts; white asterisks = volcanoes; green stars = carbonatites; pink circles = nepheline syenites; white squares = kimberlites. CVL: Cameroon Volcanic Line. S-wave velocity (Vs) image is in the 100- to 175-km depth slice (from Begg et al. 2009, in Varet, 2018)

Fig. 2.19: Map showing the seismic activity in Eastern Africa, with earthquakes recorded over a few decades; the size of the dots corresponds to the magnitude of the quake. Note the much higher seismicity along the Western branch of the EARS compared with the Eastern one. (map from <http://hudsonvalleygeologist.blogspot.com/>).

Fig. 2.20: Block diagram showing the model proposed by Chakrabarti et al. (2009) for the Virunga volcanics in the Western Rift, compared to the Eastern Rift. Nyiragongo lavas are shown to originate from 150 km deep in the mantle without differentiation, whereas in the Eastern Rift, magma production and differentiation occur at much shallower depth in a thinned continental crust (Varet, 2018).

Fig. 2.21: Major magmatic differences between the Western and the Eastern EARS. These diagrams compare the composition of volcanic rocks in 5 types of continental rift systems (West African rift, Rhine graben rift, Baikal rift, Kenyan rift, Ethiopian rift including Afar), with frequency histogram of available whole rock analysis. Plateau volcanics are included. In the upper figures, rocks are classified into basic (B), intermediate (I), and salic (S) according to an alkalis/silica plot. The lower figures refer to normative compositions, with nephelinites (Ne), basanites (Ba), alkali-basalts (Ab), olivine-tholeiites (Ot) and sub-alkaline basalts (Qz normative= Sb) (from Barberi, Santacroce, Varet, 1982)

Fig. 2.22: A-magmatic convective geothermal play system in active extensional terrains with different types of reservoirs. Type 1 is an upflow zone, with convection cell from infiltration to discharge along one fault. Temperature gradient is gradually increasing at well site 1. Type 2a and 2b are outflow zones, fault leakage-controlled plays. The temperature gradient of a well drilled into such an area rises up to the permeable layer and drops below the layer (well 2a and 2b). From Moeck (2014)

Fig. 2.23: Topographic map (DEM model) showing the location of major faults and the 2002 dike injection modelled to account for surface deformation based on radar interferometry (from Wauthier et al. 2015). Note the extent of the dike South of the volcano and its alignment with the axis of Lake Kivu at the latitude of the A1 hot-springs (from GDC/Géo2D, 2017). A1 to A5 indicated the areas selected for detailed surveys during the geothermal exploration carried out by EDCL in 2015-2017. Known hot-spring occurrences are shown in red. The red polygon indicate the limits of the area proposed for new geothermal investigations to be engaged in the frame of a bilateral DRC-Rwanda project (Varet, 2018).

Fig. 2.24: Block diagram showing the hypothetical Northern Kivu Rift geothermal conceptual model (J.Varet, 2018).

LEGEND

- Pleistocene to recent sediments
- Recent to Tertiary sediments
- Proterozoic
- Folded Proterozoic
- Proterozoic metamorphosed Sediments
- Archean (?) basement Granulite and gneiss
- Intrusive granite
- Faults
- Aewa Shear Zone

Fig. 2.25: (A) Geological map of Uganda showing the main surface thermal manifestations of Katwe (70°C), Kibiro (86°C) and Buranga (98°C) with its legend (B - down). From G.Bahati & A. Alaba (ARGeo, 2008) and (C - up) section through Lake Albert showing the geothermal model derived from seismic profiles and hydrochemical studies (Kato, 2017)

As a whole, along the Southern and Western Rift branches, convective systems across normal faults are the targets to be searched for DUGD. This will generally concern faulted systems, with permeability zones resulting from the faults themselves, but may also focus on sedimentary strata with good permeability. The knowledge of such systems may advantageously result from oil exploration, which targets such layers. In the case of Uganda, in addition to thermal springs along normal faults bordering the lakes, geothermal reservoir of interest for DUGD have been identified as sub-products of the geoscientific investigations by the oil industry (Fig. 2.25).

2.4 Geothermal resources in sedimentary basins

In the above description, we focused on geothermal systems linked with geodynamically active areas, where convective systems develop, thanks to active tectonic or magmatic conditions. There are, however, other possibilities for DUGD in regions of sedimentary basins, with average normal gradient conditions, but where the stratigraphic sequence allows for permeable formations to develop, f.i. karstic limestones or unsealed sandstones or conglomerates. Sedimentary basins cover large parts of the African continent (nearly half of it, as seen in Fig. 1.14 above), and such favourable conditions for utilisation of geothermal energy in normal gradient areas are met in various locations of the continent, including in particular its Western, Central and Northern parts, but also many coastal areas. In Africa, these sedimentary basins with hot-spring discharges along faults have been reported in Cameroon, Nigeria, Tanzania and South Africa, among other countries.

The geological knowledge and understanding of these areas at depth frequently results from the oil exploration, with geological and geophysical (in particular seismic) surveys allowing to develop 3D⁶ models at regional scale, and consequently to ascertain geothermal resources over wide areas. Such conditions allow for development of DUGD projects with limited risks, hence economic developments despite moderate geothermal gradient conditions.

We propose to report two examples studied recently in Eastern Tanzania and Central Nigeria. In both cases, the stratigraphic sequence is well established, with identified aquifers at depth forming low-temperature geothermal reservoirs, and the structural conditions allow for higher temperatures to occur, thanks to hydrothermal convection along horst-and-graben, salt domes or anticline structures.

For example, in the case of Luhoi, in Eastern Tanzania, it is a horst structure underlying a permeable sedimentary layer (the Kipatimu sandstone) which allows for emergences at the temperature of 72°C, with the possibility to reach up to 100°C at a depth of circa 1 km (Fig. 2.26).

In Nigeria and other countries surrounding basins of central Western Africa, the geothermal investigations summarised by Kwaya et al. (2019) show the control of the Tertiary and Cretaceous rifts on the geothermal gradient at the scale of the regional sedimentary basins (Fig. 2.27). These studies show potential geothermal applications for DU at wide scales in all of Africa's sedimentary basins.

⁶Three-dimensional

Fig. 2.26: Conceptual model of the Luhoi geothermal system in Eastern Tanzania shown with an idealized NW-SE section showing the Kipatimu sandstone horst of the geothermal reservoir, with a horst structure which controls the hydrogeology and consequent thermal convection. The diagram on the right shows how the convection increases the geothermal gradient in the first kilometre at depth. (Armadiillo et al. 2020).

Fig. 2.27: Some geological characteristics of the sedimentary basins in Nigeria and surrounding countries showing the structures at depth, particularly the underlying tertiary and cretaceous rifts determining the thermal gradients (A: left) and some details of the Nigeria part of the Sokoto basin (B: right) showing the resulting thermal gradients on a simplified geological base map (from Kwaya et al., 2019).

An efficient tool for the promotion of such geothermal development is to publish synthesis documents (maps, sections and reports) showing the geothermal resources existing at depth, with precise record of their extension, geometry, thickness, permeability, temperature and composition of the reservoir rocks and of the contained fluids (Fig. 2.28). Such information systems should be managed and maintained at national and regional scales and made available to the public through relevant GSOs. Such information was for example published in France by

BRGM (the French GSO) for all the sedimentary basins (Varet, 1978; 1982; 1985), and made accessible on-line⁷ for use by any party interested to develop a project of exploitation of the resource available at depth in any place (see Fig. 1.17 above). This initiative played a major role in the successful deployment of geothermal direct uses in the country, with 300,000 housing turning from fossil fuel to geothermal heating in the period 1976-1986.

⁷See for instance: <https://www.geothermies.fr/viewer/?extent=-48060.0839%2C5924786.9364%2C416065.5518%2C6138810.6156&al=region/>

Fig. 2.28: Simplified maps of the major geothermal parameters for a geothermal reservoir: the case of the Dogger, a marine limestone Jurassic layer of Paris basin now widely used for DUGD applications since it was published as an Open Public Atlas by BRGM and ELF in 1976. The parameters surveyed are: 1: Depth, 2: Temperature, 3: Permeability, 4: Thickness, 5: Lithology and 6: Salinity. From J.Varet (1985).

2.5 North Africa (Mediterranean collision zone)

In the Mediterranean active seismic zones of North Africa: Algeria, Morocco, Libya, Egypt and Tunisia, where anomalous thermal zones are known and have been utilised since time immemorial (hammams notably, see Fig. 2.29 & 2.30), many of these have been modernized into thermal stations curing various diseases. In addition, new developments have been engaged, in Tunisia and Algeria, for other DU applications including greenhousing and aquaculture (see sections 5.3 and 6.3 for achievements and government support).

Fig. 2.29: (A) Thermal springs of Hammam Meskoutine in Algeria, emerging at a temperature of 97 °C, with a flow rate of 1 650 l/s. (B) A modern thermal station was built at a place already exploited for therapeutic baths since Roman times.

Fig. 2.30: Traditional Hammam (thermal station) of Bouhadjar (Algeria)

2.6 Oceanic and continental mantle plumes (Comoros, Cape Verde & Sudan)

Mantle plumes are found in both oceanic and continental environments. These telluric heat sources are found around Africa in the Indian Ocean (Comoros, Réunion, where geothermal projects are being considered), in the Atlantic (Cape Verde Islands) and in the continent (for example in Darfur, Sudan) where an area of 100 km x 50 km is covered by basaltic flows and pyroclastic deposits ranging from basanite to trachyte, with a volcanic activity ranging from late Miocene to Holocene, and the most recent eruptions dated to $4,900 \pm 520$ y bp. Preliminary studies have been undertaken in the Darfur area confirming the potential existence of viable geothermal systems.

2.7 Other geothermal occurrences

Besides the areas listed above, several areas in Africa display geological conditions suitable for geothermal development of various kinds. Although a complete inventory and full picture is not available yet at continental scale, the following kinds of additional geothermal occurrences can be outlined:

- Along extension of oceanic fracture zones off-shore and on land: This is the case for the Sao Tome - Cameroon line, which extends from the Mid-Atlantic Ridge to Sao Tome Islands and extends North-East across the continent, a wide area which has not yet really been explored for its geothermal potential (Fig. 2.31).
- At places where hot-springs or local heat anomalies are found (along geological discontinuities): This is in most African countries, notably in South Africa (Fig. 2.32) or Eastern DRC (Fig. 2.33), thanks to specific tectonic (faults, folds) and geological discontinuities (permeable/impermeable contacts of rock formations), i.e. conditions that favour ground-water thermal convection

Fig. 2.31: Map showing the distribution of the Cameroon Volcanic Line magmatism in the continent and its extension off-shore including oceanic islands (Sao Tome, Principe, Bioko) and sea mounts (Tefogoum et al., 2017).

Fig. 2.32: Hot-springs of South Africa. Rather hot springs (above 50°C) are found in the Limpopo Province in the North and in the Western Cape Province in the South- West part of the country. Most are used for bath and recreational purposes
From Nyabeze, et al. (2015).

Fig. 2.33: Map of geothermal sources of the Eastern part of the DRC
(from Makuku, 2019).

Steam out of the ground
Photo credit: Frank van der Meuten/flickr

CHAPTER 3:

EXPLORATION METHODS FOR SHALLOW GEOTHERMAL RESOURCES

In the case of shallow geothermal resources that are the most attractive, as they are the easiest to identify and the cheapest to tap for DU applications, the geoscientific exploration – although lighter and less risky compared to classical high temperature systems, still requires specific approaches. This, in order to prove the characteristics of the geothermal project development that will be really possible on site in order to answer the present local needs and plan for future development.

It requires the selection of appropriate methods for exploration in order to maximise the chance of adequate production in the drilling phase that follows and that is also more capital-intensive. Although lighter than in the case of large electricity production projects, the exploration phase still requires a specific multi-disciplinary geoscientific approach involving geology, geochemistry and geophysics. This allows to elaborate geothermal conceptual models adapted to the area concerned (of the size order of 1 km³) and to plan for drilling, production and reservoir engineering.

Given the variety of geological conditions that can be considered for DU applications in Africa, the most important factor to consider for a successful strategy is to rely on a sound geological setting to define the nature and characteristics of the expected geothermal resource, which is then evaluated by geochemical and geophysical methods. The choice of the geoscientific approach to be implemented and of the models to be applied is crucial and should be initially defined considering the geological setting of the DU prospect considered. Although geological conditions largely vary and cannot be considered in the details of their diversity, this chapter will concentrate on three major settings that are suitable for DU applications in the African region: 1. Volcano-hosted systems, 2. Fault-controlled convective systems and 3. Sedimentary systems displaying thermal

anomalies suitable for shallow resources (Table 3.1). The next paragraphs will detail the most appropriate exploration methods for each of these 3 play-types.

In the EARS, the geological setting and development of the two rift branches have resulted in the occurrence of distinct geothermal resource types which also require different methods for their evaluation (Omenda et al., 2016). Dominant geothermal systems in the Eastern branch of EARS are volcano-hosted, high-temperature, and two-phase systems while the dominant resource type in the Western branch is fracture-controlled, low to medium temperature, and water-dominated. One should however note that fault-related resource also prevails in the Eastern Rift branch and in Afar, whereas a few systems in the Western rift include magmatic components.

3.1 Steps in Direct-Use project exploration and development

3.1.1. Preliminary data collection

A reconnaissance study for DUGD is recommended to be engaged at country or regional level; it should depart from the general geological knowledge of the area. This implies in particular to the collection of any data available from the literature on the existing hot-springs, fumaroles and steam vents. In addition, especially in remote or little-studied areas, one should rely upon the knowledge of the local population. School children can be mobilised by their teachers and local leaders may engage “participative science” actions to collect data on surface manifestations. Besides natural vents, data obtained from the wells (deep or shallow) having been drilled in the country / region are frequently of high value (in cases where temperature data was collected or can be accessed

Table 3.1. Examples of explorations methods for the three play-types for DU in Africa

Source:

Play-type	Volcano-hosted	Fault-controlled	Sedimentary
Area	Eastern Rift branch	Western Rift branch	Basin areas
Characteristics	Volcano-hosted, magma heat sources, distributed heat, deep anomalies, shallow out-flows.	Fracture/fault- controlled, deep circulation, convective systems, localised anomalies	Commonly low to medium temperature resources controlled by fault or folds systems
DU targets	Shallow out-flows with fumaroles /steam vents	Productive fault near surface spring	Near hot-springs geological discontinuities
Geological Methods	Volcanology and structural mapping and fault kinematics	Detailed structural and litho-stratigraphic mapping	Structural and litho-stratigraphic mapping based on previous oil explo. & existing wells
Geochemical methods	Fluid (hot-spring), gas (fumaroles), soil gas (radon & CO ₂)	Fluid analysis (hot- springs), soil gas (radon & CO ₂)	Soil gas (CO ₂ and Radon surveys); fluid sampling and analysis
Geophysical methods	Gravity, seismics, MT, TEM, heat flow, occasional TGH	Gravity, seismics, TEM, (optional MT), heat flow, TGH	Existing gravity, seismic surveys; TEM, heat flow eventually TGH
Conceptual geothermal modeling	Based on high-temp. exploration results, determine shallow out-flows	3D mapping of fault systems and related convective up-flow	Anomalous thermal gradient allowing to catch shallow reservoir

for new measurements). It happens quite frequently – in places of active geology - that a few sites, drilled for mining exploration or ground-water production were abandoned because they had temperatures that were too high. These are definitely spots of major interest for DUGD.

In areas where surface manifestations are numerous, as it may happen along the rift axis or active faults (where indices are not just points but continuous lines due to geological contacts or open faults), the use of a drone equipped with infra-red sensor is a technique of high interest as it allows to precisely map surface and sub-surface hydrothermal leakages at a moderate cost.

In areas where no surface manifestation can be seen, like ancient stable basement areas or sedimentary basins, geoscientific investigations for geothermal studies will rely upon the understanding of the geological structures at depth, temperature measurements from shallow wells and sub-surface investigations resulting from regional geophysical surveys. Specific exploration works, for minerals in basement areas or for oil and gas in sedimentary basins generally release data of high value for geothermal development. In the case of Europe and France in particular, it is the access to the data resulting from oil exploration (in particular reprocessing of seismic data and in-depth study of deep drilling results) that allowed the mapping of different aquifers available for DUGD in urbanised areas (for district heating applications) as well as greenhousing or fish-farming in rural areas (Fig. 3.1 and see Fig. 2.28). Such investigations are the responsibility of the public sector, and are generally carried out by the national or regional geological survey. In case of lack of national budget, multilateral, UN or EU financial agencies would generally help for establishing such data infrastructure made available online in order to stimulate the interest and initiatives for geothermal development at local, public or private level.

But differing from the methodology of reference for high enthalpy⁸ geothermal exploration, this reconnaissance phase

should also, in parallel if not even before, imply a study of the expressed or potential demand on site. This will rely upon a socio-economic study allowing to gather data on the population on site, based on census and statistical data available from national and regional sources. At this stage, even qualitative data on the kind of life-style, economic activity and production developed will be of use, for instance pastoralist versus agricultural, fishing population, honey producers, etc. The presence of schools, health centres, roads, or other public services, exiting, under construction or planned will also be recorded.

These investigations should result in a set of maps, arranged in geographic information systems made accessible through the web with associated data base, with precise coordinates and names of the sites considered as suitable for such local developments, with:

- On one side geoscientific findings: indications of temperatures and flow rates, as well as other parameters (like electrical conductivity or nature of mineral deposits), and of course chemical composition of the fluids when available, and the geo-structural environment, as well as available geophysical data (seismicity for instance).
- On the other side, the social data, with a figuration of the population density, land cover, activity/production types, and eventually awareness (and eventually traditional uses) concerning geothermal resource on their land.

The cost of such reconnaissance studies should not exceed USD 100,000 for an inventory at county or large regions levels. It should allow stakeholders (development or energy ministries, regional authorities, concerned agencies, CBOs, etc.) to receive preliminary information on the overall picture concerning geothermal potentialities on respective sites and the kinds of developments that could be envisaged as best suited for the overall local context (for instance: case studies as described in this guidebook).

Fig. 3.1. Geological section through a sedimentary basin showing (in this case the Paris basin) the succession of strata, with indication of the aquifers in limestones (blue for Jurassic) and sands or gravels (Triassic sandstones in orange and yellow, and Cretaceous sands in green). Isotherms (60 and 100°C) are also shown, documenting the temperature of the geothermal reservoirs. These aquifers are widely used for district heating. (Varet, 1973)

⁸At times referred to simply as HE

3.1.2 First on site studies

Whenever possible depending upon access conditions and number of sites, a first visit should allow to interview local people on existing emergences or other anomalies (like unusual smell or noise). This step generally allows obtaining the useful complementary data, under the form of site reports including small-scale maps of the surface geothermal indices, relative to people's settlements. The data should be synthesised in standardised data sheets (see example in Table 3.2).

For the most promising sites – showing the best geothermal parameters and a sufficient population size and demand - these geological parameters and socio-economic data should be collected with more precision, like the number of people living in the vicinity of the potential production site (at a distance of 1 km to 5 km), with an indication of their current economic activity (pastoralism, fishing, agriculture, tourism, etc.) and social changes under progress. Before collecting the data on site, an initial information gathering of the population should be engaged, with the local authorities, of course, but also with population's representatives. A gender-based approach is important during this information process and in collecting these data, as women and girls are frequently the ones primarily charged with such activities and impacted by such resources (in charge of provision of energy – i.e. firewood - and water at household level).

This generally implies direct field visits of selected sites, geological mapping and geophysical controls on the sites, allowing to engage interviews with the people living near the manifestations, exchanging preliminary information on the resource as well as its traditional and future potential

local use. Meeting the local authority to give an account of the field visit after the work on site, and exchanging views with them is also recommended at this stage. Such an approach was developed and used in the frame of the GeoPower Africa project on a few sites in Kenya, Ethiopia and Tanzania (Mariita et al., 2016).

The cost for such preliminary site surveys should not exceed a few thousand USD per site, and would be more beneficial if engaged in partnership with local university students.

3.1.3 Project planning: Pre-feasibility studies

On a site where a well-defined geothermal resource is found, with an equally well-defined socio-economic need in the immediate vicinity, engaging the project planning should be considered with the pre-feasibility study as a first step. Priorities should take into account the readiness and eventually push from the local population for a geothermal solution.

The size of these sites will generally be less than the ones leased for high enthalpy development projects, and would generally not exceed a few km² (from 10,000 m² to 10 km²). Defining the size will require in-depth study of the local population's needs – present and future – considering the socio-economic impact of the geothermal production and processes of transformation feasible on site. Just like at the reconnaissance studies stage, and even more at this step where the mobilisation of the primarily concerned and potentially most-impacted actor will be a determinant for the success, a gender-based approach is vital at this pre-feasibility studies stage.

Table 3.2: Example of data sheets for DUGD initial investigations

Geography & geology		Fluid sample characteristics		Socio-economic data	
1.	Name	1.	Sampling feature	1.	Official name of resource
2.	County, State	2.	Specimen description	2.	Local language name
3.	Lat & Long Degree	3.	Fluid temperature (°C)	3.	Community on site
4.	Elevation	4.	Discharge	4.	Local language
5.	Topo environment	5.	Analysis type, date	5.	Population on site
6.	Satellite image	6.	Laboratory	6.	Population 5 km radius
7.	Air photograph	7.	pH	7.	Sex ratio (male: female)
8.	Geological map	8.	Specific conductance	8.	% children, %elders
9.	Tectonic setting	9.	Total dissolved solids	9.	% educated persons
10.	Volcanic environment	10.	Ca, Mg, Na, K, Fe	10.	Main production
11.	Reservoir rock	11.	SiO ₂ _mgL	11.	Income (GDP/head)
12.	Reservoir extension	12.	Cl, F, SO ₄ _mgL	12.	Distance to access road
13.	Hydrological context	13.	Bicarbonate_mgL	13.	Distance to electric grid
14.	Hydrothermal products	14.	Isotopic analysis	14.	Telecom (phone access)
15.	Surrounding features	15.	Hydrothermal mineral deposits	15.	Water access, quality
16.	Geophysical data	16.	Hydr. min. alteration	16.	Organisation structure
17.	Surrounding wells	17.	Geothermometres	17.	Religion/belief
18.	Geothermal concept	18.	Bibliography	18.	Contact person
19.	Bibliography			19.	Possible management

In turn, this also requires a good implementation through the mobilisation of the targeted local population that should – in case of success - engage in the creation of a proper organisation, like a local geothermal association or CBO, a community owned enterprise, a co-operative, or even a direct engagement of the municipality or of the county. It may also be that a private entity develops interest for such a project in partnership with the local population. HHGCBO, a local entity, officially registered in 2018 and that brings together under one umbrella, the 3 administrative locations with geothermal manifestations in Kenya's Homa Bay County, with leadership representation from the said 3 locations, is a direct product of this kind of engagement by the Social Science dimension with the local population that took place under the GPA project.

For its geoscientific component, the pre-feasibility studies phase should allow – given the kind of socio-economic uses identified (to be translated in temperature level and flow rate required) - to precise the geological target and the cost to access it.

This is the stage at which the permitting conditions should be considered with the proper administration in charge at national or regional level. In most cases a lease will need to be acquired specifying the entity in charge and the characteristics of the planned project.

This pre-feasibility will include:

- Geological study at appropriate scale (generally 1/10,000) including in particular the definition of the geological sequence, detailed structural mapping showing the fault controls and kinematics, hydrogeological survey allowing to determine the aquifer formation and its walls and/or cover (aquitard).
- Geochemical study of the fluid including liquid and gas analysis for major and trace elements, geothermometric interpretations, and a first evaluation of eventual risks

of scaling or corrosion.

- Shallow geophysical surface studies (Fig. 3.2). In particular appropriate electrical methods (like dipole-dipole or TEM ⁹) should be engaged on the sites of emergences in order to precisely map the hydrothermal plumbing at shallow depth (a few hundred metres).
- The use of a drone can be efficient for Lidar topographic mapping, infra-red survey, or even magnetic or radiometric imagery.
- TGH or slim holes to determine the sub-surface temperature gradient and geology may also be engaged.

This should allow to establish a quantitative 3D geothermal conceptual model (at circa 1 km³ scale) and to precise the location of the wells, their depth and characteristics (production diameters, vertical or inclined, etc.).

For its socio-economic component, the pre-feasibility study implies in-depth discussions with the local population, with specific approach pertaining to the different gender age-groups within the population , including elders (older men), younger men, community leaders (Fig.3.3), older women, younger women (Fig. 3.4), school children, students, teachers, and also other members of the population who eventually left for higher studies (technical schools or universities for instance), for jobs in towns and cities, or even for studies out of the country. Locals engaged in economic activities that could benefit from geothermal development, running businesses and having commercial exchanges as well as mobile professionals (like truck drivers or seasonal workers), should also be consulted. Ideas coming out of these meetings should be synthesised by the consultant and processed in terms of propositions, to be further discussed in the same configurations and more general assemblies (Fig. 3.4). Participative processes that draw in members of the local population across gender-based social groups such as along age and gender should be emphasised.

Fig. 3.2: Example of result of a shallow electrical survey using dipole-dipole method, allowing to map a vertical convective body with the necessary precision for optimising the location and depth of the most promising wells.

(Source: BRGM/IRIS)

⁹TEM: Transient Electro-magnetic Method

To ensure as much inclusivity as practical, for studies targeting rural areas (as is expected would most likely be the case with most of the initiatives for DUGD in Africa), a balance in representation across socio-economic status, respective administrative area/village of residence, varied functional literacy levels, social networks (including kinship ties), and other social dynamics issues should be underscored. For initiatives targeting urbanised regions, emphasis should be laid on the same issues, except that the weight on kinship ties should ideally be replaced by attention to representation across the ethnic groups represented on the site.

Engagement methods that promote optimum participation of all segments of the local population in discussions will be employed. Consequently, depending on the culture of a given population and taking into consideration other factors such as the social dynamics within the population, community meetings may be organised such that there is a mix of different community members in any one meeting. Equally meetings may be organised around age-grouping, gender, socio-economic status, profession, economic engagements, geographic location, clan relations (in the case of rural set-ups) and so on.

Fig. 3.3: Ismael Ali Gardo and AGAP-Géo2D team meeting with elders in Teru (Photos Varet, 2016)

Fig. 3.4: Social Scientist (Susan Onyango, Géo2D & EHESS) meeting women and girls at Badlands, Kenya under GP A project. (Photo J.Varet, 2016)

At this stage, where the project becomes better identified and defined, in terms of size and socio-economic perspectives, a governing body should be formed, with elected office bearers and representatives of the various social and economic segments of the local population identified during this pre-feasibility study phase (Fig. 3.62).

As a whole, the cost of the pre-feasibility study should be in the range of 100,000 to 250,000 USD per site. However, one

needs to keep in mind that these costs should be reduced once the first projects will have been developed, allowing for the definition of the most efficient solutions in the given local context. In addition, as part of the consultant mission, local entities should be encouraged to work at ensuring that the technical capacity should as much as practical be drawn from the local population, so as to avoid the importation of external and/or foreign expertise.

Fig. 3.5: Illustration and scheme of social approach of local geothermal projects, implying all categories of members of the community, including women and girls (left), aiming (right) not only at acceptance of the initiative, but at real ownership of the project. (from Bessette, G., 2006, in Onyango & Varet, 2014)

Fig. 3.6: Illustration of the process of elaboration on consensual proposals resulting from community meetings, allowing to elaborate a consensual project that as practically as possible, maximises the interests of all concerned parties. (from Bessette, G., 2006, in Onyango & Varet, 2014)

3.2 Exploration methods for volcanic systems

Volcanic geothermal systems refer to geothermal areas where heat transfer is due to a convective reservoir driven by hot rocks or magma under the volcano with upflow zone under the central part (frequently the caldera and its immediate surroundings) while out-flows are to the sides, generally linked with recent regional faulting.

Such systems developed in the Eastern branch of the EARS which extends from the Afar triangle (Djibouti, Ethiopia and Eritrea) through the MER into the KRV, down to Tanzania. The characteristics of the rift which control the occurrence of geothermal systems are attributed to the nature of magmatism that occurs therein. In the Eastern branch of the EARS, the volcanoes developed silicic magmas that were able to form a pond at shallow crustal levels (<6 km), thus contributing to high heat flows under the volcanoes. Examples of proven (by drilling) volcano-hosted resource types in East Africa include Olkaria, Eburru, Paka, and Menengai in Kenya, Aluto-Langano and Tendaho in Ethiopia, and Lake Asal in Djibouti. There are many other potential sites under exploration; most are associated with central volcanoes with or without calderas.

Exploration best practices for geothermal resource evaluation in Eastern Africa described here is based on a guide to resource data collection, analysis, and presentation prepared by the (IGA and IFC, 2014) and additional discussion relevant to East Africa presented by Omenda et al. (2016) and summarised by IRENA (2020).

In the Eastern branch which is dominated by volcano-hosted geothermal resources, the commonly used exploration methods involve the determination and occurrence of distributed heat sources associated with magma chambers under the central volcanoes (Fig. 3.7). A convective cell is driven by a centralised magma heat source with out-flows away from the volcanic edifice to form steam vents and fumaroles at the top. The model gives rise to

high-temperature resource types (>220°C) dominantly of NaCl and in some fields NaHCO₃.

3.2.1 Geological methods

Exploration techniques that have been found to be useful in exploring volcano-hosted geothermal systems include geology – particularly volcanology - and fault kinematics structural studies. Useful geological investigations include determination of the present volcanic structure and past evolution, as well as the petrogenetic evolutionary history, allowing to characterise the magma chamber (nature, size and depth). The hydrogeological approach is also essential. Most of the prospects associated with East Africa's volcanoes have generally high permeability induced by both formations and faulting, and targeted structures result in higher output. Therefore, it is important to understand the fault patterns and kinematics as reactivated fault zones. Double faulting, with oblique extension combined with straight faults generally offers the best permeability, as can be observed at the Olkaria geothermal field in Kenya.

3.2.2 Geochemical methods

Geochemical methods are key tools in geothermal exploration, including both thermal water analysis as well as gas sampling and analysis. Marini (2000) produced a document of reference Geochemical techniques for the exploration development and utilisation of geothermal energy (82p.), detailing the field and laboratory sampling methods, the chemical classification of the waters and gases, the theoretical basis for the use of the various possible indicators, as well as geothermometers that can be used and their validity limits.

Concerning the thermal waters, the following constituents are to be analyzed: Li, Na, K, Ca, SO₄, Cl, F B, SiO₂ and NH₃; other elements of interest are Al, H₂S, Rb, Cs, Br, As and Hg. Geothermal gases usually analyzed are H₂O, CO₂, H₂S, He, Ar, O₂, H₂, CH₄ and CO, in addition to HCl, HF, and oxidised S species (SO₂, SO₃ and S).

Fig. 3.7: Conceptual model of a high-temperature volcano-hosted geothermal system: The case of Menengai. (Omenda & Simiyu, 2015).

The classification of geothermal waters allows to determine the relative ratios of the following major types:

- Sodium chloride waters characterising deep HT geothermal systems, (resulting from steam separation).
- Acid-sulfate waters found in the upflow part of HT geothermal systems.
- Sodium bicarbonate waters found in the “condensation zone” as well as in deep sedimentary reservoirs (as in Turkey).
- Acid-chloride sulfate waters, rare in geothermal reservoirs associated with recent volcanic systems.

Geothermometers are calculated on the basis of various chemical elements or ratios. For the waters, the most used are based on silica (Quartz or Calcledony), or on cations (Na-K-Ca; K-Mg, or Li-Mg). For the gases the most used are based on He, Ar, N₂, H₂, in particular using the N₂O-H₂-CO₂-CO-CH₄ system, and ratios like H₂/H₂O, CO/CO₂, CH₄/CO₂, H₂/Ar or N₂/Ar. Isotopes of oxygen (18O) and hydrogen (D) are also used.

3.2.3 Geophysical methods

A good understanding of a geothermal system generally requires the combination of several geophysical methods including gravimetry, magnetics, microseismicity and electrical methods. Among these various geophysical techniques, each offering different physical parameters of interest, the resistivity methods are the most favoured as they provide the picture of the most direct interest as resistivity decrease with water content, salinity, temperature and presence of hydrated minerals. MT, dipole-dipole, and TEM are commonly used to image both deep and shallow geothermal systems, respectively. Dipole-dipole and TEM allows to image shallow resistivity structure and TEM allows to correct for the static shift in the MT data to allow for more robust modelling; it is also an appropriate tool to map the shallow reservoir for DU applications.

The resistivity structure of a geothermal system is usually defined by resistive near-surface rocks underlayed by a

clay-rich (hydrothermally-altered) zone which is therefore conductive. This is the zone where the uprising hot geothermal fluids alter the silicate rocks into clays (smectitic clays) and hematite, and interact with cooler fluids, thus depositing minerals that include carbonate travertine and/or silica sinters. The reservoir zone has been determined to have relatively higher resistivity due to the presence of steam and resistive primary and secondary minerals. This picture has clearly been used to explore and site wells at Olkaria and Menengai geothermal fields in Kenya.

However, it has been determined that the typical resistivity structure is not in itself conclusive as the resistivity distribution can be caused by processes other than geothermal – such as clay layers in detrital, non-geothermal aquifer - as demonstrated in the case of Karisimbi area in Rwanda (Western Rift branch). Cooled reservoirs with clay minerals may also provide similar pictures as hot ones. This shows that no geophysical method is of unequivocal efficiency in geothermal exploration and should be used in combination with appropriate geological (volcano-structural, hydrogeological), geochemical and other geophysical methods.

3.2.4 Geothermal conceptual modelling

The interdisciplinary approach combining all components of the geothermal exploration: geology, hydrogeology, geochemistry and geophysics allows the development of an elaborate conceptual model in which each of these geo-scientific approaches should be consistent and support the same scheme, including all the characteristic components, i.e. the magmatic heat source, the geothermal reservoir, the impermeable cap and the temperature. The model should also explain water recharge of the reservoir and the location and characteristics of the hydrothermal manifestations as well as any supplementary data, as those resulting from any well drilled in the area and its surroundings. Concerning DU applications, shallow zones of outflow will be taken as favourite targets for shallow wells producing medium to low temperature fluids at low costs.

Fig. 3.8 provides a sketch of a geothermal conceptual model in a rift volcanic environment showing the upflow zone and the shallow outflow zone.

Fig. 3.8: Schematic conceptual model of Krafla geothermal system (Iceland) showing the upflow zone to the East and the shallow outflow to the West (from Stefansson, 1981).

3.3 Exploration methods for Fault-controlled systems

The characteristics and occurrences of the a-magmatic fault-controlled geothermal systems have been described in paragraph 2.3 above. They are the typical play-types of the Western branch of the EARS which extends from Northern Uganda through Rwanda, DRC, and Burundi, into Southern Tanzania, Malawi, Zambia and Mozambique. In this case, if present (which is rarely the case), magmatism is deep sourced, mafic and under-saturated; the magma shoots straight to the surface with no significant accumulation within crustal levels. This explains the lack of or very rare occurrence of volcano-hosted systems in the Western branch. However, the general high heat flow associated with deep faulting and crustal extension would create convective cells along the fractures, which could form viable geothermal reservoirs.

In fact, such geothermal systems also occur in the Eastern branch of EARS along rift segments away from volcanic centres, and also along the border faults of the plateaus, where numerous springs are known to exist. This is particularly the case all along the Nubian plateau escarpment from Northern Afar border down to the Southern MER. Remember that the location of the capital city of Addis Ababa was identified by Emperor Menelik II in 1880's, notably due to the occurrence of significant hot-springs appreciated by the Empress of that time. Some of the common and effective exploration methods are discussed below:

Exploration methods for such systems have been experienced and developed with success in the Mountain and Range region of the Western USA. Fig. 3.9 shows a geological model for such a system proposed in Nevada by Ayling & Hinz (2020).

3.3.1 Geology

The geological approach here is based on three components:

- Structural geology, with a precise mapping of the fault system, characterising the direction of the faults, the fault plans locations and the movements having occurred

along the fault planes (normal or shear fault). Fault terminations, fault splays and fault bends have been identified as potential sites for targeted drilling.

- Stratigraphy allowing to determine the geological sequence, with the age of the formations and their lithological nature, in particular their permeability in order to locate possible geothermal reservoir in rock-formations besides the fractured zones.
- Hydrogeology, with the determination of the recharge zones, generally found in the fault system affecting the plateau's escarpment, and the upflow zones of the hot thermal ascending fluids along faults located lower, along border faults or near to the rift axis from which part of the heat will be inherited.

3.3.2. Geochemistry

Both thermal waters and associated gas emissions should be sampled for geochemical analysis in a similar way to the volcanic systems. As shown above, the geochemistry would determine the geothermal water type, indicative of the geological nature of the hosting reservoir, as well as its temperature at depth from its water and gas as well as isotope geothermometers. The origin of the water recharge, including the latitude of the meteoritic component will also be determined. The components eventually inherited from magmatic or mantellic sources will also be identified using isotopic geochemistry.

3.3.3 Geophysics

Here, the combination of gravimetric and geoelectric methods (TEM and MT) will bring the required information, given the good knowledge of the geology, and the characteristics at depth of the fault system hosting the convective geothermal reservoir. When available from other exploration works (like oil or gas prospecting), seismic sections will allow to better precise the fault system at depth. Existing seismic data should also be exploited to confirm the active tectonics controlling the fault-induced permeability, and the movements on the fault planes. When budget allows, a micro seismic survey may also help to locate the active faulting local and regional pattern.

Fig. 3.9. Typical geological section for a faulted, a-magmatic geothermal site in Nevada. Granite and metamorphic basement in green, Miocene to present sediments in yellow. Isotherms are shown in red, normal faults in black, red arrow shows the upflow zone and meteoritic fluid flow direction is pictured with blue arrows (from Ayling & Hinz 2020)

3.3.4 Thermal gradient measurement

TGH should be considered as an important surface exploration tool for fault-controlled systems to better precise the geological section and temperature gradients whenever needed (see Fig. 3.10).

3.3.5 Conceptual modelling

A similar interdisciplinary approach to volcanic systems combining all components of the geothermal exploration: geology, hydrogeology, geochemistry, heat flow and geophysics allows the development of an elaborate conceptual model for the fault systems as well. A typical conceptual model for such geothermal play-types was proposed by Moeck (2014). It is illustrated in Fig. 2.22 above, and a specific example is proposed for a site in Nevada in Fig.3.9. There are, yet, no proven cases of geothermal systems in a-magmatic fault related environments in Africa. However, a few exploration works have allowed to elaborate some conceptual models, notably in Rwanda, Tanzania and Uganda (Fig. 2.24 and 2.25 above).

Fig. 3.10: Well design and completion diagram for 500 m and 1,000 m deep slim hole exploration drilling

Major extensional faults of the Afar and Main Ethiopian Rift intersect at the margin of the Tendaho Graben, giving rise to permeable paths for deep groundwaters heated by ongoing rift intrusion and crustal spreading. Photo credit: James Stimac/Geo Rising/flickr

3.4 Exploration methods for Sedimentary basin-hosted systems

The geoscientific approach of these geothermal systems is similar to the ones described before. It was described in section 2.4, based on well-documented examples from Eastern Tanzania and the wide Western African basins explored for oil and therefore benefiting from the necessary geological and geophysical data.

Such an approach – using existing data from the State archives and data banks issued from earlier exploration;

compiling them in resource maps (reservoir depth, thickness, permeability, fluid composition; see Fig. 3.11 below and 2.28 above) made available for the public (particularly City Councils and Engineering Units) - was extensively applied in France for all sedimentary basins of the country in the 1970's. This, together with risk coverage insurance, allowed the building of geothermal DU solutions based on "doublets" (Fig. 3.12). District heating, covering the heating and sanitary hot water needs of about 300,000 households and offices, notably in Paris' densely populated suburbs, has been provided for the last 40 years in real economic conditions, (Varet, 1982).

Fig. 3.11: Example of a resource map produced by the French Geological Survey for a geothermal reservoir in a sedimentary basin, the case of "Dogger" (Jurassic) layer of the Paris basin (see also Fig. 1.17). This shows the temperature variations. Similar maps are published for other parametres: depth, thickness permeability, salinity, etc (see Fig. 2.28). The sites of the exploitation using the "doublet" technology for district heating are numbered. (source: BRGM)

Fig. 3.12: scheme of a geothermal doublet in the Paris Basin (France). Here Chatenay-Malabry site, South-Eastern Paris suburb.
Retrieved from: <https://lavallee-chenay-malabry.com/2020/05/15/le-reseau-de-chauffage-urbain-en-geothermie/>

3.4.1 Feasibility studies

The feasibility studies stage implies engagement of the exploration drilling. However, differing from classical geothermal sites, this will require shallow drilling, that is at depth of a few hundred metres only. DU projects usually require hot water at temperatures of between 40 and 150°C. Drilling for DU projects therefore can use low-capacity drilling equipment with a rated power of about 350HP or more and with accessories like air package and mud pumps and occasionally BOPE. Such rigs are the type used for medium-depth water wells but with adaptation for larger bores¹⁰.

3.4.2 Shallow well drilling

Such wells may have a telescopic casing plan depending on the expected geology, anticipated total depth, formation temperatures and fluid characteristics. Most of the shallow geothermal wells to be drilled for DU are expected to be of medium temperature (<150°C) and water-dominated. To be able to get high energy from the wells require that large bore wells are drilled to accommodate large submersible pumps when needed. In this regard, the wells are expected to have larger bore than standard water wells and lined with at least 9” casing.

The following plan is recommended (see also Fig. 3.13):

The first section will be drilled with 21” tricone bit and cased with 18” solid casing set at 2-3m depth and cemented. This top section should be drilled with water or mud. The second section should be drilled to about 200-300m depth with 17½” tricone bit and cased with 13” solid cemented casing. The section should be drilled with either water, mud or aerated water depending on the nature of the formation.

Fig. 3.13: Drilling engineering scheme (completion design) of a shallow geothermal well for DUs applications (P.Omenda, Pers. Comm.).

¹⁰The meaning of bores is to make a hole in something with a tool or by digging.

Fig. 3.14: Steam / boiling water diverter to be installed at the well-head during drilling while the geothermal well is flowing. The flow diverter and flow line to the sump and/or the mud system to the top of the casing according to diagram in Fig. 3.13

The production section of the well would then be drilled with 12¼" tricone bit and cased with 9" perforated carbon steel liner to a depth of between 600m and 800m, depending on the resource depth. The zone should be drilled with either foam or aerated water. This will be the production zone where the submersible pump will be set. During drilling of the production section, it is recommended that a flow diverter should be used (as shown in Fig. 3.14) instead of a BOPE as the latter can be costly to hire. In many cases, shallow wells for DU will be drilled in anticipation of medium temperatures and low pressures therefore can be safely drilled without BOPE. However, large water storage, mud tanks and high-capacity pumps would be required should temperatures rise that must be controlled. In any case, drillers may need to stop drilling when flow line temperatures exceed 75°C. Cementing would be achieved by use of mud pumps to pump cement slurry through inside the casings back to the surface and a wiper plug is pumped to displace cement in casing to fill the annulus.

A 9" master valve made of high-pressure stainless steel should be used on the well-head. A gate valve of about 3" should be installed on the well-head for bleeding and as a safety valve. The side valve will also be used as a kill line during drilling and well maintenance after drilling. Hot water submersible well pump or line shaft pumps would be required in most cases, however, some wells may self-flow and as such may not need pumps.

This approach also requires utmost care when drill pad is set up above a fault zone as steam may discharge from the ground during the initial civil works. Compared to classical geothermal sites, the risks are much less, and the exploration drilling should eventually become the production well, responding to the needs of the whole project at the initial stage.

3.4.3 Project development cost

Considering local cost estimates of 200 USD per metre for drilling, drilling up to 5 wells (a total of 2,500 metres depth) should not exceed 500,000 USD, and the total cost of the feasibility study including the design and cost estimate of the surface installations could reach 250,000 USD in the simplest cases, but are not expected to exceed 500,000 USD.

The feasibility study also includes the design of the geothermal fluid processing (eventually with steam/brine separation), the heat exchangers devices allowing successive uses of the fluid, from ORC plant (if suitable temperature is encountered) to DU of the heat for the various kinds of usages responding to the local demand (various kind of solutions detailed below, chapter 4), and finally the use of the fluid itself, for bathing or other applications.

The feasibility study also includes:

the design of the geothermal fluid processing (eventually with steam/brine separation),

- the heat exchangers devices allowing successive uses of the fluid, from ORC plant (if suitable temperature is encountered) to DU of the heat for the various kinds of usages responding to the local demand (various kind of solutions detailed below, chapter 4),
- and finally, the use of the fluid itself, for bathing or other applications.

3.5 Surface engineering and development on site

During the feasibility phase, the drilling engineering and well testing will require the intervention of drilling and production engineers with experience in geothermal developments. Having at hand wells of good quality and well-established production parameters, the site development should hence be reduced - concerning the production part of the system - to eventually a few complementary drillings, depending upon the initial size of the system. However, except when the demand is high and well-documented, it is recommended to start the project with a small-sized device, based on the productive well(s) drilled during the exploration phase.

The site development will mainly includes the costs of the surface installation, eventually including the ORC binary plant as the main investment, in the range of 2,000 USD per kW installed. As a whole, the investment for energy production will represent roughly half of the total project cost (Fig 3.15).

The surface engineering will therefore be an important part of the project and as stated above, the costs for DU devices will vary considerably depending upon the application considered, but will be minimal, if it is only the geothermal part that is considered (geothermal pipes, heat exchangers, reinjection wells). The rest of the investment – whatever the application (aquaculture; greenhousing; agro-industry – crops, vegetables, meat, fruits ; fish drying; sanitary and health devices; drinkable water production; mineral bottling; bathing; cleaning; balneo-therapy and spa) will progressively become the major part of the project, as the markets will develop and diversify.

As a whole, the geothermal site development should roughly cost a few 100,000 USD, reaching 300,000 USD for a village DU device including a 100kW ORC, and not exceed 1 million USD for an average unit including the production of circa 10 MWth, the DU devices as well as production of water by condensation of the steam in liquid-water-deprived arid zones. This corresponds to a price of less than 8 cents per kWh, which is very competitive compared to any other options for grid electricity or stand-alone systems, like diesel-engine-powered systems that the geothermal plant would generally displace in such characteristically remote sites.

However, it is the various applications derived from the use of the heat contained in the geothermal fluid, and the final use of the geothermal fluid itself that will be the major sources of income for the community benefitting from the plant, and in particular the various stakeholders that will have invested in the system, as this is the part that will increase the sales of the community. To this respect, an intelligent cascade use of the fluid will allow to particularly provide economic solutions for all stakeholders as the same fluid production, at the same time, enables diversified productions.

3.6 Site management, maintenance and global costs

Since the first stages of the project feasibility, design and construction management, a local entity in charge of the project will have been established. Such entities could have different status. In the case of Afar, their example is AGAP – established in January 2015 (see Fig. 3.16). It intends, on each site to be developed, to create a local entity, involving representatives of all concerned parties of the site population, as well as incoming partners.

Once the system is installed, the phase of start-up and commissioning will be a major step, as this would allow to determine the optimal production parameters and to adjust each individual surface unit and to optimise the whole system of cascade uses.

At this stage, the agents in charge of operation and maintenance will become operational and take their full responsibilities. They will have received training in advance, including on sites fully operational abroad, but will still require coaching, mentoring and guidance, during the initial period of work. Facilities for training all along the process should be organised, for the staff on site and also in view of continuous or future extensions, as well as for duplication on other sites.

As a whole, once local partners running the system are properly trained, the running costs are particularly low, as no consumable or import is necessary.

As shown by the IEA (2021) in its special report Net Zero by 2050, average costs for various options of DUGD in terms of kWh produced; whether for electricity production or heat applications are the lowest compared with any alternative - fossil fuels or other renewables. As shown in Table 3.1 and already seen in Fig. 1.11 above. These are world-wide statistics, for geothermal building heating, greenhouses, aquaculture and ground heat pumps. Geothermal solutions in Africa should even turn to be more competitive given the particularly favourable resource conditions, shallower than anywhere else, and a high and diversified demand.

Fig.3.15: Investment cost breakdown (in per cent) of utility scale geothermal power development based on data from Iceland (ESMAP, 2012)

Fig. 3.16: Vote of the status and of community representatives for AGAP at Ab'Ala (Afar regional state, Ethiopia). Photo J.Varet, January 2015)

CHAPTER 4:

DIRECT USE DEVELOPMENT

APPROACH

4.1 The direct use development approach enabling uptake

As indicated in Chapter 1, whereas geothermal energy development worldwide takes place in various geological conditions and types of applications, under a variety of initiatives at community, enterprise or even individual levels it appears that, until now, geothermal development in Africa has remained quantitatively limited (see Fig. 1.14 & 1.15). Especially if we consider the excellent characteristics of a good number of the continent's geothermal resources particularly along the EARS where plate tectonics allows for higher geothermal gradients and development of convective systems with significant surface manifestations.

In other parts of the continent outside of the EARS, such as along the Cameroon line (as seen in Fig. 2.31), or active seismic zones in Northern Africa (see Fig. 4.1), geothermal resources of high quality may also prevail, that equally need to be better known in order to allow for diversified uses of geothermal resources in the continent. Even in normal gradient areas, where sedimentary aquifers allow for high permeability, and/or tectonics favour convective systems. As shown by Kwaya et al. (2018) in Nigeria or by Armadillo et al. (2020) in Eastern Tanzania (see Fig. 2.25 & 2.26), geothermal energy can meet specific socio-economic needs, generally of low temperature through DU or the help of specific devices, like heat pumps.

* Hot spring

Fig. 4.1: Structural map of Africa showing the recent volcanic systems in red: the Eastern EARS and the Cameroon line in particular. Volcanic oceanic islands around Africa are also in red (Comoros, Réunion, Cape Verde, Canary). The recent tectonic trends of the Western and Southern EARS are also clearly visible. The active alpine zone of North Africa is also pictured in brown. Locations of known hot springs are shown in black stars (Société Géologique de France)

Opportunities are therefore many and diversified in terms of size and usage, offering perspectives that should be of interest at country as well as regional, local community, or even individual levels. Various options are possible, from large-size units valorising geothermal fluids from electricity production units serving the grid, to local projects, specifically designed to serve the need of local communities. This guidebook mainly focuses on this last option.

The present situation described here, showing the African lag in this field is largely due to lack of adequate information and limited technology transfer at local level, given that the geothermal resources are frequently more favourable for DU in this content than in most places in the world where DU is more developed. The main application of DU worldwide is for households (space heating, sanitary hot water and eventually cooling), whereas these applications are not necessarily the first priority in Africa. At present, the installed capacity for DU by type in Africa is first for bathing, then greenhouses, and

fish farming, as shown in Fig. 1.15. However, this statistic is not representative of the potential, as it is based on a few cases only. As a whole, despite favourable geological perspectives, there are very few DUGD initiatives in existence in the region, and the attempts to achieve site development face the lack of appropriate conditions and support devices. This results from gaps in:

- Adequate knowledge by the inhabitants of the geothermal areas;
- Proper geoscientific approach for investigations for shallow low-to-medium temperature geothermal systems;
- Adequate and appropriate shallow medium and HT drilling equipment;
- Information on technologies responding to local

Table 4.1: Comparison of HT projects for electricity production serving the national grid versus DUGD (size, time-frame, unit cost, ownership, studies, development process and social science approach)

Type of development	Classical HT projects		DUGD	
Serving	Electricity production sold for the national grid		Various uses answering the needs of population on site	
Size	10-500MWe		1-10 MWth	
Time frame	5-8 years		2-3 years	
Unit cost	100-2,000 M USD		1-5 M USD	
Ownership	Private or stataal		Local community	
Geosciences & technologies / Social Science	Geo-science Technologies	Social Science (Impacts)	Geo-science Technologies	Social Science (ownership)
6 Plant operation	X	-	-	X
5 Plant construction	X	-	-	X
4 Steam field development	X	X	X	X
3 Feasibility study	X	X	X	X
2 Pre-feasibility study	X	-	X	X
1 Reconnaissance	X	-	X	X

Fig. 4.2: Artisanal steam condensation using industrial products (Otuju rift, North of Eburru, Central rift, Kenya); photo J. Varet, 2016

Fig. 4.3: Some possible options for extracting the heat from geothermal power stations for D U applications (Here crop-drying, after Lukmana, 2020)

populations' needs;

- Specific and adapted legal and institutional framework;
- Support from development and financial agencies;
- Ad-hoc local and legally-recognised entities taking up the initiative for geothermal projects;
- Local engineering offer;
- Awareness of geothermal potential in the region by decision-makers.

DU is the most efficient utilisation of geothermal resources as it allows to valorise fluids in the low-to-moderate temperature range (below 150°C). Occurrences of such resources are much more common compared to the ones

for electricity production. The Technical Workshop on The Geologic Development and Geophysics of the Western Branch of the Greater East African Region, organised in 2016 by UNEP, through the ARGeo project, concluded that most of the geothermal resources in the Western branch are of low-to-medium temperatures and suitable for DU applications (Omenda et al., 2016). As a whole, there are numerous small-sized occurrences within sections of the rift floor and margins all over the EARS including the Afar triangle. Local cascade uses of the energy, from electricity to heat and water production, tapping shallow geothermal convective systems can be developed. This was presented as what is named the Geothermal Village concept in 2014 by Varet, Omenda et al. If well implemented, DUGD could support local rural and pastoralist resilience in remote areas and ensure the ecological socio-economic transition through clean industrialisation of the countries in the African region.

Table 4.2: Three kinds of DUGD projects with examples from EARS

Type	By-products of Large electricity product sites		Commercial or industrial investment including DUGD		Specifically built project answering local community needs
	Owned by developer	Facility built by developer	Public	Private	
Option	Owned by developer	Facility built by developer	Public	Private	The aim of this guidebook
Examples	Spa, crop dryer, milk processor	Pyrethrum dryer, greenhouse	Sugar factory (study)	Malster (Study)	Information gathering, research, studies, local engagement
Site	Olkaria, Menengai	Eburru, Olkaria	Tendaho	Oromia	Numerous sites along EARS
Country	Kenya	Kenya	Ethiopia	Ethiopia	All EARS countries
Issue	Community mobilisation	Users' ownership	Impact on pastoralism	Lack of support	Public policies, local communities' information and capacity building

Fig. 4.4: Commercial Spa fed by geothermal fluids at Olkaria, Kenya built by KenGen. (photo J.Varet)

4.2 Geothermal utilisation in high temperature systems

Basically, there are two ways to consider DUGD projects. The first and most considered at present, given that operators exist, is to consider DU projects as by-products of large-sized electricity production sites. In such cases, the geothermal fluid extracted for electricity production is partly diverted to be used for other applications after steam separation and before reinjection of the separated hot water. The advantage of this option is that there is no exploration nor drilling costs as these investments were already paid for in the electricity production initiative. The demand of the population on site is part of the environmental and social study, and a “community management unit” is established by the developer to deal with questions of social, economic and environmental impact as well as those related to the development perspectives. (Table 4.1).

This is the kind of approach developed by KenGen on the site of Eburru, where water production units were put in place serving the local community’s needs by modern collective steam condensing devices using shallow wells, replacing the artisanal individual initiatives still prevailing in the area (Fig. 4.2). (KenGen also pumps water from Lake Naivasha to serve the community). In the case of Menengai, GDC built a demonstration site, using a well drilled for power generation for various kinds of DU applications to be developed in the future by concerned parties around HT geothermal sites (see Fig. 5.6 and 6.21).

Various devices can be considered: extracting the heat from the separated brine before reinjection, using a well not connected to the grid for specific reason (lack of adequate pressure for instance), or using the steam condensates (Fig. 4.3)

4.2.1 Commercial and industrial development of DUGD

In Ethiopia, commercial and industrial projects have been studied for specific production systems including DUGD but not applied yet. It is the case for powering a sugar factory at Tendaho and for tobacco-drying at Abaya (Amdebrhan & Kebede 2020), both associated with projected geothermal sites for electricity generation. A study was also engaged by a private developer (Boortmalt, Belgium in view of powering a maltster, an industrial plant consuming 5MWe and 40MWth for which geothermal appears as a particularly appropriate solution (Table 4.2).

The study that has led to the development of this guidebook focused on the 3rd type (last column in Table 4.2 above).

At KenGen’s main production site of Olkaria, a spa using otherwise wasted heat was built and is currently used for commercial purposes (Fig. 4.4).

4.2.2 Shallow low-to-medium temperature geothermal systems

The methodological approach for specific DU developments should differ from the one used for “classical” HT projects aiming for large-size electrical production feeding the national grid. The project should initially be conceived to adjust the production system to the needs in terms of size, objective, philosophy, technologies and costs (Table 4.1). The overall economic success of the project directly results from the quality of this adjustment, which in turn determines the temperature, flow rate and general characteristics of the resource to be tapped.

DU projects development requires both appropriate geo-scientific and socio-anthro-economic approaches adjusted to the African situation (Onyango & Varet, 2014). In particular, in the concerned indigenous and under-served – mostly pastoralist populations – communities living along the rift lowlands, a gender approach is imperative as women are the ones primarily charged with water and energy provision at household level. In addition, there is a need for specific geo-scientific studies, as it is not common on planet earth to have to master HT steam at the surface, which also requires a specific technological approach as detailed in Onyango & Varet (2018).

DU applications can also contribute to climate adaptation. For example, geothermal use in greenhouse heating, aquaculture, herds watering and other agricultural or pastoralist practices have a positive impact on food security and improved incomes that help address extreme poverty of rural communities. Furthermore, geothermal can provide potable water through desalination or condensation of

steam to address water shortage in the most arid areas characterizing the most low-land rift floor (as in Afar, Turkana or Natron areas). Gender inclusivity is addressed by the use of geothermal heat in value chains where women – liberated from carrying fire-wood and water on their shoulders – will play a significant role in food production through aquaculture, greenhouse farming or post-harvest processing.

Finally, it is worth noting that conflicts and insecurity rampant in Northern Kenya, Afar in Ethiopia and parts of Djibouti and Eritrea are driven by competition for scarce resources such as water and pasture for livestock. These areas are endowed with geothermal resources, which can be utilised to stabilise pasturelands and create alternative economic activities for the populations. AGAP was created by concerned communities to promote such developments (Nebro et al. 2016; Gardo & Varet, 2018). Geothermal, therefore, can also be considered as a potential enabler of peace (Varet, 2018, 2020).

This guidebook will concentrate on this last category of geothermal development, (DUGD projects specifically established to respond to needs and relevant expectations of local populations on site – see Table 4.2) but the variety of the applications described will also be of interest for centralised systems for which DUGD are by-products of the electricity production.

The reason for this guidebook’s focus on the third category shown in Table 4.2 results from the fact that such developments do not yet exist in Eastern Africa, despite geothermal resource conditions which are particularly favorable because appropriate temperature and flow-rate conditions are available at shallow depth, hence particularly economical conditions for geothermal resource development.

*The Allaobeda Hot Spring area in the Afar Rift, Ethiopia consists of numerous boiling pools and small geysering springs depositing sinter. Nomads camp here finding rare shade.
Pot credit: James Stimac/Geo Rising/flickr*

CHAPTER 5:

DIRECT-USE DEVICES AND TECHNOLOGIES

The surface devices implied by DUGD widely vary depending on the applications which are also highly diversified, and may be just site-specific, but can be advantageously associated in cascade uses for an optimal use of the geothermal production, as described below.

A major difference between high enthalpy geothermal systems serving the electric grid and DUGD is that the first is essentially driven by the quality of the geothermal resource (provided the resource is not too far from the grid), whereas the second is first driven by the local demand. In the latter case, whereas the specialised geologist is driving the exploration process for electricity production, it is the social approach that determines whether a DUGD project should be looked for in a given site, and justify the intervention of the geothermal geologist.

Depending upon the unit size of the demand, the kind of geothermal aquifer to be looked for will be determined based on the permeability and thickness of the reservoir. Similarly, depending on the temperature, the depth of the reservoir will be determined based on the geothermal gradient. For instance, in sedimentary basins, the geological sequence may allow for several geothermal aquifers to occur, at various depths and temperatures (see Fig.3.1 above). Similarly, along a fault system, when geological conditions allow, different fluids may be reached by drilling at different depths. In such conditions, at a given site, depending on the demand, the target that facilitates the best usage of the fluid will be chosen by the geothermal geologist.

Take the example of a maltster. A standard industrial unit will require 5 MW electrical and 40 MW thermal. The site should not be too far from the raw material production (an agricultural area producing barley), and the geologist will search for the geothermal sites that best answer these two criteria.

At present, there is no standard DU device and technology. They vary considerably in size and the kind of applications. Even the mode of management will largely depend on the socio-anthropological character of the population in question. Some may be run at family level whereas others will provide services for a municipality, or be owned by a private enterprise that will deliver services or products either directly from the geothermal fluid or derived from it and be incorporated in a product with some value addition, thanks to geothermal uses.

For instance, in Japan, where more than 10,000 sites utilise hot-springs for baths, most are run at family level whereas some are large-sized commercial units providing a variety of geothermal applications including collective or private baths and other kinds of applications like mud¹ and other skin treatments. Additionally, in North Africa, hammams are frequently popular sites that may be free-entrance or affordable for anyone, but could also be luxury places for foreign tourists or rich citizens.

Similarly, in France, thermal stations of swimming pools using geothermal fluids may be owned and run by the municipality or by large private thermal companies with a diversified offer in terms of thermalism and SPAs like a consortium called La chaine thermale du soleil. Such variations are also observed

in regards to greenhousing which could rely upon a shallow single well owned by a private producer, or be owned by a co-operative exploiting a deep geothermal doublet serving numerous units run by different families also sharing the commercialisation of the products.

Thus, the DU devices and technologies are different depending on the size, level and range of development and utilisation of the resource.

5.1 Key components and system design

5.1.1 For low-to-medium temperature resources

As described above, given local geological conditions, geothermal systems vary greatly from place to place depending on the depth of heat source, temperature, permeability, reservoir and the overall characteristics of a given geothermal feature. The geothermal fluid production for the direct utilisation of low-to-medium temperature resources may be the following: (i) the simple capture of a surface thermal spring, artesian wells (ii) simple shallow well with pumps and (iii) deep-seated costly drilling with reinjection of the fluid (a device called “doublet”, (J. Varet, 1973), once the heat is extracted, into the reservoir (Fig. 5.1). Wells may be naturally flowing (artesian wells and thermal convection) but they may require pumping. In such cases, two options are possible: submersible pump or line-shaft pump² (Fig. 5.2).

The engineering option relies upon a variety of constraints: the quality of the geothermal fluid, the depth and characteristics of the reservoir, the importance of the demand and of the distribution system, and of course the local/regional/national regulation.

- A self-flowing (also called artesian) water well is of course the cheapest option in terms of investments and running costs. But this is only possible for specific geothermal reservoir conditions, implying high permeability and a recharge at higher altitude than the production well. It is also a solution offered in the case of geo-pressured reservoir. This kind of utilisation prevails in many parts of the world, and various geological conditions including sedimentary basins, fault-zones or volcanic environments. Most thermal stations in France are for instance located along convective normal-faults at the contact between the basement and the sedimentary infilling, whereas artesian wells are commonly drilled in sedimentary basins.
- Wells drilled on fumarole sites, or on a convective upflow will allow to capture steam or steam-water mixture providing conditions for which no pumping is needed. This is of course the optimal solution for small-sized geothermal devices at village or family level,

¹Used on the body for skin, beauty and health care.

²Depending on geothermal fluid composition, submersible pumps may induce higher maintenance costs (due to corrosion or scaling) but on-line shaft pumps are adapted to shallower pumping conditions.

1. Artesian resource

2. Self flowing drilled well

3. Pumped production well, no re-injection

4. Geothermal doublet

Fig. 5.1: Various kinds of geothermal production devices for DUs (ESMAP, 2020)

Fig. 5.2: Technical schemes of line shaft pump and submersible pump

replacing the artisanal capture of liquid water by steam condensation at the surface (Fig. 5.3 & 5.4).

- A hot-spring is a natural self-flowing well, which just necessitates surface engineering in order to prevent the thermal water from surface contamination. This is frequently the problem encountered in Africa, when natural, non-engineered hot-springs are used by animal herds (or wild animals) without protection from animal excrement. Thermal baths and stations need particular care in order to ensure such pollution, including those caused by the consumers themselves are prevented. It is not rare that thermal springs occur in low lands or valley floors and therefore thermal water easily mixes with surface or alluvial aquifer waters and therefore requires such specific protections.
- When the flow of the well is not sufficient to fulfill the needs, in case the water table is only accessible at depth, the production will require to the insertion of a pump. This can be either a submersible pump or a vertical shaft pump (as seen in Fig. 5.2). The first solution necessitates a well engineering with a diameter large enough to insert the pump at the proper depth, whereas the second solution allows for slimmer casing.
- When the fluid itself is used (for instance for drinking purposes), there is no question of reinjection, but if only the pressure or heat content is used, it is generally recommended to proceed with reinjection of the fluid after use at the surface. This option becomes a must when the fluid displays chemical characteristics that are incompatible with surface flow (high salinity, or toxic mineral content), or when the natural recharge of the reservoir does not allow to sustain the production in the long term. It may also be that the national or regional regulation requires reinjection of the geothermal fluid in all cases. In the case of the Paris basin, for instance, the exploitation of the deep Jurassic geothermal reservoir made it mandatory to use the "doublet" technology in which the whole geothermal fluid is reinjected without any contact at the surface with the atmosphere, (as described below in section 5.1.3).

Fig. 5.3: Ismael Ali Gardo from AGAP visiting an artisanally engineered natural steam vent (a device called boina in Afar language) allowing to condensate the steam and collect liquid water in these arid lands (South Dabbahu, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia; Photo credit J.Varet, 2016)

Fig. 5.4: Satellite image showing artisanal steam wells (a few meters wide circles) at EraBoru, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia (from Gardo & Varet, 2020)

5.1.2 Heat exchangers

Concerning the modality of the use of the geothermal fluid: it may be used directly in the system, and even be utilised for its intrinsic qualities, either as drinkable water (as in the case of mineral water of high therapeutic or sales value in particular). But if only be used for its pressure or heat content, and if the fluid is corrosive, toxic or too salty for surface release, it needs to be utilised through a heat exchanger. In such a case, a variety of options are available, for example:

- plate heat exchangers, easier to clean in case of significant scaling (Fig. 5.5). They are eventually more expensive, as these are imported products, but allow for the highest performance, with reduced maintenance costs. They are currently being used at Oserian flower farm, Naivasha, Kenya.
- tube heat exchanger, that may be more or less sophisticated (Fig. 5.6), The simplest ones, used for instance at Menengai (Kenya) just necessitate a rolled tube in which the water used in the DU devices is placed in a cement cave containing the geothermal fluid.
- down-hole heat exchanger in case of flowing reservoirs in particular (Fig. 5.7)). However, this solution is rather specific and not necessarily adapted to the African context.

Fig. 5.8 summarises the various kinds of devices developed for different DUs options (BRGM, France).

5.1.3 The doublet technology

The doublet technology was developed in France in the 1970's in order to master the utilisation of deep saline aquifers in normal gradient sedimentary basins as found in stable continental platforms in most continents, including Europe and Africa. The wells may be either vertical when space and costs allow for two different pads, but deviated wells (either both or the reinjection well only, drilled from the same pad) are generally favored as space availability is a major challenge in urban areas.

In normal gradient areas, differing from active rift zones, the rate of utilisation of the heat is much higher than the heat transfer by conduction in the sedimentary sequence. One therefore needs to rely upon thermal modelling of the reservoir. Fig. 5.9 shows the doublet modelling for a horizontal sedimentary reservoir with the typical scheme of thermic transfer developed by BRGM, in which:

- Every flow line has its own time of thermal transfer
- Invaded zone is deformed with time
- Piercing times calculated on the basis of mathematical formula

Fig. 5.5: Plate heat exchanger. Technical scheme (A: left) and picture (B: right) of a plate heat exchanger at work (Oserian greenhouses, Naivasha, Kenya, Photo J.Varet, 2015)

Fig. 5.6: Tubular heat exchanger: Technical scheme of a multi-tube heat exchanger (A: left) and a simple tube heat exchanger at work in Menengai, Kenya (B: right, photo J.Varet, 2018),

- The process considered implies :
 - diffusion, dispersion and convection in the aquifer
 - conductive exchanges with aquifer walls
 - homogeneous layer with semi-finite walls
- The approach for the calculation of optimal size includes:
 - perimeter of thermal influence
 - evolution of the production curve
 - time for piercing and life time
 - reservoir schematisation, optimisation and safety

The models, developed and applied in the 1970's were calculated for a life time of the doublets of 20 to 30 years, using high safety conditions as a reduction of the thickness of the aquifer to the most productive layers. It was shown, after 50 years of production, that the calculation was really on the safe side as most doublets still work after 50 years without noticeable temperature decrease.

The investment costs for such deep doublets (1,500 to 2000m deep in order to reach temperatures of 60 to 90°C) is valuable in case of thick aquifers with high permeability allowing for high flow rates (150 to 300 m³) and large-sized district heating systems serving several hundred or thousand housing equivalents (apartments, schools, hospitals, sports

Fig. 5.7: Dow-hole heat exchanger (an option developed at Klamath Fall geothermal project, Oregon, USA)

Fig. 5.8: Various kinds of geothermal devices developed in continental France: From left to right, doublet exploiting deep aquifers for district heating, single wells for agriculture or swimming pools using aquifers of a few hundred meters depth, tertiary building or individual housing with ground heat pumps and lastly, deep EGS. (Source: BRGM)

Fig. 5.9: Mathematical model developed by BRGM to calculate doublet life time in sedimentary aquifers (Varet, 1982)

facilities, swimming pools, retirement homes, tertiary offices, etc). The best devices allow for cascade use of the fluids, depending upon the heating dissipation devices (radiators or heating floors).

5.1.4 Ground-source heat pumps

When the temperature of the geothermal fluid is lower than the level requested by the DU in case of heat applications (for instance for building or greenhouse heating), the use of heat pumps (see Fig. 5.10) is a good option. The heat pump itself will consume some electricity (in addition to the consumption of the production and injection pumps), The

advantage of the heat pump is that it lowers the electricity consumption by a factor ranging from 4 to 6 compared to direct electric systems based on Joule effect otherwise used for heating buildings or production of sanitary hot water. The heat pump solution is getting more popular worldwide, with an even faster growth than direct geothermal heating, as it applies also for small-sized units, including individual housing. This became for the last 20 years the regular option for household heating and sanitary hot water production in Sweden or Switzerland.

With climate change, the need for air conditioning and building cooling is increasing world-wide and here again,

geothermal heat pumps are the most economic options, in particular the reversible heat pumps that allow for both heating in winter and cooling in summer; with the best performance also for the geothermal reservoir (gaining heat in summer and increasing the efficiency of winter heating, as shown in Fig. 5.11).

Many cities in Africa use air conditioning in summer, and eventually ends up being for a considerably large part of the year in places like Djibouti, Massawa (Eritrea), or Mombasa (Kenya), and geothermal solution would allow a drastic decrease of the electricity consumption (given that for example, 70 to 80 per cent of the electricity consumption in Djibouti city is devoted to air conditioning).

Fig. 5.10: Technical scheme of a heat pump, allowing the transfer of heat from a geothermal source colder than the heating system; reversely the heat pump can provide cooling from a hotter geothermal source. The first option is developing fast in Europe, the second should similarly develop in Africa.

Fig. 5.11: Reversible geothermal heat pump and ground device used for either cooling or heating.

5.1.5 Electricity for off-grid production and use

Shallow geothermal convective systems may be used to produce electricity, through ORC technologies (for fluid temperature ranging from 80 to 160°C) or direct steam pressure turbines (for temperatures above 160°C and pressures of at least 5 bars). Such an option is particularly efficient when the geothermal fluid reaches a temperature that is above the thermal use needed. In such a case the electricity production is installed at the entry of the thermal cycle, before the direct uses, and the electricity produced will allow to serve the needs of the whole energy and water scheme, as well as serve the electricity needs of the off-grid site. When not used due to decreasing demand, as in the night or holidays, the electricity surplus will be used for water pumping to elevated storages (Fig. 5.12 & 5.13).

In the proper understanding of the term “Direct-Use”, using this term for this option could be considered inappropriate. It has however, been included in this guidebook on Direct-Use Geothermal Development, as it allows off-grid production of electricity independently from the grid, particularly in isolated areas, and this; for any size of the site, from a few kW to a few MW. Serving any kind of local uses, from water

production to thermal as well as electricity production, and even mineral extraction from the fluid are therefore all covered under the DUGD concepts.

5.1.6 Water production

In arid areas, for the local population living on site, the demand for water is frequently even more acute than the demand for energy, especially in the lowest parts of the rift valley (for instance Afar, Turkana, Magadi, Natron). Three options can be considered here:

- Simple steam condensation devices using local materials, as observed in many places as already illustrated in Fig. 4.2 and 5.3 respectively for instance in Eburru (Kenya) and in Afar (Ethiopia, Eritrea and Djibouti) where they have a specific name: *boïna*)
- Improved steam condensation compared with traditional artisanal devices, or ground- water pumping (when electricity is available from an ORC and a fresh water aquifer is available)
- or desalination plant using the geothermal heat and electricity (see Fig.5.14).

Fig. 5.12: Electricity production devices: The portable 100 kWe ORC option, 2m x 1.5m x2m in size (photo Enogia).

Fig. 5.13: Electricity production devices: Direct steam back pressure turbine serving the DU plant of the greenhouses (Oserian, Naivasha, Kenya photo credit: J.Varet 2015)

Fig. 5.14: Geothermal desalination: Schematic description of the experimental test rig. a) heat source, b) heat exchanger, c) water tank, d) air pre-heater, e) humidifier, f) dehumidifier, and g) cooling water.

5.1.7 Diversity of applications: ORC plants and cascade uses

Although it is a clear objective to develop and fully rely upon African expertise for DUGD, it is necessary to insist on the diversity of solutions and systems to be used or involved, which may require a great number of technologies and imply sometimes innovative social or administrative organisations to optimise the use of the geothermal resource locally through cascade uses of the fluid produced.

Basically, the kind of applications that will be developed on site results from the complementary or conflicting interests between the nature of the demands on site on one hand and the physico-chemical characteristics of the geothermal fluid finally encountered on the other hand.

In some cases, as seen in the key components (section 5.1.4), the enthalpy of the fluid will allow for electricity production. Depending upon the temperature and pressure of the fluid, the turbine may work directly with the steam pressure (a solution that needs pressures above 5 bars and temperatures above 150°C) or a binary solution will be necessary. The device productivity will depend upon the temperature and flow rate of the geothermal fluid at the entry (Fig.5.15). The ambient air temperature will also play a role for the cooling device, as in most cases no cold surface water will be available in the concerned arid regions of the rift. The advantage of the ORC technology, besides the electricity production needed to power the whole system for local use, is the fact that the whole geothermal fluid only exchanges heat at the entry of the system and is therefore fully available with no loss at exit where it also keeps its original composition (Fig.5.16). Some deposits may happen in the heat exchanger, but appropriate devices

(plate heat exchangers described above) enable the recovery of these minerals and optimally valorises them, depending on their compositions and properties. The first ORC plant was installed in Congo, present day DRC as early as 1952 in order to power a metallic mine. However at present, no such device has as yet been implemented off-grid in Africa, whereas, portable ORC units that can be installed nearly anywhere that is accessible by road, are now available on the market for electricity production from geothermal fluids in the range of 80 to 180°C (Fig. 5.12, 5.17 and Table 5.1).

In most cases, the whole geothermal fluid produced will be directly used for non-electrical applications. Then, as discussed above (see Fig. 5.1), depending upon the characteristics of the fluid, and the kind of application considered, different options are possible:

- The geothermal fluid could be directly used in the process, because its chemical composition is harmless or even valorised per se. This is notably the case in most thermal baths, spas and hot-spring resorts.
- The geothermal fluid could be used only for its heat content and reinjected in the reservoir without contact with the atmosphere (particularly in the case of environmentally unfriendly or even toxic chemical composition).

The most complete option is ensured combining heat exchanger for energetic uses including (i) electric production through ORC unit, (ii) heat production and (iii) final use of the fluid for (iii a) its bio-chemical advantages (for example balneo-therapy), (iii b) for chemical extraction (for example lithium or silica) and finally (iii c) as mineral water for drinking, or, simply, water for irrigation (iii d) or livestock keeping (iii e).

Fig. 5.15: Various options available for electricity production from geothermal fluids (temperatures range 100-240°C). Kalina and ORC allow for the best production within the range of 90-180°C. Abscissa provides the power production in kW per ton/hour of geothermal fluid. E.g.: at 120°C, 250t/h provide an installed power of 1 MWe.

Fig. 5.16: Technical scheme for an ORC plant allowing to produce electricity from medium-temperature fluids (90 to 150°C). The geothermal fluid exchanges heat with an organic fluid with a lower temperature boiling point than water, and the steam produced drives a turbine to produce electricity. Such plants are available in various sizes, from a few ten kW to a few thousand MW

Fig. 5.17: Scheme of integration of a binary plant (ORC system) for electricity production from geothermal fluids at intermediate temperatures (80° to 180°C). ENOGIA systems allow for portable production modules in the range 20 to 200kWe; a size adapted to the needs and production expected for isolated villages along the EARS. (<http://enogia.com/wp/>).

Table 5.1: Technical data sheet for a 100kWe ORC portable plant, including dimensions of the equipment.

Source: (Enogia, <http://enogia.com/wp/>)

Electrical Ratings	Maximum gross electric power Grid connection	100kWe 400V, 3Ph, 50-60 Hz
Heat Source	Temperature range Thermal power input range Hot source medium Hydraulic connections	70-120°C 800-1400kWth Water DN 150, PN16
Cold Source	Temperature range Working fluid Cooling system Hydraulic connections	0-60°C Water Dry cooler, cooling tower DN 150, PN16
Main Components	Working fluid Generator Expander Heat exchangers Pump Controls Monitoring	R1233zd Medium speed, permanent magnet Kinetic turbine Braze plate Multi-stage magnetic coupling Industrial PLC Remote web support
Main ratings	Weight Dimensions (L x W x H) Environmental Noise level @10m Design lifetime Safety	3,000kg 2.0m x 1.5m x 2.0m IP 20 60 dB 20 years Non-flammable, non-toxic, ODP=0
Norm Compliance	Machine directive PED Electrical norms Grid codes	2006/42/EG 2014/68/EU 2014/35/EG VDE-0126 (G59, VDE-ARN, UL,)

DIMENSIONS

It is also important to underline here that any local project in the kind of convective geothermal systems we are dealing with in the EARS, can evolve with time, in terms of production (deeper, hotter, higher flow) and use, answering the increasing demand on site. Particularly when owned by a local community whose needs and capabilities will not only increase thanks to the added value of the DUGD, but also evolve with time answering the evolution of the society and markets. DUGD are wealth-creating options, and the dynamics of the system should be such that the geothermal device will progressively enrich the local entity in charge and the individual stakeholders, allowing for new investments. In case of convective systems controlled by normal faults – the most frequent in all branches of the EARS – the possibility to start the project with cheaper, shallow wells will leave open the option to drill deeper more costly wells in future,

thanks to the finances expected to be generated by the initial system and related sales. Hence higher temperature and flow rates will hereby allow – with time - for more diversified DUGD (as schematised in Fig.5.18).

Later, when the “Geothermal Village” (a concept described later in chapter 8, see Fig.8.1) gets inter-connected to the progressively expanding electrical grid, it will even become possible to produce more electricity than needed locally and so the kWh produced in excess can be sold to the national electricity grid at negotiated tariffs. The local entity will have the capacity, if the geothermal resource allows, to become an electricity producer owned by the local population. A similar situation is being undertaken in New Zealand by the Maori that may inspire African local and indigenous populations (as described by Onyango and Varet, 2016).

Fig. 5.18: Schematic figure showing the incremental evolution of a local DUGD with time (from left to right) in convective geological environment (as found in the EARS). From near-surface simple DU devices, to combined uses; thanks to shallow wells, and more diversified combined uses including ORC's tapping slightly deeper geothermal resources. Increasing incomes generated at each step allow to finance the successive increment and diversification.

5.1.8 Technological parks and business incubators

Technology parks (also called science parks or technopoles) are open spaces that serve as business incubators for new economic activities and start-ups that are engaged in innovative approaches. Also called technopark, or a science and technology park (STP), a science park is a property-based development that accommodates and fosters the growth of tenant firms in link with a university or a public R&D facility based on proximity, ownership, and governance. Knowledge is shared, innovation promoted, with Development outcomes moving to viable commercial products. Such parks if developed in African countries, would contribute to national economic development, stimulating the formation of new firms, attracting foreign investment and promoting exports (Fig. 5.19).

Business incubators are legal entities and places where new economic activity develops benefiting from services such as management training, office space or other facilities (like low-priced electricity, water, or heat). Business incubators are dedicated to early-stage companies whereas STPs tend to be large-scale entities housing everything from corporate, government or university labs to very small companies. Within EU countries funded programs offer support in form of consulting, mentoring, prototype creation, co-funding and other services.

STPs and incubators may take the name of Centre of Excellence, and this terminology is used to describe the initiative taken by UNEP to promote such a centre for geothermal training in Kenya. In Kenya, Geothermal Technology Parks are being created in relation with large geothermal plants, at Olkaria by KenGen, or Menengai by GDC. These include various demonstrations. The R&D component has however not yet been associated to these initiatives.

In Tanzania, a geothermal research centre for supporting Research and innovation in the country is being established by TGDC at Songwe. The technology once developed and tested at Songwe will be transferred to other sites. The intension is to develop local grown solutions and capabilities to ensure sustainability of projects, creation knowledge and skills, and employment.

5.2 Local population's traditional knowledge

At present, in Africa as in many other parts of the world, local populations and most individuals have no information concerning the geothermal resources eventually available underground in the place where they live or administer. When not having fears for underground space and features (frequently associated with religious beliefs as a location of hell and the devil or on the contrary, the place for their gods or supreme being), they have no idea of the resource eventually available on the surface and at depth and even less concerning the possible applications that could be developed using this resource.

Of course, there is generally a good knowledge of natural emergences of hot-springs, and fumaroles and these are eventually used for direct and simple applications like cloth washing (Fig.5.20), bathing (Fig. 5.21), boiling eggs, cooking vegetables, and of course using the water itself for human consumption (potable water) (Fig. 5.22), drinking of the water by the livestock from hot springs (Fig. 5.23) or geothermal steam condensation (Fig. 5.24), irrigation of pasture for animal grazing or for agriculture (Fig. 5.25 & 5.26), etc. When the water is available in the form of steam, condensation devices are frequently developed – particularly in arid regions – for liquid water production by condensing using natural materials available locally (like rock-walls and acacia branches, (Fig. 5.26 & 5.27) eventually improved

Fig. 5.19: Partial views of technoparks in Morocco (A) and Tunisia (B)

with cementation of the condensation towers, (Fig. 5.28 & 5.29) or systems built with industrial products available in the nearby commerce centres (see Fig. 2.16).

Fig. 5.20: Clothes washing at a hot-spring site: Meteka, near Gawani, Southern Afar, Afar Regional State (Ethiopia).
Photo credit: J.Varet, 2017

Fig. 5.21: Men bathing in a hot-spring pool: Meteka, near Gawani, Southern Afar, Afar Regional State (Ethiopia).
Photo credit: J.Varet, 2016

Fig. 5.22: Young girls in charge of collecting the water answering the needs of the family, produced by artisanal condensation of the steam emerging along a caldera wall at Aluto, MER, (Ethiopia).

Fig. 5.23: A herd of goats drinking water at a hot-spring near Erepti, Northern Afar, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia.
Photo credit: J.Varet, 2017

Fig. 5.24: Steam wells used by pastoralists to provide drinking water to livestock (a herd of goats in this case), installed on a fault scarp. The slope allows for a direct access for the herds to the clay basin. Take note of the fabrics on a wall after having been washed using the same water source. (EraBoru, Afar Regional State, from Gardo & Varet, 2020)

Fig. 5.25: Sheep grazing on a graben floor fed by hot-springs emerging from the bordering faults. Sakalol, Djibouti Republic (Photo J.Varet, 2012)

Fig. 5.26: In the background of the photo is a herd of goats grazing in the plain, West of Lake Abhe (Djibouti Republic) on vegetation growing from hot-spring water of the salty lake (Photo J.Varet, 2015)

Fig. 5.27: Artisanal device built in dry stones and covered with acacias branches, condensing natural steam in North Dabbahu, Teru Woreda, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia (Photo J.Varet, 2017)

Fig. 5.28: Schematic cross section through a traditional geothermal steam condensing device known as boina in Afar language, as observed above in Afar. Steam leaking from faults is channeled through a circular (2 to 5 m diameter) dry-stone wall and condensed through acacia branches. Liquid water is collected in a clay basin accessible through a removable opening in the dry-stone wall. The clay is originally collected from cleaning the steam emissive fault which developed as a result of hydrothermal alteration of the volcanic rocks; the so called “self-sealing” process (in Gardo & Varet, 2020)

Fig. 5.29: Stone-built steam condensing towers (in this case the acacia branches are replaced by a stone cover) built by Afar pastoralists on the upper wall of a steaming normal fault of the Asal Rift (Djibouti Republic). The liquid water is syphoned with the green tube and collected below in a plastic can (Photo J.Varet, 2020)

However, even though some local craftsmen have developed capacities to dig wells of a few metres depth, this perspective is always limited when steaming sites reach high temperature and have high flow rates. Local experts from within the population know that a better resource is available deeper but have no access to the knowledge on how to dig or drill further. Additionally, access to the technical solution is made even more difficult, as it would mean approaching one of the few enterprises around that would be equipped with better performing digging or drilling devices (for ground-water or civil works), and who would most definitely respond negatively as none would like to take the risk of engaging equipment and workers in such a dangerous venture.

This means that – in order to develop DUGD, a huge effort around awareness creation, information generation and dissemination is needed, in order to reach the target population, at all possible levels. This concerns more particularly:

- The schools in the frame of natural sciences teaching in regards to climate, water cycle, geology (volcanic and tectonic phenomena) and hydrogeology, but also biology, food and sanitary education (the benefit of washing clothes utensils and bodies, food pasteurisation and preservation through cooking, boiling, drying, etc). This implies a revision of the content of the education programs and continuous teachers’ training.

- Women and girls, usually in charge of managing and providing energy (firewood) and water (sometimes from distant water sources: springs, wells, rivers, lakes, ponds, etc) at household level.
- The mayor and its municipal council (or the equivalence in cases of where such exist), the elders, or traditional leader in charge of managing the community and of dealing with social changes or conflicts, each or all need to be properly informed of the geothermal resource(s) on their land, the technologies, and of course the legal frame and resulting socio-economic advantages, but also the expected resulting social changes.
- The politicians and administrative leaders at district and respective countries' regional levels who need to facilitate the access to administrative procedures and the evolution of the regulations and procedures so as to better facilitate the implementation of local geothermal facilities.
- The local enterprises for them to familiarise with the specific civil works, drilling, piping and surface devices construction, on-site transport and building.
- The CBOs and NGOs that would learn these specific characteristics of the geothermal resources and development perspective from scientists and engineers willing to participate to the capacity building of the community.
- The high schools, technical colleges and universities which should help in training new technical and engineering personnel able to master the whole chain of science and technologies from geological resource assessment, drilling, fluid production, and management (piping, separators, heat exchangers), water and energy (heat, electricity) production, DUGD devices adapted to local production, distribution, sales, maintenance, accounting, etc.
- A specific challenge here is to facilitate individuals' return to their local community; especially the young educated people from these populations who, at present do not see their future within their ancestral system and consider living and working in big towns and cities or even abroad, as the only perspective.

An efficient education programme developed at regional level in Africa, and customised down to national and regional states as well as district levels, particularly in places where geothermal resources are known to be abundant could be sufficient to induce the popularisation of DUGD. But in addition, the mobilisation should rely upon additional

stakeholders from the administration whenever possible, and even more efficiently from the civil society. To this respect, the national and regional professional geothermal associations have a determinant role to play in developing regular updated information through any possible media, contribution to the education curriculum, creating regional and local branches, and helping local NGOs and CBOs to develop their own action of information and mobilisation.

The base of AGAP in Afar Regional State of Ethiopia and of HHGCBO in the case of Homa Hills in Western Kenya (Homa Bay county) are examples of interest for other parts of Africa where such resources are present as is the case all along the EARS (Nebro et al., 2016; Gardo & Varet, 2018; Onyango, 2020; Onyango & Varet, 2020; Varet et al., 2020).

5.3. DUGD examples of circular economy

DUGD can provide typical examples of circular economy; an economic and ecological system aimed at eliminating waste and promoting the continual use of resources. Such systems, eventually traditionally developed in these communities living in harmony with their natural environment, but which disappeared in supposedly "modern" linear economies, facilitate adapting to climate and other changes as well as constraints, through reuse, sharing, refurbishment, repair, remanufacturing and recycling to create a closed-loop system.

Circular economy allows to minimise the use of resource inputs and the generation of waste, pollution and carbon emissions. It aims to keep products, equipment and infrastructure in use for longer, thus improving the productivity of these resources. Energy, water, or any other material(s) can become input for other processes: either as a component or recovered resource for another man-made process or as regenerative resources for nature (e.g., waste water for irrigation, compost and sewage for soils enrichment, etc).

This regenerative approach, in contrast to the supposedly modern linear economy, which has a "take, make, dispose" model of production, is a resilient form of civilisation for which DUGD offers a key component.

There should be more and more public policies and multilateral or bilateral financial support for such options and DUGD should take its share in these new opportunities.

*Natural geothermal steam (fumarole) rises from the ground in a ravine within the Corbetti Caldera.
Photo credit: Robert Sauers, USAID Ethiopia/flickr*

CHAPTER 6:

CASE STUDIES OF

DIRECT-USE APPLICATIONS

In the Northern hemisphere including Europe, Russia, China, Japan, Canada, USA and Iceland, the main development of DUGD is for heating buildings (houses, offices, enterprises, etc.). This corresponds to a large part of the total energy consumption of the countries (from 30 to 50 per cent), and is advantageously covered using geothermal resources (Varet, 1978, 1982). This is the reason why these countries show the highest performance in terms of DUGD applications (Lund & Freeston, 2001; Lundt, 2011).

variety of possible applications for the benefit of the people. Van Nguyen et al. (2015) issued a specific publication of the Food and Agriculture Organisation FAO dedicated to agro-industrial applications (Fig. 6.2.) showing the variety of experience acquired worldwide in developing countries for DUGD. This synthesis has informed some of the ideas developed and most illustrations presented in this chapter.

However, apart from the district and building heating, there are many other kinds of DUGD that are also widely developed, and are more appropriate for applications in Africa. In 1973, Lindal exposed the first holistic approach of the various kinds of geothermal applications possible, depending upon the temperature level requested (Fig. 6.1). This was further developed by numerous authors including Barbier and Fanelli (1977), Fridleifsson (2001; 2003; 2013), who showed the

Table 6.1: Technical description and cost estimates for a spa thermal resort corresponding to international standards in the hypothesis of an isolated location in a "geothermal village" project in the EARS (Program Component Summary, from E.Madec, LeSpaFrancais, Personal. Communication.)

Type of building	Estimate building cost €/m ²	Amenities	Area in m ²	Construction cost estimate
The hot- springs water park	1,200	Outdoor main thermal pools (20m x 8m)	160	192,000
	1,200	Sanctuary outdoor thermal ponds (5 ponds)	80	9,6000
	600	Natural mineral pools beaches (sun protected with pergolas)	720	432,000
		Thermal water park (outdoor)	960	
	800	Thermal technical building	150	120,000
		Thermal resources management system for hot-spring park		200,000
	1,200	The hot-spring house (welcome area) * (see details below)	350	420,000
The thermal dispensary	1,500	Thermal medical dispensary (local primary medical care center)	100	150,000
Total (USD)				1,610,000

Table 6.2: Technical description and costs estimates for a spa thermal resort responding to international standards in the hypothesis of an isolated location in a "geothermal village" project in the EARS (The hot-spring house details, from E.Madec, LeSpaFrancais, Pers. Comm.)

Type of building	Estimate building cost €/m ²	Amenities	Area in m ²	Construction cost Estimation
Reception	1,200	Welcoming area for thermal springs visitors	50	60,000
Vestuary (males and females)	1,200	Separate vestiaries for ladies and gentlemen	120	144,000
Polyvalent thermal cabins	1,200	5 thermal cabins + circulation zone	180	216,000
		Total (USD)	350	420,000

Fig. 6.1: Lindal diagram summarising the variety of possible Us applications

Fig. 6.2: Expanded Lindal diagram detailing potential uses of geothermal energy in the agriculture and agro-industry sectors (Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

6.1 Caves and mushroom cultivation

For centuries and even millennia, mankind managed to survive, particularly during the glaciation periods (120ky¹, 180ky, 240ky, 430ky) installing their habitation in caves, either natural or man-made (troglodyte habitat). Whereas geothermal energy was not known as such then, this was a clever way to benefit from the geothermal gradient, which allows for regular temperature regardless of the climatic conditions. For instance, in Europe, the average temperature at a depth of a few metres, where climate variations are not felt, is of 12°C near sea level. Caves therefore have been the first geothermal application of mankind, even as they also protected the human beings against wild carnivorous animals.

Caves are also favourable places for the cultivation of certain species, in particular mushrooms, as their growth requires constant temperature and air humidity. Depending upon

the variety, temperatures of 12 to 16°C are optimal, with humidity ranging from 80 to 90 per cent. The well-known "Paris mushrooms" (*agaricus bisporus*) are grown in caves dug - in the limestones and chalk Mesozoic and Tertiary layers found in the hills surrounding the French capital² - to extract the material used in the construction industry for centuries (Fig. 6.3). The advantage of this solution is that these conditions are met without the need to build specific constructions that necessitate high insulation costs.

Large industrial productions are however nowadays developed on the ground as this allows for a more efficient mechanisation. It is worth noting that mushrooms may grow in any climatic environment provided that the building – or underground cave - is properly insulated and kept at the right temperature and air humidity conditions (Fig. 6.4). The best source for providing such conditions is of course geothermal, as near-surface resources will at low cost provide the optimal temperature and humidity.

Fig. 6.3: Cultivation of "Paris mushrooms" in limestone caves after rock-building extraction. 12°C constant regardless of the external climatic conditions, thanks to geothermal gradient.

Fig. 6.4: Industrial mushroom cultivation in temperature and air-conditioned building

¹A ky is thousand years

²Paris is the capital of France.

6.2 Aquaculture

6.2.1 Fish farming

At least 22 countries in the world use geothermal resources for fish farming (Lund, et al. 2011). The most common species include tilapia, salmon, trout, tropical fish, lobster, shrimps, prawns and even alligator. Carps, catfish, frogs, mullet, eels, sturgeon, crayfish, crabs, oysters, clams, scallops, mussels and abalone are also grown in fish farms (Boyd and Lund, 2003). To reach the best growth conditions, water temperatures should be kept within the range of 10 and 35°C (optimum around 30°C) and pH levels of between 7 and 8, depending upon the species (Fig.6.5). The following examples and data are from FAO (Van Nguyen et al., 2015):

In Algeria, the government is promoting a project for utilising geothermal energy and 3 fish farms have been built – in Ain Skhoua, Ouargla and Ghardaia. Ain Skhoua Tilapia Farm consists of 33 ponds covering a total surface area of 49,500 m². Hot water at 30°C is supplied from a drill hole with a capacity of 60 l/s. The production is planned to reach 500 t/y. At Ouargla, drill holes provide 44 l/s of water at 21°C and 150 l/s of water at 28°C at Ghardaia. A total of about 1,500 tons of tilapia are produced each year from both sites.

In Israel, the use of geothermal water for fish farming began in 1979 when geothermal water resources at about 40°C were discovered in the arid lands of the South. The main species include common carp and tilapia, followed by silver carp, grass carp, grey mullet, North African catfish and gilthead sea bream. In 2009 Israel had 45 fish farms covering a total area of 2,693 ha and a total production of 18 kilotons (kt) of fish per year

Treece (2011) published a report on geothermal fish farming in USA, a production well developed in Idaho, where catfish, tilapia, ornamental fish, as well as corals, aquatic plants and alligators are all being raised. The natural hot water at 35°C has been used since 1973 for aquaculture businesses and research. Six Idaho businesses use geothermal water to raise ornamental aquaculture products: angelfish, goldfish and others. In Ada County, USA, the Flora Company raises koi (domesticated varieties of the common carp, *Cyprinus carpio*) and goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) in a cascading application that is downstream from their geothermal greenhouses. AmeriCulture raises a genetically improved Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*).

Two examples can be cited for France. In Aquitaine, caviar, a highly valued product (sold at between 1,300 and 3,500€ per kg) processed from sturgeon fish eggs (Fig. 6.6) is produced in water at constant temperature and pH produced from geothermal wells, reaching 25 tons/year and sold worldwide, whereas in Languedoc, the company called Les Poissons du Soleil exploits thermal springs merging from the sea pond of Thau (Mediterranean Sea side). It was founded in 1975 and since 2003 is part of the co-operative group called Aqualande, employing 600 persons with a cash flow of 86M€ a year (Fig. 6.7). It produces fish eggs and fry fish³ (30 million alevins⁴ of marine fish), as well as 350 tons of marine fish per year (Bar: *Dicentrarchus labrax*) for the first time produced in captivity. The other very promising marine fish produced by Les Poissons du Soleil are Maigre (*Argyrosomus regius*) and Daurade Royale (*Sparus aurata*). The company also engages in consulting and engineering work for fish farming adapted to local conditions worldwide.

GDC aquaculture demonstration project at Menengai -Kenya) has shown the possibility to cultivate fish with waters at constant temperature, thanks to a cascade use of the heat extracted from geothermal fluids derived from a geothermal well.

Fig. 6.5: Optimal water temperature in aquaculture (Boyd, 2018), although it may vary from species to species.

³A baby salmon whose sac or yolk has almost gone.

⁴An alevin is a young fish, especially a newly hatched salmon when still attached to the yolk sac

Fig. 6.6: Aquitaine caviar produced from sturgeon fish eggs

Fig. 6.7: Sea-side fish farming using a thermal spring on the Mediterranean pond of Thau (Les Poissons du soleil, France)

6.2.2 Spirulina

Spirulina, a multi-cellular and filamentous cyanobacterium (Fig. 6.8) is considered an absolute food supplement to combat malnutrition, particularly in Asian and African countries. Spirulina has gained considerable attention in the health care and food sector as a protein and vitamin supplement. Species belonging to the genus *Spirulina*, now called *Arthrospira*, are among the photosynthetic micro-organisms of commercial importance. It grows in water and can be harvested as well as processed easily. It also contains very high amounts of micro and macronutrients. It is also being used for the production of food supplements, animal feed and pharmaceutical products.

Spirulina's optimal growth is at 30°C in the 25 to 35°C interval. When it is below 25°C and above 35°C, minimal growth is observed. Correspondingly, the highest biomass yield is obtained at pH 9.5 and a temperature of 32°C. The optimum pH levels range between 8.5 to 10.5 at ambient conditions (30°C). The product is sold as dry powder; the production of which requires the heat for drying which would also come from geothermal sources.

In Greece, a spirulina cultivation project using geothermal

energy started in the late 1990s in Nigrita. Geothermal hot water at a temperature of 51°C and a flow of 10 kg/s is used to heat the surface water to between 33 and 36°C. Geothermal CO₂ is also used in spirulina cultivation, to increase production and reduce production costs. The spirulina cultivation season runs from April to November as the plant is not insulated and winters are cold. The project uses 8 shallow raceway ponds made of concrete in which the cultivation water is mixed using paddle wheels. Each raceway pond has a surface area of about 225m² and hold 40m³ of water. The ponds are located in a greenhouse covered by polyethylene. In 2008, 4.5 tons of dried spirulina was produced by this gree project (Van Nguyen et al., 2015).

In Italy, a project that cultivates spirulina from geothermal energy was installed in Chiusdine, Tuscany, and by 2018, had created around 100 jobs.

A geothermal resource, ensuring a constant temperature, pH and CO₂ production is particularly well-suited for spirulina production and processing for sales. The present development is still embryonic and the product relatively new on the market, but this option should be really considered in Africa where numerous hot-springs are still to be valorised.

Fig. 6.8: Spirulina under the microscope, and aquaculture devices for optimal growth at the temperature of 32°C.

6.3. Greenhousing

Another form of agricultural production from geothermal sources is greenhousing. The world's use of this resource for greenhousing reached 1,500 MW thermal in 2010 (Lund et al. 2011). It has mainly developed in countries in the North where cold weather renders heating necessary for a large part of the year. This allows to produce fruits, vegetables and flowers all over the year and feed the markets independently from climatic variations. When powered with fossil fuels, this kind of production is not really climate-friendly, but the use of a geothermal resource facilitates an ecological and sustainable production. Even in a cold country like Iceland, this enables the production of tropical fruits like banana or pineapples!

Greenhousing does not only permit production in controlled temperature, but also enables the adjusting of lighting, humidity and air composition. In particular, CO₂ when properly adjusted to about 1,000ppm instead of 300ppm in normal free air conditions speeds up the growth of most vegetal. And many low-temperature geothermal resource also produces CO₂. There are even natural CO₂ vents (called "mofette") or reservoirs that produce "dry" CO₂ that can be exploited as such in agriculture or other industrial applications like production of gaseous drinks like various colas and beers. Some of the natural CO₂ gas vents occur adjacent to geothermal fields like at Olkaria in Kenya.

In 2010, 34 countries used geothermal resources to heat greenhouses, with vegetables, flowers and fruits as main crops grown in these greenhouses. Besides the reduction in fossil fuels use and benefits for the climate, other advantages include better hygiene, with cleaner air and water, and the ability to maintain a specialised workforce. Geothermal-heated greenhouses developed fast in the 1970's and 1980's in North Mediterranean countries like Turkey, Greece, Italy and South France. Main productions are tomatoes, sweet peppers, cucumbers, lettuces, green beans, strawberries and aromatic herbs (Van Nguyen et al., 2015).

More recently, countries in Northern Europe have also developed geothermal resources for greenhouse production, eventually including the use of geothermal heat pumps. Large geothermal powered greenhouses are also found in Eastern Europe, Russian Federation and Northern China, allowing for the production of a range of high-quality vegetables in all seasons. In Iceland geothermal greenhouses have been in use since 1924 and now ensure the country's production of vegetables such as tomatoes, carrots, cucumbers and paprika as well as potted plants and flowers.

In Africa, geothermal greenhouses are known in Tunisia as well as in Kenya, where the only commercial installation in the country, run by the Oserian Development Company at Naivasha (near Olkaria), has been utilising geothermal energy to heat rose flower greenhouses since 2003, reaching 50 ha in 2010 (Fig. 6.9 & 6.10). Geothermal piping network

Fig. 6.9: General view of the geothermally-powered Oserian greenhouse flower farm in Naivasha, Kenya (Photo J.Varet, 2015)

Fig. 6.10: Inside Oserian greenhouses roses cultivation in Naivasha, Kenya. Metallic pipes for geothermal heat circulation are seen. (Photo J.Varet, 2015)

maintains constant temperature and controls humidity and CO₂ air content, which eliminates fungal infection avoiding the use of pesticides. The use of geothermal greenhouses leads to better-quality flowers and increased production. The company exports more than 400 million stems of roses annually, mainly to USA and Europe.

Greenhouses are built on steel or aluminum frames⁵ covered by glass, plastic film, fibre-glass and/or other rigid plastics. In Africa, plastic covering is the solution of reference, with arched or hut-shaped frames, and as in the case of camping tents, a double layer of plastic with a small blower allows to maintain the cover standing. This ensures better insulation, reducing heat loss and overall costs. Geothermal greenhouses can be heated through natural or forced air movement (Lund, 1996). The geothermal water has a temperature of about 40°C, and is adjusted with heat exchangers depending on the required temperature within the greenhouse. Plate heat exchangers allow for easier cleaning of the mineral deposits (as shown above). Warm water is driven through plastic or metallic pipes, which are placed under or on top of the soil between plants, or suspended from the roof, with air that is rich in geothermal CO₂ blown through a horizontal or vertical hot water unit heater including a small propeller fan (Fig. 6.11).

At present, the few geothermal greenhouses built and operating in Africa are oriented towards export (of roses mainly); they are therefore located at places of easy access, indirectly serving the needs of the local population with jobs and salaries, but not producing food for direct consumption. Of course, such projects may develop further. However, the current challenge is to be able to stimulate a production

that would serve the needs of local populations in isolated sites where the geothermal resource is known to exist, and greenhouses would enable the production of vegetables and fruits all year round. We know that food shortage and even death due to starvation mostly result from seasonal droughts that tend to increase with climate change during dry seasons, especially in some of the most geothermal-rich arid regions of the EARS and such geothermal production device should help to address this issue.

Mouldi Ben Mohamed presented at the World Geothermal Congress 2015 a paper titled Geothermal Energy Development: the Tunisian Experience which shows that Tunisia occupied the first place in the world in 2002 for geothermally-heated greenhouses. Starting with 1 ha, as an experiment in 1986, the area reached 21 ha in 1988, 111 ha in 2005, and 244 ha in 2015. The cropping system is composed principally of tomatoes and snake melons comprising 57 and 23 per cent respectively, due to their commercial value for export. (Fig. 6.12)

GDC geothermal demonstration project allows growing tomatoes and capsicum at Menengai geothermal field (Kenya).

A similar project is being engaged by TGDC at Songwe (Tanzania). The geothermal site is surrounded by food and cash crop agricultural activities mainly maize, puddy, tea, coffee, vegetables and beans. Geothermal greenhouse growth and drying technologies are being tested at Songwe with intention of promoting the use of geothermal energy to increase productivity, improve quality of agricultural products and reduce post-harvest loss.

Fig. 6.11: Horizontal (left) and vertical (right) air heating devices. (Geo-Heat Centre, Oregon, USA and Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

⁵Aluminium frames are preferred when geothermal fluid contain traces of sulphur hydroxides that are beneficial to culture as they are combating germs, but may create corrosion for steel frames.

Fig. 6.12: Geothermal-heated greenhouse for tomato production in Tunisia

6.4. Crops, fruits and vegetables drying

The main cause of post-harvest losses in Africa results from agricultural systems that lead to a loss of food that people would otherwise eat, sell or barter to improve their livelihoods. These losses may be due to a variety of factors and circumstances under which commodities are grown, harvested, stored, processed and marketed (Tyler, 1982). The APHLIS (see www.aphlis.net) presents weight loss estimates for 8 different cereals in Eastern and Southern Africa. Post-harvest losses are reported to range from 5 to 35 per cent, varying by crop and geographical location (Fig. 6.13). These figures include weight loss but do not reflect other factors like quality, market value or food waste. The gross postharvest weight loss for 6 major cereals in these countries was shown to reach 15 per cent of total production value that is 1.6 billion USD in 2007 (Hodge et al., 2011).

Improving food handling and processing methods, these losses can be reduced and contribute to more availability of nutritious diet and reduced food waste. This will furthermore

improve quality and safety of food, increase food security and lead to value addition and access to more regular, valuable sustainable markets therefore contributing to better living condition in areas gifted with geothermal resources.

In particular, during the rainy season, high amounts of agricultural products are lost due to lack of appropriate processing: unexpected rain can cause high damages and loss of products for open air/solar drying of maize and other crops that is the most common practice in Africa. When unfavorable weather conditions prevent crops from drying sufficiently, losses will be high. Sub-optimal drying practices and poor storage of grain products can also lead to problems associated with pathogenic micro-organisms. The currently used open air processing methods attract insects, birds and animals that compete for the food and draws these animals to the communities' dwellings. Current drying methods furthermore often occupy a big part of living quarter of the villages and therefore contribute to the risk of spreading any kind of contagious diseases. All this can be secured by processing the food in a closed environment.

Fig. 6.13: Estimated per cent cumulative post-harvest weight loss from production of wheat, sorghum and maize by provinces, for countries in East and Southern Africa for 2007 (Hodge et al., 2011).

Drying of agricultural products using geothermal is a solution for avoiding wastage and ensuring that nutritious food is available all year round, and during droughts. It also allows for earlier harvest and therefore to engage another production cycle, eventually leading to doubling the production. In the EARV, low-to-medium enthalpy geothermal resources have the highest potential for agricultural drying applications (Ogola, 2013). The heat for drying can be captured from hot-springs, from purposefully drilled shallow geothermal wells or by recovering waste heat from the brines of an industrial geothermal plant.

Numerous examples of crops and food-drying are provided by Van Nguyen et al., (2015) in the FAO report on the subject. Geothermal energy has been used to dry a wide range of agricultural products, such as rice, wheat, tomatoes, onions, cotton, chillies and garlic. It can be a ubiquitous solution, as geothermal drying of fruits and vegetables can develop with water temperatures as low as 55°C, with rather simple horizontal or vertical devices (Fig.6.14).

It can be expanded to larger variety of agricultural products growing in Africa like coffee, tea, banana, papaya for internal consumption or exports, etc. Among documented examples of this application are the following:

- A small-scale tomato-drying plant located in Nea Kessani, Xanthi in Greece started operating in 2001. Tomatoes are dried using geothermal water at 59°C in a 14m long rectangular tunnel dryer (1 m wide and 2 m high). The tomatoes are sorted and washed to remove dust, dirt, plant parts, etc. They are then cut in half and placed on to stainless steel trays (of 100 cm² × 50 cm² mesh). Each batch of 25 trays is dried for 45 minutes, with about 7 kg of raw tomatoes on each tray (Fig.6.14). It was shown that tomato-drying requires 1,450 kWh/t of wet weight. The dried tomatoes are then immersed in olive oil and are ready for transport and sale. During the first year of operation, 4 tons of high-quality dried tomato products were produced.
- A pilot-scale geothermal drying system for the pre-drying of cotton was designed and tested in the same district of Nea Kessani, Xanthi in 1991 and 1992. The test demonstrated that cotton can be dried in a specially designed tower drier using geothermal water (Fig. 6.15).
- Chillies and garlic are important to the economy of Thailand, where people consume them both fresh and dried. Waste heat recovered from a geothermal power plant is used for the drying process. Chillies

Fig. 6.14: Tomatoes loaded on drying racks in Greece (Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

Fig. 6.15: Pilot scale cotton dryer using geothermal energy in Greece (Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

and garlic are dried in cabinet driers 2.1 m wide, 2.4 m long and 2.1 m high. Each dryer has 36 trays placed in 2 compartments with a total capacity of 450 kg of chillies or 220 kg of garlic (Fig. 6.16). Geothermal hot water at about 80°C circulates through a cross-flow heat exchanger 100 mm wide, 500 mm long and 300 mm high, enabling a constant air flow of 1 kg/s to pass through the 10.5 m³ drying chamber. The required air temperatures are 70°C for chillies and 50°C for garlic, with drying times and hot water flow rates of about 46 hours at 1 kg/s for chillies, and 94 hours at 0.04 kg/s for garlic. The total energy consumed is 13.3 MJ/kg H₂O evaporated for chillies and 1.5 MJ/kg H₂O evaporated for garlic. This type of dryer has relatively low running costs and can be used in any weather conditions.

- In Macedonia (a former Yugoslav Republic), water from a geothermal well for the direct heating of a rice-drying plant in the Kotchany geothermal field is used (Fig. 6.17). The capacity of the dryer is 10t/h with a heating capacity of 1,360 kW. The thermal energy required for rice-drying is therefore 136 kWh/t of wet weight. Outside air at an average temperature of 15°C and relative humidity of 60 per cent, is heated to about 35°C in a water-to-air heat exchanger. The inlet and outlet geothermal water temperatures are 75°C and 50°C respectively. The heated air is blown into the drying zone to dry the rice, which moves downwards through the drier at constant velocity. There is gravitation mixing as the grain column moves downwards. The temperature of the heated air is kept

- | | | |
|--------------------|-----------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1. Window | 6. Centrifugal fan | 10. Insulated walls |
| 2. Return air duct | 7. Air duct | 11. Grills |
| 3. Exhaust opening | 8. Heat exchanger using hot water | 12. Shelf for putting grill |
| 4. Valve | 9. Hot water tap | 13. Door |
| 5. Inlet | | |

Fig. 6.16: Geothermal dryer for chillies and garlic (Thailand) (Geo-Heat Centre, Oregon, USA and Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

Fig. 6.17: Vertical geothermal rice dryer (Macedonia). (Geo-Heat Centre, Oregon, USA and Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

below 40°C to prevent cracking of the rice. The rice is dried to decrease the moisture content from 20 to 14 per cent and then air-cooled.

- For years, pyrethrum, tobacco and maize were dried at Eburru in Kenya, where the local population uses a traditional system to harness and condense geothermal steam for drying agricultural products, but in the recent past years the small plant has no longer been in use except for drying of a few crops (Fig.6.18).
- At Los Azufres, a geothermal field in Mexico, a fruit dryer was designed by Lund and Rangel (1995) and installed. The dryer is 4.0 m long, 1.35 m wide and 2.3 m high (Fig. 6.19), with concrete walls, a timber ceiling and roof, and a reinforced concrete floor. It has 2 containers with 30 trays each and has a capacity of about 1 tonne of fruit per drying cycle. Energy consumption is 10 kJ/s at a geothermal water flow rate of 0.03 kg/s. The drying chamber is kept at a temperature of 60°C and reduces the moisture content of fruit from 80 to 20 per cent in 24 hours.

- In Indonesia, a geothermal dryer is being used to dry beans and grain in the Kamojang geothermal field (West Java). The system is designed to be used to dry most crops produced in the area, such as coffee, tea, rice, beans and fishery products. Geothermal fluid from a well, at about 160°C, is used to heat air for the drying process. The air is blown through a tube-bank heat exchanger where it is heated before being blown into the drying chamber, consisting of 4 trays (Fig.6.20). The heat transfer rate in the geothermal exchanger is 1kW. The air flow velocity ranges from 4 to 9 m/s and the drying temperature from 45°C to 60°C. The drying time depends on the moisture content of the raw material.
- Esther Njuguna presented at ARGeo-C8 in 2020 the batch grain dryer (Fig. 6.21 & 6.22) installed in 2019 by GDC in collaboration with ICEIDA at Menengai well 03, hosting another four demonstration projects for DU. It utilises 0.15m³/min of hot water introduced at 55 to 65°C into the drying chamber, produced through a heat

Fig. 6.18: Pyrethrum geothermal dryer at Eburru (Kenya) now converted for the drying of other crops. Outside view of incoming and outflowing steam, and drying racks inside (Photo. J.Varet, 2016)

Fig. 6.19: Fruit dryer using geothermal heat at Los Azufres, Mexico. (Geo-Heat Centre, Oregon, USA and Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

Fig. 6.20: Geothermal dryer for beans and grains, Indonesia (Geo-Heat Centre, Oregon, USA and Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

exchanger (Fig. 6.22) using geothermal fluids flowing at about 90°C. Ambient air in the chamber is 40 to 60°C, and different types of grains are being used to ascertain the optimal drying parameters for each grain type. First tests have shown that drying using geothermal is the most favorable in terms of costs, reliability and time in comparison to other modes of drying (for example sun-drying, using wood-fuel or diesel) applied by farmers and the industry in Nakuru. A variety of grains (maize, wheat, beans, canola) are produced all year round, making this dryer a game changer in the grain farming and grain industry in Nakuru County.

- In Western Nevada (USA), a large-scale onion and garlic-drying facility developed a more efficient process based on continuous conveyor belt dryers measuring approximately 3.8 m wide and 60 m long (Fig. 6.24) fed by 3,000 to 4,300 kg/hour of wet onions. The production capacity of the dryers varies from 500 to 700 kg/hour, reducing the moisture content of the onions from 85 to about 4 per cent after 24 hours of drying. The plant employs 75 workers.

Fig. 6.21: 3D view of the pilot batch grain dryer installed by GDC with the support of ICEIDA in Menengai, Kenya. Njuguna (2020)

Fig. 6.22: View of the tube heat exchanger in Menengai, Kenya, using a geothermal fluid at 80°C to heat water at 55-65°C, itself heating the air at 40-60°C in the drying chamber. (Njuguna, 2020)

Fig. 6.23: Two perpendicular sections through a geothermal conveyor dryer for onion and garlic in Nevada, USA (Geo-Heat Centre, Oregon, USA and Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

Fig. 6.24: Batch grain dryer using geothermal heat from a water/air heat exchanger (Geo-Heat Centre, Oregon, USA and Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

Summing these first examples, note that a deep-bed dryer (batch dryer) for grains (as shown above in Fig. 6.11) consists of a fan that blows air through a geothermal heat exchanger, where it is heated. The hot air is then distributed uniformly to the product through a perforated floor. The temperature of the hot air is controlled by adjusting the flow rate of the geothermal fluid. The drying temperature of some grains can approach 90°C, but moderate temperatures of 50 to 60°C with relative humidity of about 40 per cent is adequate for drying most products. For example, the drying temperature of coffee berries is about 50 to 60°C while that for rice must be maintained below 40°C to prevent cracking. The final moisture content of dried grains should be in the range of 12–13 per cent to prevent mould growth and spoilage. For tea leaves moisture content of approximately 70 per cent initially should be reduced to 3 per cent.

This survey shows the variety of DUGD that could be implemented in Africa, as it concerns in fact any kind of agricultural production, from grains, beans, potatoes to any kind of vegetables or fruits. Given the significant production of tea and coffee in the region, geothermal drying, not yet utilised for this purpose, could become an option of interest. As shown in the examples, the technological devices are rather simple, easy to adapt, build and operate locally, at any scale, but with an advantage for systems run at community level allowing for better usage of the system and eventually to identify and train specialised staff.

These food-drying DUGDs allow the increase of local consumption with availability of the products all year round and not only seasonally, enhance the production by shortening the planting-harvesting cycle, and create or increase exports, with creation of jobs in the agro-process itself as well as in the derived activities (like packaging, storage, transport, sales on markets and by internet, etc). Compared with industrial production, these are ecological and eventually labeled “bio-products” which should also benefit from labels like the AOC developed in France.

6.5 Milk pasteurisation and cheese processing

All over Africa, and particularly in the low-lands of the EARS, as a consequence of the dry climate, the local population is dominantly, if not exclusively, pastoralist. Animals (goats, sheep, cows, camels, etc) are mainly raised for selling in the neighborhood, or for local consumption of the meat, and also for their milk. Milk is a nutritious food and an important part of the diet of pastoralist communities. The quality of milk changes rapidly after collection, mainly as a result of enzyme activity and the growth of micro-organisms at ambient temperatures.

In order to keep the original quality of the milk, and prevent enzyme activity as well as microbial growth, milk must be processed using high-temperature treatments such as pasteurisation or the UHT process. Geothermal hot water is suitable for milk pasteurisation and drying processes, while geothermal steam is required for milk evaporation and the UHT process.

The flow chart of a milk pasteurization process is shown in Fig. 6.25 (Lund, 1997). The temperature of the geothermal fluid is pumped from the well at 87°C and the outlet is 77°C. The geothermal water and milk fluid flow through the plate heat exchanger, moving in opposite directions on either side of the plates. Water flow and circulation are controlled by the placement of the plate gaskets, which are installed to prevent mixing of the milk and geothermal water. Fresh milk at a temperature of 3°C is pre-heated to 71°C in the plate heat exchanger A by the hot milk from the homogenizer. The heated milk is then passed through geothermal plate heat exchanger B for pasteurization, where it is heated to at least 78°C for 15 seconds. After pasteurization, the hot milk is passed through the homogeniser and then back through plate heat exchanger A where it is cooled to 12°C. It is finally chilled to 3°C by cold water in plate heat exchanger C before packaging and storage.

Fig. 6.25: Diagrammatic representation of a milk processing plant using a geothermal well producing fluid at 87°C. (Geo-Heat Centre, Oregon, USA and Van Nguyen et al, 2015)

The following history of operations for milk/dairy processing plants are reported in literature:

- A geothermal milk processing plant was first created in Iceland in the years 1920 but was not maintained.
- The first significant operation was developed at Medo-Bel Creamery, in Klamath Falls, Oregon (USA) in 1945 where it operated for about 30 years.
- A plant which is still operating was built in Oradea (Romania) in 1981, where the geothermal water is used for district heating and other applications. This geothermal milk processing factory pasteurises up to 200,000 l/day of milk collected in the surrounding farms.
- At Monterotondo Marittimo, a few kms from Larderello (Tuscany, Italy), the San Martino farm produces cheese with the milk from Massa sheep raised wild within a radius of 300 km, for a total of 50,000 tons of milk, allowing the production of 40,000 rounds of Pecorino and 20,000 rounds of Ricotta cheese a year. Considering that the cheese production, maturing and storage processes require significant amounts of energy both to heat and to cool, the company decided to reduce its production costs which previously amounted to 10,000 euros (8-9 per cent of the total cost of production) a year by taking advantage of the presence of a nearby geothermal power plant. To transport the steam from the geothermal power plant to the dairy, a 72 mm diameter, 500 m long, insulated pipeline was built. This initiative takes part in the Taste Clean - Slow Food project, which aims to promote food production through the use of sustainable energy, an added value provided by the geothermal DU process (Fig. 6.26).
- The Miraka milk processing facility is located at Mokai, 30 km North-West of Taupō in New Zealand's central North Island. It has the capacity to process more than 300 million litres of milk a year into powders and UHT

products. The milk supply comes from 100 local farms, with a total of 60,000 cows, within an 85 km radius of the plant. Miraka is powered by geothermal energy with electricity and clean steam from the nearby plant. It is the only Maori majority-owned and controlled dairy company with 80 per cent of shareholders from Whanau trusts and incorporations. Miraka is manufacturing UHT milk products and milk powder, which is supplied to 23 countries throughout Africa, the Middle East, Asia, the Pacific and Latin America. Their staff of over 100 employees continues to grow, as does the community of milk suppliers.

- Kenya has about 3.4 million dairy cows producing about 2.7 million litres of milk a year. Geothermal resources of below 150°C can provide direct energy for the milk pasteurisation and UHT processes. A demonstration project of DUGD was built by GDC using fluids from Menengai Well 03, with a low pressure of about 2 bars and a flow rate of 60 t/h (USAID and GDC, 2013). The pilot geothermal milk processing plant is operational showing that locally the concept of DUGD in dairy industry has been proven to be technically viable. A government policy incentive introduced zero rate taxes on inputs used in milk processing and tax exemptions on investments to set up processing facilities in rural areas, hoping to stimulate commercial developments.

Milk processing is still limited in Eastern Africa, including in regions where pastoralism is the main economic activity and geothermal resources are abundant. A real challenge is for the populations in question to have access to the knowledge of these resources and the facilities they contain to allow for processes that would make the benefits from their traditional production better, favor milk production and engage geothermal applications thus enabling valorisation of the milk-derived products for their own consumption and sale.

Fig. 6.26: Geothermal cheese processing at San Martino farm (Tuscany, Italy)

6.6 Fruit, wine and cheese maturation

It should be noted that caves, whether natural or man-made, display constant temperatures, and are typical near-surface geothermal sites that can be used for maturation process of various kinds of foods. This kind of geothermal energy can therefore also be used in the cheese production process which requires both heating and cooling.

It is a well-known fact that, in France, the best wine producing terroirs⁶ are places where the grapes benefit from the most appropriate soils and insulation, but also areas where caves allow for the maturation of the final product, which improves in quality with time, hence in price from the sales. This is the case for most products such as Champagne, Bordeaux, Bourgogne, Loire Valley wines and many others. One should not forget that this is a benefit from geothermal energy which allows to maintain the right temperature and humidity for years and decades.

What is valid for wine is equally valid for cheese. Archaeological research shows that cheese has been produced by man-kind for at least 7,000 years. Cheese is rich in proteins, calcium and phosphorus. Most of the best considered and priced cheese in France and Europe as a whole, are produced in caves, at constant temperature resulting from the appropriate geothermal conditions. This is the case for one of the most expensive cheese, Roquefort, in France, whose production process in thick karstic Jurassic limestone caves (Fig. 6.27) allows the appropriate temperature and humidity for the development of the specific moisture *Penicillium roqueforti*. Similarly, this is the case with *Penicillium camemberti* for other cow cheeses in Normandy and Auvergne, also in France or goat cheese in Berry (France).

The same is true for a variety of wines and cheeses in Spain and Italy. The well-known and worldwide sold Parmigiano Reggiano gets its specific taste and quality from its 2 years'

period of maturation in geological caves of Emilia-Romagna, in South Lombardi.

It is also worth noting that fruits like bananas imported into Europe from tropical countries while still green, are ripened in natural caves also benefitting from appropriate geothermal temperatures.

6.7 Fish processing

Fishing is an important economic activity in Africa, particularly along the Atlantic and Indian Oceans as well as the Red Sea (Fig. 6.28). It is also a major food and source of income in the lake regions (Lake Victoria and the numerous lakes along the Eastern and Western Branches of the EARV (Fig. 6.29). This is mainly for local consumption; the fish are eaten soon after catching due to lack of preservation facilities. It may be cooked, smoked or even dried using wood or charcoal but the sales are limited, with local prices being 10 times less than in consumption centres in cities and towns.

It would therefore be an advantage to develop fish-drying and processing facilities and geothermal would offer a suitable solution if this technical option was known to the local populations. For instance, the Ol-Kokwe island in the middle of Lake Baringo in Kenya is inhabited by a fishing population. The island has steam vents and hot-springs which presently are only used for cleaning of clothes, but fish-processing using geothermal to preserve it and for sales are both not mastered by the local population for lack of specific knowledge (Fig. 6.30).

The lack of know-how is especially evident during the rainy season where high volumes of fish decompose and are consequently lost due to lack of good processing possibilities. This is best described by the common method of drying small fish like dagaa along the lake shores on sand close to landing sites where unexpected rain can cause high damages and loss of products.

Fig. 6.27: Village of Roquefort at the foot of Jurassic limestone cliffs that allowed for the development of karstic caves where the fermented cheese exported worldwide benefits from the best geothermal conditions for its maturation (Photo P.Thomas).

⁶Refers to the complete natural environment in which a particular wine is produced, including factors such as the soil, topography and climate.

Fig. 6.28: Afar fishing along the Red Sea coast near Edd. (Photo J.Varet, 1969).

Fig. 6.29: Fish market in Naivasha, Kenya. Photo J.Varet (2016)

Fig. 6.30: Ol-Kokwe Island (Lake Baringo, Kenya): Steam vents along a fault marking the northern shoreline; a resource that is used for cooking and cleaning, and available for drying fish for conservation and sales to the benefit of the local fishing community. (Photo J.Varet, 2015)

No demonstration project is as yet available in Africa but an example of a large-scale industrial operation that uses geothermal energy for fish-drying is known in Iceland, from where part of the products are sold in the West-African markets! Indoor drying has been applied for more than 35 years in places where geothermal energy is available. Salted fish, cod heads, cod backbones, stockfish and any small fish are among the products most commonly dried in this way. About 20 companies across Iceland dry fish using geothermal hot water and steam. One company drying seaweed has an annual capacity of 2,000 to 4,000 tons

using geothermal hot water, and the drying of pet food is an emerging industry, with annual production currently standing at about 500 tons (Arason, 2003; Bjornsson, 2006).

Fish is dried in a two-step process: i) primary drying in a rack tunnel dryer (Fig. 6.31) or conveyor dryer (Fig. 6.32) for between 24 and 40 hours at a drying temperature of between 20 and 26°C, to reduce the moisture content from 80 to 55 per cent; and ii) secondary drying in containers (Fig. 6.33) for 3 days at a temperature of 22 to 26°C, resulting in a moisture content of about 15 per cent (Arason, 2003).

Fig. 6.31: Rack geothermal tunnel dryer for fish-drying in Iceland (From Arason, 2013)

Fig. 6.32: (A: left) Conveyor for geothermal fish-drying in Iceland (From Arason, 2013) and (B: right) geothermally-dried fish backbones from the conveyor for export on the West African market.

Fig. 6.33: Secondary drying of fish in containers in Iceland

6.8 Abattoirs and other agro-industrial processes

6.8.1 The importance of livestock in Africa

Livestock is a major resource in Africa, and even the economic life-base for many, particularly the pastoralists. The reported livestock population of sub-Saharan Africa in 1999 comprised 191.3 million cattle, 158.7 million sheep, 182.1 million goats, 15.5 million pigs and 700 million chicken (FAOSTAT, 2000). Camels and donkeys are not considered in this statistic. According to FAO (Otte and Chilonda, 2002) East Africa has by far the largest population with 55.3 per cent of the total in sub-Saharan Africa, followed by West Africa, Southern Africa and Central Africa, with 27.1 per cent, 9.4 per cent and 8.2 per cent, respectively. Agricultural Ecological Zones (AEZs) are some of the most important determinants of the characteristics of livestock production systems, in terms of species, breed, stocking capacity, disease pressure, individual productivity, and so on. Fig. 6.34 illustrates these zones and one can observe that the EARV, where some of the strongest manifestations of geothermal resources occur, is characterised by a large

proportion of arid and semi-arid zones. This results from the low altitude of the Rift Valley floor.

The estimated cattle density, and population by zone and region in 1994 are presented in Fig. 6.35. One observes that Eastern Africa is characterised by the highest density of livestock in sub-Saharan Africa, with huge figures in the arid and semi-arid zones. Numerically, the lead species in the arid zone are goats and sheep, followed by cattle. In such places, livestock breeding is the most common economic activity with semi-nomadic pastoralist populations adapting their lifestyle to these harsh climatic conditions. Rainfall may, for example, not exceed 100 or 200 mm/yr in the Afar region (of Ethiopia, Eritrea and Djibouti).

Although the lower rainfall areas of the semi-arid zone (500 to 750 mm/yr) are best suited to grazing, livestock production in this zone is usually a component of mixed smallholder crop-livestock systems. The semi-arid zone has cattle as its lead species (with 30.6 per cent of all animal numbers), followed by goats and sheep. In the sub-humid zone, livestock production is undertaken together with some cultivation of crops.

Fig. 6.34: Agro-ecological zones in Sub-Saharan Africa showing the extension of arid zones in the East-African lowlands (FAO, 2002)

Fig. 6.35: Livestock in Sub-Saharan Africa: Cattle per surface unit (FAO, 2002)

Geothermal was used for centuries for cooking by the Maori in New Zealand. In Africa, sites with surface geothermal manifestations are particularly abundant in these arid and semi-arid zones characterising the rift floor where pastoralism is the main economic activity. Hence, applications of abattoirs and food processing based on the geothermal resource should be studied and developed with appropriate technologies adapted to the region.

Rotich et al. (2016) studied the perspective to develop geothermally-powered abattoirs in Kenya. They observed that most of the abattoirs along the Kenyan Rift do not meet the required level of hygiene and compliance to international standards, and so, they need to be replaced with modern and hygienic facilities. The study was based on medium level abattoirs with slaughter capacity of 200 heads of cattle and 225 small stock per working day. A more detailed pre-feasibility study for abattoir using geothermal was developed in a report prepared by USAID. The plant proposed is meant to engage both slaughter and processing of a range of meat products to increase viability of the operation with due regard given to the potential markets and livestock availability.

It results from the pre-feasibility study that, though the initial set up cost for a geothermally- operated abattoir is slightly higher than that of a conventionally powered one, there is a substantial cost-saving in relation to energy for a geothermal-powered facility. The profitability for a geothermal-powered abattoir is enhanced by value addition to the abattoir products too, as such a clean process will be preferred by the consumers.

There are different ways to process the abattoirs products: cooking, drying and sterilising. Sterilisation is an efficient step in meat canning, as it allows to stop the growth of bacteria, some (for example *Clostridium botulinum*), of which are toxic. The recommended temperature and time for killing the bacteria are 121°C for 3 minutes. Geothermal steam is normally used for food sterilisation processes, but either geothermal hot water or steam at a temperature of 105 to 120°C allows to sterilise equipment in the food processing, canning and bottling industries (Lund, 1996).

At present, pastoralist communities are frequently obliged to sell their products locally at rather low prices compared to the markets in cities and towns. In addition, when the dry season approaches, the animals are even more difficult to sell. It is recommended to create a demonstration for geothermal-powered abattoir and meat processing plant in the EARS, particularly in a pastoralist area, owned and operated by the local population allowing for better sales of their livestock all year round.

6.8.2. Egg Hatching and poultry farming

Another DUGD concerns Egg-Hatching and Poultry Farming. This is being tested by TGDC at Songwe geothermal site in Tanzania. Given that Tanzania is a net importer of chicken, it was shown that one of the reasons for importing chicken is high cost of energy for the incubation and post hatch phases in the poultry value chain. In order to cut down this cost, a geothermal heated incubator has been developed and successfully tested at Songwe. The next step is to upscale and diffuse the technology to other parts of the country where the geothermal resource is located. The technology

is simple, home-grown and rely upon geothermal resource at a temperature widely spread in the country. Lower the energy cost, it will increase the volume of production thus making the poultry industry vibrant and competitive.

6.9 Washing, peeling and blanching

A large amount of low-temperature energy (35 to 90°C) is consumed in domestic tasks as well as several industries for washing and cleaning. One principal consumer of low-temperature energy is washing of clothes as well as utensils and vessels used on a daily basis. It is also used in agriculture and industry for vegetable and fruit cleaning, in soft drinks and wine production, for container and reusable bottle washing (77°C), in poultry dressing as well as canning and other food processes. Textile industry finishing plants are another large consumer of wash water at 90°C. Sizeable amounts of hot water and other hot fluids at temperatures under 90°C are used for cars and transportation equipment, for degreasing and washing processes.

In the typical peeling operation, of fruits and vegetables, the product is introduced into a hot bath, and the skin or outer layer, after softening, is manually or mechanically scrubbed or washed off. Peeling equipment is continuous flow type in which the steam or hot water is applied directly to the product or indirectly by heating the product bath. In most instances, contact time with the product is short.

Blanching⁷ operations are similar to peeling. Product is usually introduced into a blancher⁸ to inhibit enzyme action, provide coating, or for cooking. Blanching may be either continuous or a batch operation. Industrial blanching fluids require closely controlled properties. Thus, the composition of the geothermal fluid needs to be adapted, otherwise a heat exchanger is required. The temperature range for most of the peeling and blanching systems is 77 to 104 °C, which is well adapted for geothermal applications.

6.10 Health applications: baths, swimming pools, hydrotherapy and spas

Natural spa springs are diffused all over the world and their use in pools is known since the most ancient of times. Mineral and thermal springs are used for recreational purposes or wellness applications and are available everywhere including Africa. They have been particularly used and developed in the Mediterranean basin, where these waters have been utilised and valorised for health and recreational purposes for millenniums. On both sides of the Mediterranean Sea, the Romans magnified this opportunity of personal and social care through the realisation of the monumental *thermae publicae*, with major spa buildings that included areas for baths, gardens, stadiums, gyms, rest-rooms and spaces for massages or health-related activities. Similarly, the Arabic and Turkish culture developed the hammams, also used at all levels of the society (see Fig. 2.30 above). Even more widespread is the tradition of baths developed in Japan and in Asia. Over centuries and for different cultures, spas have maintained a significant role of promoting health world-wide.

Nowadays, the increase in wellness awareness and fitness expectations has led to the exploitation of thermal waters and extended spa businesses, based on the notion of a joint interaction between natural resources and man-made enterprises. As shown by Valeriani et al. (2018), the spa economy is presently estimated at USD 94 billion, with a consistent growth perspective. The spa and recreational thermal water tourism mainly flows towards Europe, but also in North America and South-East Asia, with a lesser development in sub-Saharan Africa, where the resource and development perspective are particularly high. The application of thermal waters in swimming pools, spas and wellness centres represents a renewed and promising tool for prevention, rehabilitation and health promotion; providing possible physical, mental or social benefits. The therapeutic role of mineral elements and other chemical compounds present in thermal waters has been demonstrated. For example, treatments with mineral thermal water or mud have proved effective in pain relief and function restoration, impacting also on quality of life. The facilities have also been used in the treatment of skin and rheumatological diseases like knee and hand osteoarthritis, chronic low back pain and osteoporosis.

The water of natural spas should be of satisfactory micro-biological quality and must be adequately managed to control the exposure of bathers and personnel to infectious agents. Indeed, literature describes individual cases of outbreaks associated with the use of swimming/spa pools or similar environments, such as hot-springs, hot-tubs, whirlpools, natural spas, for recreation, wellness or therapeutic purposes. Knowledge on pool uses and on composition of the water that supplies the spa is needed for effective and appropriate management. Indeed, the particular and typical composition of each thermal water represents an interesting richness and a potentially beneficial property for health, but it also implies additional challenges in not adhering to the correct management, treatment and monitoring of that specific water in a defined application, such as aerosol, beverages, lavender or in a pool. Based on their geological composition, natural waters are enriched with different salts and ions, such as sulfur, halogens like chlorine (Cl), bromine (Br), iodine (I), or alkaline earth metals like magnesium (Mg) or calcium (Ca). Therefore, in natural spa pools, the water should be left untreated for assuring the specific composition, maintaining the original properties and the potential health benefits.

The last century saw massive changes and new trends in international health-tourism, where, alongside the traditional health services, thermal-tourism and wellness-fitness became increasingly popular. The spa industry has grown by 7.7 per cent annually, from USD 60 billion in 2007 to USD 94 billion in 2013, representing the fastest growing sub-sector in the health tourism and leisure sector. Following the number of publications from different regions, it can be noticed how the interest in this topic is mainly concentrated in Europe (42.3 per cent), Asia (26.3) and Africa (21.7 per cent); an indication of the potential the development of this sector has in the African continent.

⁷To blanch is to make white or pale by extracting colour.

⁸A machine for blanching or whitening

The first demonstration spa and hot-bath built by KenGen near the Olkaria geothermal plant, Naivasha (Kenya) is already a popular tourist destination (Fig. 6.36). The advantage of geothermal spas in Africa would be related to eco-tourism and the possibility to benefit from both a well-preserved natural environment, with authentic pastoralist ways of life and at the same time the wellness of geothermal fluid made available in clean natural conditions.

In an attempt to present in a synthetic way the technical and budgetary framework of an experimental site project for a park of hot-springs and a thermal bath-house in the environment of development at local community level in the EARS, we describe below a hypothetical pilot project that can be part of a logic of local development of the territory from a tourist point of view. This small thermal site project would also constitute a therapeutic response and a preventive health tool for sanitary purposes for the population of the territories considered.

Le Spa Francais, specialised in spa development worldwide summarised here the main elements necessary for the preliminary costing of such a pilot project. This, projecting to constitute a test for the implementation of an effective tool from the point of view of the social and economic development of the territories where it is located.

Some of key success factors for a global hot-spring destination village to be considered are:

- The rich geothermal potential.
- Possible synergies with other geothermal developments (other DUGD).
- Installation in a preserved natural site.
- Existence of some touristic interests (natural hills, proximity of natural springs, beautiful landscaping/landscapes, local cultural richness, wildlife).
- Potential for hot-spring destination open possibilities for a thermal/ medical destination.
- Such infrastructures should generate interest from local consumers and community.

- It is a very efficient tool of valorisation of the local economy. It also represents for local authorities a unifying project for the wealth of the territory (employment, measurable economic development in term of structural investments).
- Strong derived industrial potentialities generally exist regarding hot-springs business model itself like derivative products (mineral bottling plants, medical mud production, cosmetic) etc.

The price of construction for such a project varies a lot from one country to another. At this stage we just provide a rough estimation of the investment budget based on the diversified experience of Le Spa Français in Europe, North Africa, India, and China. In Europe or USA, the average price for a turnkey project for a spa resort generally reaches around 3,000 € per square metre for a Thermal Destination project including thermal hospitality.

For such a project in Africa, the construction and equipment costs could reach 1,500 € per square metre for a medium end level project. We took an estimated cost for identified turnkey project in China and India (50 per cent less than Europe).

Considering the hot-spring park project and due to the necessity of importing the specialised equipment for the technical aspects, careful thought of the estimate is necessary, taking into consideration the experimental nature of the project and the need to stick to the economic reality of the territory. The characteristics of the spa park project must integrate a maximum of local resources in the choice of materials and construction techniques. The cost of carrying out this experimental project will nevertheless have to include the import of specific equipment related to hydrotherapy and hot-springs industry applications, both for reasons of energy efficiency and health security of the project, making the project more expensive.

Budget estimates resulting from this approach are provided in Table 6.1, which include the program component summary and details about the hot-spring house (Table 6.2), and an optional complementary program for lodges and restaurant (Table 6.3).

Fig. 6.36: Geothermal spa built by KenGen in Naivasha, Kenya.

6.11 Derived sanitary products

As exemplified with well-known thermal springs sites like Vichy and Avene in France or Blue Lagoon in Iceland, the “derived products” as they are so-called, sold in specialised shops and luxury shopping places such as in the international airports and on the planes, tend to, with time bring in more income than the frequency of visitors to the thermal station itself. These are cosmetics, collagen, skin care products, shampoos, solar creams, deodorants, make-up, etc.

This kind of economic development is built, in fact from the reputation of the thermal station and site itself, and therefore cannot be envisaged as a first target when starting such a new economic development in Africa. It may however answer the needs of local markets to consider the perspective of organising the sales of such derived products to visitors of the region. For instance, in Northern Afar regional state, a phreatic explosion crater allows for salt products from deeper geological horizons to be accessible, and known in the surrounding regions for its beneficial medicinal properties. These salts are collected locally and sold on local popular markets.

6.12 Chemical extraction

Geothermal fluids contain a variety of chemical products. This is due to two factors:

- The thermal water will have circulated at depth, in contact with a variety of rocks not necessarily outcropping and containing chemical elements otherwise not accessible at the surface.
- The fact that, at high temperature encountered at depth, the solubility of certain elements increases drastically. As a result, the geothermal fluid travelling to the surface, eventually fast, in convective hydrothermal systems, will keep dissolved elements in the liquid or in the gas.

This is the case for a variety of chemical elements that may be extracted at the surface at marginal costs, as the fluid is made available by the geothermal exploitation and the cost for access is therefore limited to the minimum. Among the elements that are made available in the highest proportion and may have a good value, one can consider:

- Silica
- Lithium
- Metallic components like zinc, copper, magnesium, silver, gold
- Boron, cesium and rubidium,
- Hydrogen

The perspective of New Zealand was discussed by Climo et al. (2015). They did show the key to successfully developing the economic viability of a geothermal minerals industry in New- Zealand relies upon the connections between 7 factors (Fig. 6.37): technology, economics, market drivers and business risk that directly influence economic viability. In addition, the legal frameworks, technologies, and ultimately the chemical composition of the geothermal fluid in a given location.

Of course, among these factors, the mineral content in the fluid and the flow-rate of the production system is determinant. In the case of the Asal geothermal field in Djibouti, the author (Jacques Varet) calculated in a study for UNDP that, based on the fluid composition of the geothermal well A2 and a production of 50 MWe based on wells exploiting the same reservoir composition, among the various metallic products present (Zn, PB, As, Ag, Au among other), the most economic was silver (Ag).

In 2018, KenGen issued a call for the study of the presence of commercially viable minerals in the separated brine at Olkaria. It aimed at establishing the available quantities of those minerals (among them silica and lithium), and to demonstrate market need for those minerals locally, regionally and/or globally. Then to outline the development of a mineral extraction technology for extracting the minerals from brine, and finally draw the application of the technology developed by designing and developing a pilot extraction plant to demonstrate the functionality of the technology.

The main trend in R&D at present concerns lithium, as this metal is known to be increasingly in demand due to the development of electric-powered cars, whereas the production is concentrated in only a few countries in Latin America.

Table 6.3: Technical description and cost estimates for a spa thermal resort answering international standards in the hypothesis of an isolated location in a “geothermal village” project in the EARS (optional complementary program for lodges and restaurant, from E.Madec, LeSpaFrancais, Pers. Comm.)

Optional Component program				
Type of building	Estimate building cost €/m ²	Amenities	Area in m ²	Construction cost estimation (€)
The hot-spring lodge	1,200	10 rooms with 3 beds comfort for staying for a weekend or longer	938	1,125,000
The hot-spring restaurant	1,200	25 pax restaurant and all logistic equipment	375	450,000

Fig. 6.37: Interdependence and connections between the success factors for developing a geothermal minerals industry in New Zealand (From Climo et al., 2015)

Another line of research is to consider that native Hydrogen (H_2) drastically increases with temperature and may reach a few percent of the geothermal fluid. Given the high steam production of large geothermal plants, H_2 may become a valuable by-product when efficient separation methods will be proved to be economical.

6.13 Bottled mineral water

A major economic sector in the field of DUGD is the production and sale of bottled mineral water. In Europe, this is a flourishing industry with for instance waters from Evian, Vichy, Volvic, Perrier in France or San Pelegrino in Italy and many others in Europe that are not only sold locally but exported worldwide.

Revenue in the bottled water sector amounted to USD 273,996 million in 2020. The market is expected to grow annually by 7.5 per cent, but real mineral water is only a small part of these volumes. In global comparison, most revenue is generated in USA (USD 61,076 million in 2020). In relation to total population figures, per person revenues of USD 36.81 were generated in 2020. The average per capita consumption stood at 59.8 litres in 2020.

In Europe, Directive 2009/54/EC[45] deals with the marketing and exploitation of natural mineral waters in the EU. The two main types of bottled water recognised are mineral water and spring water. Broadly speaking, "mineral water" is ground-water that has emerged from the ground and flowed over rock. Treatment of mineral water is restricted to removal of unstable elements such as iron and sulfur compounds. Treatment of such minerals may extend only to filtration or decanting with oxygenation. Free carbon dioxide may be removed only by physical methods, and the regulations for introduction (or reintroduction) of CO_2 are strictly defined. Disinfection of natural mineral water is completely prohibited, including the addition of any element that is likely to change bacterial

colony counts. If natural mineral water is effervescent, it must be labelled accordingly, depending on the origin of the carbon dioxide: naturally carbonated mineral water (no introduction of CO_2); natural mineral water fortified with gas from the spring (reintroduction of CO_2); carbonated natural mineral water (CO_2 added following strict guidelines).

Directive 2001/83/EC[46] deals with bottled water that is considered a "medicinal product" and is thus excluded from the scope of the other regulation. Fig. 6.38 shows the part of the market of bottled water per continent. It shows that Africa is still an embryonic market. Hence, the perspective for development can be considered as high. African thermal waters however are already well known and eventually popular. This is for instance the case of Ambo water in Ethiopia. Ambo Mineral Water is a brand of naturally-carbonated bottled mineral water, sourced from the springs in Ambo Senkele near the town of Ambo in central Ethiopia. It is a popular drink in Ethiopia, and has been described as the "oldest modern mineral water", because it has been bottled since 1930. The company used to be state-owned but was sold to SAB Miller PLC. The plant produces 40,000 litres hourly (Fig.6.39).

Ambo Mineral Water is sourced from a thermal mineral spring that has significant amounts of natural calcium, magnesium, potassium, bicarbonates and carbon dioxide. The water is naturally carbonated by the carbon dioxide at the source. The water is derived from a volcanic fissure, from which it runs down a stream in a montane environment, and is collected in Ambo Senkele, Ethiopia, approximately 130 km South of Addis Ababa. It is sold in quite a few countries in Africa (Ethiopia, Kenya, Somalia, South Africa and Sudan) and even exported to other continents: Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, England, Sweden, United States and Canada.

6.14 District and buildings Heating/Cooling

The use of geothermal for district heating is widespread in Europe – notably in France in the sedimentary basins where hot aquifers are found at depth despite normal gradients (as seen above in Fig. 1.4.a and Fig.1.17) - and an option generalised in Iceland using wasted heat from geothermal plants producing electricity. The option of using a low-temperature geothermal source (from aquifers equipped with doublets, or even soils or rocks using vertical heat exchangers) for both heating and cooling is also developing fast in the northern hemisphere, at collective or even individual level (as illustrated above in Fig.1.1 and Fig.5.8).

As also already discussed, in the case of Africa, where heating needs are generally reduced, this could be an option for building and district cooling, particularly for cities located in the arid low lands (for instance Semera, capital of the Afar Regional State of Ethiopia, or in the case of the capital of Djibouti) and other port-towns in the inter-tropical regions where temperature may reach levels of 45 or even peak at 50°C.

Fig. 6.38: World bottled water consumption in 1999, in litres/year/person and (in per cent) (Ferrier, 2001)

6.15 Direct use for circular economy

DUGD can provide typical examples of “circular economy”, an economic system aimed at eliminating waste and the continual use of resources. Such systems, often traditionally well-developed in these communities that live in harmony with their natural environment, adapting to climate and other changes and constraints, through reuse, sharing, refurbishment, repair, remanufacturing and recycling to create a closed-loop system. This allows to minimise the use of resource inputs and the generation of waste, pollution and carbon emissions. The circular economy aims at keeping products, equipment and infrastructure in use for longer, thus improving the productivity of these resources. Energy, water and any materials can become input for other processes: either a component or recovered resource for another man-made process or as regenerative resources for nature (e.g., waste water for irrigation, compost and sewage for soil enrichment, etc). This regenerative approach, in contrast to the traditional linear economy, which has a “take, make, dispose” model of production, is a resilient form of civilisation for which DUGD offers a key component.

Fig. 6.39: Ambo mineral water bottling plant, Ethiopia

Fig. 6.39: Local residents collect water from the natural geothermal steam (fumarole) rising from the ground in a ravine within the Corbetti Caldera.

Photo credit: Robert Sauer, USAID Ethiopia/flickr

CHAPTER 7:

SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS MODELS

At present, the lack of references for DUGD systems in Africa is a real handicap for the credibility of the approach. Despite the fact that numerous such devices are operating under various forms worldwide, such as in Western United States (Basin and Range in particular), in various places in Europe, Iceland, New Zealand, Japan or China, there is still a need to demonstrate that such operations are feasible and economical in the African context. Besides this, the socio-economic conditions prevailing in these northern countries may not apply in Africa.

It is worth noting that, basically, DUGD are decarbonised, decentralised, resource-efficient and climate-resilient systems operating in a self-management arrangement with a self-contained circular economy. The DUGD system serves the direct needs of the users on site and relies upon exchanges of various kinds (information, know-how) within the concerned communities. This is in fact the major strength of these systems.

Relying upon local renewable sources, the added value provided by a given DUGD project is essentially beneficial for the local stakeholders. The incomes generated by the sales resulting from the quantitative and qualitative increase as well as the diversification of the production generated by the project allows to pay for the maintenance costs and for new investments, thus enabling expansion of the network and diversification of the uses of the geothermal fluids.

However, the initial investment will generally require cash or loans that will need to be paid back in hard currency by the external sales (electricity or products generated by the DUGD). Besides exploration and feasibility studies, this initial investment concerns in particular the drilling of the production wells, the piping and other devices, such as separators, heat exchangers or pumps, as well as a steam turbine or ORC plant and mini-grid, as well as the project engineering.

The economy of each project will vary considerably according to the kind of production and added-value generated. For example, flower production for export from greenhousing will bring in new finances in terms of hard currencies, but not necessarily serve the direct needs of the population (except for job creation), whereas food-processing may allow for a better use of the agricultural (or fishing) production on site all year-round (and not only in the production period when prices are the lowest) with some added value from additional sales. Spa and ecotourism based on thermal facilities will also produce cash, whereas electricity production from an ORC plant would beneficially replace the diesel-powered local electric plant, reducing the earlier imports of fuel. Electricity sales through grid expansion also increase the regular incomes. Calculation shows (see section 2.5) that an ORC plant, based on shallow depth medium enthalpy¹ wells allows for an electrical production that is much cheaper than if produced from fossil fuels and even competes with large-sized geothermal plants serving the grid, due to lower drilling costs despite more expensive power plants (in USD/MWe).

7.1 Community-driven models

The most recommended option, in terms of community ownership and economy for the final user is the community-driven project. However, this should rely upon community's social, political and financial engagement, and administrative as well as technical capabilities existing or to be mobilised on site. The problem encountered in Africa, is the relative weakness, or even total lack of such intermediate corps in the society. There is frequently a lack of technical services at municipality level, except for major cities and capital towns. Policies of devolution exist in several countries (such as in Kenya), or even federal systems with "regional states" (such as in Ethiopia) but the possibility to master such projects rarely exist at that level. Besides these administrative and political entities, it is generally possible to rely upon the initiative of a CBO in which concerned citizens will join efforts to engage a project answering the needs of their community. But here again, we have to face the problem of the capability of the entity to manage and operate a project which relies upon administrative, technical and financial experience, rarely available at that level. Two examples are known to exist in Africa, with AGAP in Ethiopia and HHGCBO in Kenya (see section 8.1 below).

7.2 Government-driven models

Government initiative is definitely one of the ways to help start geothermal developments both for electricity production and DUs. African countries which up to now have succeeded in geothermal developments for electricity production (Kenya and Ethiopia) have relied upon government initiatives through state-owned companies to achieve this. For the DUs, such a direct involvement at state level is less necessary, given the local nature of the resources' usage.

Public support is however fully justified at R&D and demonstration levels. This is what is observed in Kenya, where both public entities in charge of geothermal development and production, KenGen and GDC, have developed demonstration sites for DUs aside from their power plants in Naivasha and Menengai. It is also what appears to be the case from the proposals made in Ethiopia both in Tendaho (for powering a sugar factory) and Abaya (for tobacco-drying) aside from electrical power plants being planned on those sites. The effort being made by TGDC in the Songwe geothermal prospect including drilling of temperature gradient (TG) wells and the possibility of using the hot water for a large variety of direct use applications (detailed in Chapter 6) is another significant example of a government-driven demonstration site for DU.

Another option, as is the case in Tunisia and Algeria, is to generate projects handled by ad-hoc entities at regional or local level through strong initial public support at national level.

Our recommendation here would be for concerned governments to support DU development initiatives through:

- Supporting dissemination of information to the general public concerning geothermal resources and opportunities;

¹At times referred to simply as ME

- R&D and demonstration projects handled at municipal, county, or community level, with the proper incentives;
- Ensuring the implementation of teaching and capacity building at TVET and university levels;
- Supporting with ad-hoc policies; private initiatives providing first success stories;
- Implementing at national level (or Africa's regional level apart from GRMF) a facility allowing to cover at least part of the geological risks of these projects (even if much less than for the HT exploration)

Such conditions, although exceptional, may also be encountered in other parts of Africa. But until now, despite having operated successfully for years, this private sector DUGD project model has not been duplicated. This relies in particular on the lack of ad-hoc legal framework for such projects. Even the present GRMF although suited for electricity generation projects (with for instance, well-established leases and guaranteed feed-in tariffs) do not fit for DU projects as seen from the experience encountered by a private company that intended to develop a maltster powered by a geothermal resource identified in the MER a few years ago. .

7.3 Private sector-driven: PPP/IPP

The most significant DUGD in Africa is a private investment: the Oserian Flower Farm, in Naivasha, Kenya with large greenhouses powered by geothermal energy. The project benefitted from the local proximity of the Olkaria geothermal power plant and a marginal well, better suited for DU applications than electricity production. It also benefitted from a particular market condition in which the whole production is exported, generating directly the hard currencies needed to pay for the initial investments and part of the running costs.

In the OECD countries, particularly in Europe and USA, there are energy providers (IPPs) – originally specialised in oil, gas or electricity – now diversifying to REs. Although frequently targeting the sales to the public grid, they may also include in their offer a service for heat sales and eventually other DU applications. Such companies have the capacity to operate projects at local level in PPPs, in the frame of structures called SEM in which both parties will jointly manage the project for the benefit of all, the first beneficiary being the final consumer benefiting from lower energy prices and bills II.

CHAPTER 8:

ENABLING INSTITUTIONAL AND LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORKS

As we start on this chapter devoted to institutional and legislative framework, let us keep in mind that geothermal has been used for centuries – if not for millennia! (Gardo & Varet, 2020) – in various places within the EARV from the dry Afar triangle (Ethiopia, Djibouti, Eritrea), to the region along the MER and in the KRV where it was also applied in Eburru, Kenya, for purely DU without electricity generation. For over 80 years, due to lack of potable water in the area, the residents have also been condensing the steam used in the dryer and from steam traps mounted on the ground to provide water for their domestic use. Steam from a shallow borehole was also used at Eburru (see Fig. 6.18) to dry pyrethrum and cereals, honey-processing, or chick-hatching and brooding, (Kinyanjui & Mburu, 2012). Other traditional examples in Africa are found in Tunisia, Algeria and Morocco in the numerous “hammams” where popular hot-water and steam baths were developed even before Roman Empire times all over North Africa from Morocco to Egypt. These types of projects have been developed around hot-springs or steam vents without institutional or legislative backing. Most of them are not even counted in the national statistics of geothermal uses!

Consequently, DU projects in Africa are so far either ill-known or ignored by the authorities in charge of energy policies, despite being used artisanally for long, and have generally not benefited from concessional funding in spite of the massive potential of the resources and the technologies. This is attributed to lack of adequate awareness, at all levels in the concerned societies. Consultation with stakeholders revealed that the difficulty of funding DU projects is partly attributed to lack of knowledge concerning these solutions by concerned authorities and the consequent lack of demonstrable financial viability in modern accounting.

Differing from high enthalpy geothermal projects serving the national electric grid, DUGD responds to local needs and therefore first necessitates the involvement of local inhabitants who become stakeholders. They should not be considered by the developer as merely “final users” but should be part of the entity in charge of the project identification, study, development and maintenance. It is even better if the entity in charge is initiated and established by the local population on site. The owner of the geothermal system should ideally be the community of the final users. It should therefore take the form of the most appropriate entity: either a CBO, or a company owned by the local stakeholders, a municipal public entity, a co-operative or a “mixed” (private-public) enterprise, known as SEM in French.

Of course, some space should be left open for private initiatives, serving the needs of a specific entity (like a milk-processing factory, an industry specialised in wood-processing, construction materials, food-drying, fish-farming, greenhousing, sanitary and touristic resort, such as a thermal spa, etc). As a whole, the approach should take into account the existence of any other potential users of the geothermal resource on site, as well as the possible entrance of other consumers, if any exist on site or are willing to come on board and offering to take part in the project. Ideally, any newcomer should be given the opportunity to also benefit from the resource in a negotiated arrangement between the parties.

In this chapter, we will recapitulate the main operational recommendations concerning the institutional and legislative framework governing DUGD, which eventually are still lacking in most African countries due to the limited experience on the subject.

8.1 Project Management (with an illustration of community-owned DU initiative in Afar)

This question has already been discussed in section 6.2, and has been shown in section 7.1 that it concerns all components of the project, from exploration and production, to mini-grid and networks as well as proper share of the benefits locally, marketing, sales, maintenance and provisions for future extension.

This situation implies the need for some technical capabilities, although not absolutely essential as it may be hired externally. The most important is to acquire a real support of the population locally, for them to become not only users but real stakeholders of the project. This implies not only the leaders, the elders and the most educated segments of the community but also women and girls who are frequently in charge of the energy and water questions at family and community levels. The men and boys, particularly in the pastoralist communities are likely to be the ones who are best placed to know the geological indices of interest, like fumaroles, hot grounds, alteration zones, etc., owing to their outdoor role linked to taking livestock for grazing which involves searching for pasture and water.

But the main challenge, as exposed earlier in chapter 6, is the general management capabilities that are too frequently lacking at local level, where traditional rules are better known than the legal, administrative and even political conditions at national level.

Once the geothermal resource is assessed on site, and local demand identified implying all potential uses (at the pre-feasibility stage, ideally engaged under public funding); the stakeholders on site will need to take care of and ensure compliance with national or regional regulations, benefit (where possibilities exist) from specific facilities and initiatives (like incentives for climate-friendly projects), eventually backed by bilateral or multi-lateral funding. The next step will be to establish the best-suited legal form of local entity that will be in charge of the DUGD project.

This should be done at the feasibility study stage, the local entity being initially – or becoming during the process - the owner of this study, even if initiated and partly financed from external sources. The same entity should then preferably become the manager of the construction of the DUGD project, and the owner of the geothermal system. It should ideally be the specialised “arm” and legal expression of the concerned community, implying all the final users. This should take the form of the most appropriate entity, given the legal formula existing in the country and may be a:

- CBO,
- Company owned by the local stakeholders,

- Municipal, county or district public entity,
 - Co-operative (for example. existing agricultural, agro-processing or fishing entity)
 - “Mixed” (private-public) enterprise (referred to as SEM in French).
- At present, as mentioned above, two examples of such local initiatives are known to exist in the region:
- AGAP: Established in 2015 (Table 8.1)
 - HHGCBO: Established in 2017

Table 8.1: Example of a local geothermal development company in Ethiopia: Check list for AGAP

Name: Afar Geothermal Alternative Power Share company (AGAP)								
Legal form, nature of business Investment :								
Permit no. N/026/2009 from the Afar National Regional State Investment Office in line with the investment law of Ethiopia.								
Business License no. 686/2010 from the Afar National Regional State in line with the commercial law of Ethiopia								
Principal place of business address of its head office								
Afar Regional State, Zone 1								
Semera Logya Woreda, Logya Town, Tel + 251 911 840014								
E-mail: gardoali@yahoo.com								
Name, address, telephone number, and email address of the CEO								
Ismael Ali Gardo, General Manager								
Tel. +251 912 840017								
E-mail: gardoali@yahoo.com								
Afar Regional State, Zone 1, Semera/Logya Woreda.								
Name and nationality of every director, the name of any person owning capital share:								
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>S.N</th> <th>Name</th> <th>Nationality</th> <th>Share holder/ Director</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td><i>12 names are provided</i></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	S.N	Name	Nationality	Share holder/ Director		<i>12 names are provided</i>		
S.N	Name	Nationality	Share holder/ Director					
	<i>12 names are provided</i>							
Office address in the capital: Kiros K. Ketema, Woreda 08, Home N° # 004, Addis Abeba, Ethiopia								
Telephone: +251 91 284 0017 ; +251 912840017 Email: gardoali@yahoo.com								

Table 8.2: GRMF and DUGD (from GRMF site)

<p>GRMF Announcement:</p> <p>After five successful Application Rounds of the Geothermal Risk Mitigation Facility (GRMF) with 30 awarded projects, the Regional Geothermal Coordination Unit (RGCU) of the African Union Commission (AUC) is currently assessing the potential of a scope extension. Therefore, the RGCU would like to gather market information both for the financing situation from the exploration phase up to the power plant operation, and for direct-use projects in East Africa.</p> <p>The results of this survey will form the informational base for the discussions with the relevant financing institutions and donors, in order to develop further financial instruments for the advanced project phases, and to assess the potential financial support for direct-use projects.</p> <p>Please fill the survey form until 12 February 2020 on the following link: https://survey.roedl.com/limesurvey/index.php/412455</p> <p>Feel free to contact the GRMF team via the website www.grmf-eastafrika.org. The survey will take approx. 15-20 minutes (depending on your internet connectivity). Once the survey and the internal discussions are finalised, all stakeholders (including participants of this survey) as well as relevant media will be informed accordingly.</p> <p>Many thanks in advance for your cooperation and contribution to this next development stage of GRMF.</p> <p>Your GRMF team</p> <p>Note: All data as submitted by the participants will be kept confidential by the GRMF.</p>

The projects proposed by AGAP in the Afar Regional State of Ethiopia entails the development of small power plants (a few 100 to a few 1000 kW in size) serving the needs of local communities for both electricity and direct uses including water production. Besides electricity supply, such projects are meant to supply thermal energy and water to support the local agro-pastoral & industrial development, which is based on livestock keeping. When issues of food-water-energy nexus are promoted as part of the project, then available incentives may be easier to access. In addition, the decentralised geothermal developments in such areas where steam is available at the surface require shallower and cheaper wells to be drilled thus lowering the whole project budget. It is foreseen that DU could play a catalytic role to diversify the economy and stimulate artisanal economy or even industrialisation in local development centres. In such cases, as mentioned earlier, geothermal offers a low carbon, resource-efficient and climate-resilient solution in these lowland arid regions of Africa deeply affected by recurrent droughts resulting from climate change.

8.2 Need for a specific support system

Presently, in terms of DUGD in Africa, there is a lack of existing entities that could help in duplicating a model that has proved its efficiency, and that could eventually help in diffusing its know-how at regional level in the continent. We therefore have to rely upon advice from external entities that have developed such systems elsewhere in the world, and/or with consultants helping to develop the required local capacities.

Some prototypes exist in Kenya (drying plant in Eburru; milk-processing, laundry and greenhousing in Menengai; spa in Olkaria). However, all of them are directly related to nearby high enthalpy geothermal systems offering such diversifications as a by-product or technology promotion. A few hot-spring resorts also exist in Ethiopia, the main and historic one – still used for bathing, swimming pools and sanitary hot-water distribution in hostels - being in Addis Ababa. Indeed, even the location of Addis Ababa as the capital of the Empire in the 19 century was a decision made due to the presence of hot-springs along faults bordering the Nubian plateau towards the Rift Valley.

Lack of policies and enabling regulatory frameworks for DU is primarily due to the lack of awareness and can partly be attributed to a limited assessment of DU potential due to emphasis on power generation by the region's governments because geothermal departments are by and large hosted by Ministries of Energy whose main mandate is the generation of electricity, or eventually favor the search for oil. This lack of appropriate government support induces fears concerning the viability and potential of DU projects. However, this is gradually changing since countries in the Western Branch of EARS and other parts of Africa have understood the emphasis to be placed on low-to-medium temperature resources suitable mainly for DU (Omenda, et al., 2016). Pre-feasibility studies carried out by GDC with the support of USAID confirmed that DUGD should be viable at commercial scale in Kenya for some applications and recommended the identification of other solutions using appropriate tools. Uganda also carried out, with the support of EAGE pre-feasibility studies for various DU applications

in combination with electricity generation in Kibiro and Panyimur geothermal prospects (see Fig. 2.25 in Chapter 2) In a similar vein, the TGDC is drilling temperature gradient wells with a view to use the low-to-medium temperature geothermal resources for DU applications at the Songwe geothermal prospect.

Measures that would help promote DU in the region include sharing of information on successful projects, as well as capacity development on projects' identification and development. A recommendation by several geothermal stakeholders is that the benefits of DU, particularly the socio-economic impacts, should be clearly outlined in order to influence decision-makers and local communities to support its implementation. However, most of them indicated a lack of technical capability to undertake such studies. A methodology developed by the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO, GIZ, 2019) to assess the costs and benefits of implementing sustainable energy solutions in agri-food value chains can help for this purpose.

According to IRENA (2020) among policies and incentives which could support DUGD, an option is to engage specific roadmaps with targets as well as fiscal and financial incentives such as tax breaks and subsidies. Examples from France, Germany and the Netherlands show that accelerated DUGD was preceded by the development of enabling policies, regulatory frameworks and supportive incentives. In France, a geological risk-coverage was put in place for geothermal DU projects in the 1970's, allowing for the development of projects owned and handled at municipality level (Varet, 1982), which allowed for the implementation of heating and sanitary hot water production installed for 250,000 houses equivalent between 1976 and 1986. In the Netherlands, the geothermal action plan set a target of generating 11PJ of energy from geothermal heat plants by 2020. Besides, 5PJ of geothermal energy per year is ear-marked for development and utilisation in horticulture. Mexico published a roadmap for geothermal DU development which envisaged the growth on installed geothermal heat from 156 MWt in 2013 to 3,800 by 2030. The roadmap highlights potential DU applications, barriers to implementation and strategies to overcome them (IRENA, 2019). The NZGA has published a guide aimed at providing a strategic approach to develop DUGD in New Zealand which is expected to result in an annual increase of 7.5 PJ of geothermal DU as well as employment of an additional 500 people due to new projects between 2007 and 2030 (NZGA, 2017). In contrast, for the period up to 2030, in Africa, only the United Republic of Tanzania through TGDC indicated in the survey for this report that it had set targets for DU installation.

One of the aims of this guidebook is to help for such facility to be implemented in a suitable and attractive way for geothermal DU developers, One aspect would be to extend the GRMF existing at present for covering the geological risk inherent to high enthalpy project to DU projects. This perspective was considered, and announced (see Table 8.2), but it is yet to be implemented. One of the aims of this guidebook is to help for such facility to be implemented in a suitable and attractive way DGU developers.

Table 8.3: Factors and actors contributing to successful RE policy (IPCC, 2020)

Dimension of enabling environment: Factors and actors contributing to successful RE policy	Integrating policies (national/supranational policies)	Reducing financial and investment risk	Planning and permitting at the local level	Providing infrastructure, network and markets for RE technology	Technology transfer and capacity building	Learning from actors beyond government
Institutions	Integrating RE policies with other policies at the design level reduces the potential for conflicts among government policies.	Development of financing institutions and agencies can aid cooperation between countries, provide soft loans or international carbon finance (CDM). Long-term commitment can reduce perception of risk.	Planning and permitting processes enable RE policy to be integrated with non-RE policies at the local level.	Policy-makers and regulators can enact incentives and rules for network and markets such as security standards and access rules.	Reliability of RE technologies can be ensured through certification. Institutional agreements enable technology transfer.	Openness to learning from other actors can complement design of policies and enhance their effectiveness by working within existing social conditions.
Civil society (individuals, household, NGOs, unions, etc.).	Municipalities or cities can play a decisive role in integrating state policies at the local level.	Community investment can share and reduce investment risk. PPP in investment and project development can contribute to reducing risk associated with policy instruments. Appropriate international institutions can enable an equitable distribution of funds.	Participation of civil society in local planning and permitting processes might allow for selection of the most socially relevant RE projects.	Civil society can become part of supply networks through co-production of energy and new decentralised models.	Local actors and NGOs can be involved in technology transfer through new business models bringing together multi-national companies/NGOs/SMEs.	Civil society participation in open policy processes can generate new knowledge and induce institutional change. Municipalities or cities may develop solutions to make RE technology development possible at the local level. People (individually or collectively) have a potential for advancing energy-related behaviors when policy signals and contextual constraints are coherent.
Finance and business communities		PPP in investments and project development can contribute to reducing risk associated with policy instruments.	RE project developers can offer know-how and professional networks in: i). Aligning project development with planning and permitting requirements ii). Adopting planning and permitting process to local needs and conditions. Business can be active in lobbying for coherent and integrated policies.	Clarity of network and market rules improves investor confidence	Financing institutions and agencies can partner with national government, provide soft loans or international carbon finance (CDM).	Multi-national companies can involve local NGOs or SMEs as partners in new technology development (new business models). Development of corporations and international institutions reduces risk of investment.
Infrastructure	Policy integration with network and market rules can enable development of infrastructure suitable for a low-carbon economy.	Clarity of network and market rules reduces risk of investment and improves investor confidence.		Clear, transparent network and market rules are more likely to lead to infrastructures complementary to a low-carbon future.		City and community level framework for the development of long-term infrastructure and networks can sustain involvement of local actors in policy development.

8.3 Policy, Legal and Regulatory Framework

Most countries in the world, including Africa, developed objectives and eventually even policies in order to fix RE targets. (Fig. 8.1) Although Africa is not the most advanced continent one can observe that Eastern and Northern Africa (with the exception of Libya) are well engaged in these policies.

Analysis of the current status in the region indicates that no policies really exist to specifically guide and regulate DUGD. However, there are licensing procedures for DU in Ethiopia and to some extent in Kenya, but regulations have not been developed in both countries to guide investment in this sector. In Ethiopia, licensing of DU projects is undertaken separately from power generation and is restricted to resources of up to 120°C (the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2016). In Kenya, the Energy Act of 2019 emphasizes power generation aspect of geothermal development while DU is mentioned as co-development if resource characteristics allow. However, it appears that these legal frameworks are yet to really be applied.

8.3.1 Ethiopia

In the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, any geothermal project shall be submitted to the Licensing Authority for registration and initial review. DUGD necessitate a "Grade II Geothermal Resource License" issued by the EEA. Grade I Licenses concern the high enthalpy geothermal projects.

If the project utilises a total of 2,000,000 m³ or less of geothermal fluids annually and the anticipated temperature of the resource is 120°C or lower, the application is promptly sent/transferred to the authorised licensing entity in the State where the proposed project would be located for further review and issuance or denial of a license by the State. If more than 2,000,000 m³ of geothermal fluids annually with anticipated temperature greater than 120°C, the EEA shall process the application in accordance with the applicable health, safety, environmental and drilling requirements for Grade I Licenses and shall coordinate its review with the State of the proposed location of the anticipated project.

The application shall be made in writing to the EEA on the prescribed form, accompanied by the prescribed application fees, and shall include a list of information and documents on the entity and a description of the proposed project including detailed geological maps, geothermometer temperatures based on water and gas sampling, interpretation of any geophysical surveys conducted, a proposal for delineation of the license, with proposed access, identification of human habitation including nomadic communities, business plan including anticipated types of products, revenues and expenses during the license period, employment and training benefiting the local community; information on the technical and financial capacity; a description of production, discharge and injection with adequate testing and monitoring plan to measure fluid temperature; program of employment and training; a description of the types of goods and services that will be obtained within Ethiopia and those that will be obtained from outside. Such Geothermal Resource Licenses shall be issued on an exclusive non-competitive basis for DU of geothermal resources. It shall be issued for a maximum period of 25 years and may be renewed at the end of the period.

Early 2011

Fig. 8.1 : Countries with at least one Renewable Energy (RE) specific deployment target and/or at least one RE specific deployment policy (figures from 2011, in EIA, 2020).

8.3.2 Kenya

In Kenya, which is the most advanced country in Africa in terms of current geothermal development projects, the national legislation dates back to 1982 with the "Geothermal Resources Act No. 12", which defines the subject: "geothermal resources means any product derived from and produced within the earth by natural heat; and includes steam, water and water vapor and a mixture of any of them that has been heated by natural heat whether as a direct product or resulting from other material introduced artificially into an underground formation and heated by natural heat" and goes ahead to precise that "All un-extracted geothermal resources under or in any land shall be vested in the Government subject to any rights which, by or under any written law, have been or are granted or recognised as being vested in any other person", so that "no person shall sink a bore, tap or take and use or apply geothermal resources for any purpose unless he is first granted an authority or license". The Act further specifies that the Minister "may authorise any person (including a public officer), in writing, to make surveys, investigations, tests and measurements in search of geothermal resources and for that purpose the authorised person may (a) enter upon any land specified in the authority with such assistants, gear, appliances, and equipment as he thinks fit; (b) sink any bore...; (c) make geological surveys and geophysical surveys ...; and (d) generally do all things necessary in connection with the survey, investigation, test or measurement", and then may grant a license "to drill and construct all necessary boreholes; ... erect, construct and maintain houses and buildings ... erect, construct and maintain plant, machinery, buildings and other ... to utilise the geothermal resources... and utilise any water;...".

In 2018, a new National Energy Policy was published which stipulates the mission of the Government as: "Facilitate provision of clean, sustainable, affordable, competitive, reliable and secure energy services at least cost while protecting the environment", and specifies that "to enhance exploitation of the vast geothermal resources that Kenya is endowed with, the Government will continue to fund the Geothermal Development Company (GDC) so as to manage the geothermal exploration risk and attract investors... Further, the Government will encourage investment in the geothermal sub-sector so as to achieve at least ... 2,056MW by 2024, and enhance direct use of the resource".

In 2019, the "Energy Act" operationalise the government policy in a detailed document (168p.). It specifies Government obligations as, who "shall facilitate the provision of affordable energy services to all persons in Kenya... provide energy in all areas". Where "a supply of energy in any area is necessary and upon assessment it is established to be commercially inexpedient to provide for the necessary reticulation by any licensee, the Cabinet Secretary or County Executive ... may undertake the provision of any such works or provide the funds necessary for the development of such works... develop and implement a fair, transparent and equitable strategy to ensure that all households are connected to a supply of electricity by 2030... develop a conducive environment for the promotion of investments in energy infrastructure ... disseminate the guidelines among potential investors". A Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation is established, but for Geothermal Energy, it is the Cabinet Secretary who authorises to "search of geothermal resources... sink any well ... make geological and geophysical surveys; and generally do all things necessary in connection with the survey, investigation, test or measurement... grant a license over part or the whole of a geothermal resources area" in order to "drill and construct all necessary wells; erect, construct and maintain houses and buildings ... construct and maintain plant, machinery, buildings ...utilise the geothermal resources... reclaim and utilise any water...".

At the local level, "A County Government shall establish a fund for the purposes of promotion of efficient use of energy and its conservation within the County" that ... "shall be credited all grants and loans that may be made by the County or National Government or any other organisation or individual"... A County Government shall establish a fund for the purposes of promotion of efficient use of energy and its conservation within the County. Establishment of a Fund by County Government. To the Fund shall be credited all grants and loans that may be made by the County Government or, National Government or any other organisation or individual for the purposes of this Act".

To this respect, regulations are to be published, notably for "prescribing the value of geothermal energy at the well head... providing guidelines on direct use of geothermal energy.

CHAPTER 9:

RESEARCH, INFORMATION
AND CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT

9.1. Current situation and identified needs

At present, in Africa as in many other parts of the world, local populations and most individuals have no information concerning the geothermal resources available underground in the place where they live or administer. They have no idea of the resource and even less concerning the possible applications that could be developed using this resource.

Of course, there is generally a good knowledge of natural emergences of hot-springs, and fumaroles and these are eventually used for direct and simple applications like cloth washing (Fig. 5.20), bathing (Fig. 5.21), cooking eggs, or vegetables, and of course using the water itself for human consumption (drinking water or tea) (Fig. 6.39), drinking of the water by the livestock from hot springs (Fig. 5.23) or geothermal steam condensation (Fig. 5.24), irrigation of pasture for animal grazing or for agriculture (Fig. 5.25 & 5.26). When the water is available in the form of steam, condensation devices are frequently developed – particularly in arid regions – for liquid water production by condensing using natural materials available locally (like rock-walls and acacia branches, (Fig. 5.27 & 5.28) eventually improved with cementation of the condensation towers, (Fig. 5.29) or systems built with industrial products available in the nearby commerce centre (Fig. 2.16).

9.1.1 Need for information programs

The limited or lack of information by local populations regarding the geothermal resources on their land means that – in order to develop DUGD, a huge effort around awareness creation, information generation and dissemination is needed, in order to reach the target population, at all possible level. This is detailed in chapter 5.

9.1.2 Need for education projects

An efficient education programme developed at regional level in Africa, and customised to national and regional states as well as district levels, particularly in places where geothermal resources are known to be abundant could be sufficient to induce the popularisation of DUGD, especially, if the approach also mobilises the press and other media, including social media. This is detailed in Chapter 5.

9.13 The African Geothermal Centre of Excellence

An African-led and owned Center of Excellence for geothermal; The AGCE is in the process of being established and will be hosted by the Government of Kenya. UNEP in collaboration with AUC and relevant partners is supporting the establishment of this fully-fledged Center of Excellence. This Center of Excellence is meant for developing capacity (skilled manpower) of the continent in terms of geothermal science and technology as well as engineering for both power generation and DU applications. Presently, UNEP hosts an IPCU of AGCE to respond to the urgent training needs of African countries using the KenGen and GDC geothermal training facilities in Kenya.

Kenya successfully embraced the option of renewable energy sources making it an exemplary country in the use of geothermal power in Africa and the West. We are considering Kenya as the main hub of the African region in terms of capacity development for geothermal technology. This is also the main achievement because they have built very good experience as well as institutional and infrastructural capacities. They can share their best practices with the rest of the world, said Meseret Zemedkun (UNEP). The government's commitment in supporting geothermal technology is also demonstrated in the sound national scale of the budget allocated to the project: It is really not common in any other African country. You can see the government is committed and allocates the funds for geothermal resources, she said.

It is also observed that Kenya has developed a clear and coherent geothermal policy anchored on the Geothermal Act which strengthens PPPs in developing RE power projects. The government's financial support, PPPs and legal framework of geothermal technology are exemplary approaches that the rest of the world, especially African countries can emulate to implement the technology.

The project also aims to promote geothermal power for DU applications, thus increase the use of RE, with the aim of reducing GHG emissions, similar to what is being done in developed countries. Since its creation, various local, regional and continental geothermal fora have recognised the AGCE to be a vehicle to ensure the development of skilled manpower for sustainable geothermal development in the continent

9.2 Components of the DUGD and manpower optimisation

9.2.1 Major components of a DUGD project, required knowledge and skills

For clarification purpose, a DUGD project can be broken down into different components or steps, corresponding to the different professional categories and tasks involved (see Table 9.1):

- The energy and fluid identification, production and management (including eventually reinjection), as well as geoscientific studies and drilling operation for geothermal fluid and ground-water.
- The processing devices conception, construction and management: fluid-separators, heat-exchangers, steam turbine or ORC plant, cascade uses devices.
- The "mini-grid" allowing the distribution on site of the energy (electricity or heat) and fluid produced (steam, liquid-water, chemical components contained in the thermal water) as well as the maintenance of the system.
- The local trade structure implying accountants and banking support, the benefits from each stakeholder allowing a repayment of the investments and maintenance costs.

If these services are handled by different legal entities on site,

Table 9.1: Major components of DUGD and type of skills / jobs involved

Component /step	Activity concerned	Skills/jobs requested
Reconnaissance	Geosciences – Social sciences	Geologist, geochemist geophysicist, anthropologist, sociologist, economist
Fluid production	Drilling and tests	Drilling engineer, drillers, geologists, geochemists production and reservoir engineer
Process devices	Surface engineering for fluids, electrical and thermal uses	Civil engineer, fluid engineer, electrical engineer, plumbing, technicians and workers
Mini-grid	System engineering, electrical and grid management as well as maintenance	System engineer, electrical and grid manager, maintenance staff
Management	Trade, economic and financial management	General manager, commerce economist, accountant

the project risks appearing, at quick glance, un-economical given the small size of the system. Therefore, a local ad-hoc entity should be established in order to properly manage the whole project conception, construction, maintenance and development, and optimise the use of the skills and job qualifications required.

9.2.2 Required manpower and skills for DUGD projects

Consequently, a DUGD project will require the following skills:

- Geosciences and geo-technology knowledge, concerning the geothermal resource locally, implying:
 - **Geology:** in particular structural geology and hydrogeology, and -depending upon the site – other specialities such as volcanology, mineralogy or stratigraphy
 - **Geochemistry:** in particular for liquids and gas, both to understand the origin of the fluid and the geothermometry (temperature at depth), but also the conditions of exploitation (in order to prevent or master corrosion and scaling)
 - **Geophysics:** in particular electrical methods – like MT-TM, eventually associated with gravimetry and micro-seismicity, allowing to properly map the vertical dimension of the geothermal system
 - Integrated geoscientific knowledge: Conceptual 3D modelling of the geothermal system allowing to locate the exploration-production wells
 - Drilling, production tests and reservoir engineering, environmental scientist, allowing to plan the long-term production system and its development/extension.
- **Social sciences** including anthropology, sociology, including gender approaches, as well as political, economic and development sciences, particularly when IPs are concerned, which is the case for local populations like pastoralists or some fishing communities along the rift axis lowlands.
- **Technology studies**, in order to adapt existing

technologies developed elsewhere in the world with success to the local conditions in Africa, as well as departing from present uses and traditional know-how developed locally for the utilisation of the thermal manifestations (including fluids, clays and other components).

- Implementing an efficient electrical mini-grid and an optimised cascade use for the energy and for the water generated by the production system is a major engineering challenge.
- It is a key objective to develop both local engineering capabilities and local production of the components of the DU systems. This, in order to lower their costs, ensure the best appropriation and favor local innovation.
- Development of technical and business skills of DU will lead to empowerment of local women and youth through creation of jobs , generate incomes and spur economic growth of the communities . This is expected to motivate return to native lands, of young, educated local citizens who have moved to towns looking for jobs corresponding to their capabilities and which have not yet been made available on their ancestral land.

In addition to these specific capabilities, there is of course also a need for more general know-how, like project management, general engineering, sales management, accounting, financing and business development, ensuring legal issues, fair employment, etc.

In any case, there will be need to develop professional training that will serve the capacity-development needs of the local public entity or the specialised private sector operator depending on the case at hand.

Such trainings should initially be run at regional level – for instance under the AGCE being hosted in Kenya – but in case of success of a DUGD development policy in Africa, they should also be customised at national levels, particularly in Ethiopia and Kenya where the multiplicity of such sites would justify offering this kind of technical training nearer to the respective authorities and stakeholders.

9.2.3 Developing the African Engineering domain for DUGD projects

Given the very few existing references for DUGD in Africa at present, there will be a need, in a transition period, to call for partnership and expertise from foreign consulting and the engineering domain. However, given the perspective of the local market, and differing from large-sized plants for electricity production, there is a real space for African professionals to quickly master this technical aspect.

To this respect, the regional associations (eg. AGA and AW AG) and national ones (eg. GAK and EGA), backed by the AGCE based in Kenya should help to develop appropriate training programs addressed to young scientists, engineers, economists and administrators from the region who would in turn create firms specialised in DUGD.

It would also be the role of African Universities eg. in Ethiopia, Kenya, Tanzania, Rwanda and other countries in the region to implement and develop all related scientific disciplines (in geosciences, social sciences and engineering) as well as interdisciplinary approaches including economy, political science and management teaching. These pedagogic engagements should in fact be associated to research and innovation, as usual in an academic environment, as DU is a domain in which there is a real need for adjusting the offer to the specificity of the local situation, which varies from site to site given the diversity of geological and anthropological situations encountered in the field.

9.2.4 General information and education (media, schools, politicians) programs

The first and major condition for a suitable development of DUGD is to create awareness and develop some general information for the target populations for them to know and understand the reality of the geothermal resources lying below their settlements and the way tapping these resources should help in improving their living conditions. This is not even a one-sided approach, as local knowledge is essential, and in fact both parties will contribute to the information sharing.

This means teaching the basic concepts of geology, showing how the volcanic and tectonic conditions on site allow for convective geothermal systems to develop, with, as a result, thermal springs or steam vents to be visible at the surface. Starting with the knowledge the concerned people will have accumulated on these resources, the characteristics of the geothermal manifestations that they eventually use their limited tools to engineer so as to serve some of their needs, and showing them how simple additional techniques – such as shallow drilling or heat exchangers – could help improve the energy and water harvesting as well as develop and diversify the usage of this local resource for their benefit.

Educational programmes should be engaged both for the children at schools, and at the successive higher levels (that is: primary and secondary schools, colleges, technical college and universities) and for the general population through appropriate media (eventually even orally depending on how information is best transmitted in a given local population). Meaning geothermal programmes should be included in

the training of the teachers. This was done by Dr. Jacques Varet, the main author of this guidebook for an academic year at DeKUT¹ in Kenya for technical university teachers.

Administrators and politicians – particularly in the areas where geothermal resource is widespread – should also be offered training programmes, for which this guidebook could be of help.

9.3 Examples of financed projects: Research and Development

Considering the present low level of development of the DUGD sector in Africa, and the specificity of the resource, of the demand as well as of the development perspective, there is a need for specific research to be engaged at the R&D, RD&D and pilot levels. This means stimulating public research organisations and universities with ad-hoc programmes, to be studied and implemented in relevant places on a diversity of sites concerning both the geothermal resource characteristics and the socio-economic considerations to be taken into account. One of the characteristics of Africa is the lack of public R&D policies in the RE sector and more specifically in the geothermal energy sector, DUGD in particular. Therefore, there is a limitation of partnerships between universities and ongoing geothermal development.

9.3.1 The EU-AU renewable energy R&D initiative

In a partnership between AU and the EU, a significant research programme was launched in 2020, for a sufficient period of time to cover the successive stages of R&D aimed at identifying appropriate forms of RE development for duplication in the continent. LEAP-RE² is part of EJP aiming to set the foundation for future collaborative AU-EU activities in the field of RE. This project forms the basis for long-term African-European collaboration in RE with the objective to enlarge and strengthen the interactions of relevant stakeholders and engage a joint strategic RD&D programme and framework recognised and supported by the EC and national actors with appropriate funding while addressing the needs of the public and respective end-users (in particular RTOs³ and SMEs⁴ in EU & Africa).

After a first call for expressions of interest, 7 project proposals concerned with geothermal energy were submitted. In order to have a chance to succeed, they were merged into 2 projects respectively called Geothermal Village 1 (GV1) and Geothermal Atlas for Africa GAA. Both projects were accepted and started operating in mid-2021 for a 3-year period. Additional funding will be made available through successive calls during this period and successive years.

¹Dedan Kimathi University of Technology

²Long-Term Joint EU-AU Research and Innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy

³Research and Technology Organisations

⁴Small and Medium Enterprises

Table 9.2: Time-frame of the GV1 R&D project with its 7 work packages (WP) and deliverables (D)

		YEAR 1												YEAR 2												YEAR 3											
		Q1			Q2			Q3			Q4			Q1			Q2			Q3			Q4														
M1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36		
WP-1 Geology, Geochemistry, Geophysics & Modelling		D1																																			
1.1 Site Selection		D1A																																			
1.2 Topo, geology																																					
1.3 Geochemistry																																					
1.4 Geophysics																																					
1.5 Modelling																																					
3.1 Concepts																																					
3.2 ORC Plants		D3A																																			
3.3 Grid Designs																																					
3.4 Cook cool process																																					
3.5 Fish farming		D3B																																			
3.6 Spa/Eco-tourism																																					
WP-2 Social and Economic Studies		D2																																			
2.1 Contextual Analysis																																					
2.2 Social dynamics investigation		D2A																																			
2.3 Stakeholder analysis and engagement																																					
2.4 Best practices and Case studies		D2B																																			
WP-3 Conceptual Design & Engineering																																					
4.1 Framework		D3																																			
4.2 Rwanda																																					
4.3 Djibouti/Ethiopia																																					
4.4 Kenya																																					
4.5 Legal Framework																																					
WP-4 Site Feasibility Studies		D4																																			
7.1 Demo 1 planning		D7																																			
7.2 Demo 2 & 3 planning																																					
7.3 Planning capacity building																																					
7.4 Planning replication																																					
WP-5 Resource Mobility and Capacity		D5																																			
WP-6 Project Management		D6																																			
C1		C2																																			
		C3																																			
		C4																																			

9.3.2 The Geothermal Village project

The original concept was described in a publication by Varet et al in 2004 (Fig. 9.1), and several attempts to promote it did not fully succeed, despite the identification of numerous sites where the local resource would really fit with respective populations' socio-economic needs. A team of scientific partners from Africa and the EU have joined their efforts in the first phase of this initiative (GV1) to fill the knowledge and technology gaps that need to be solved in order to succeed in a socially mastered efficient development of local DUGD (see Varet et al. 2020).

After field studies have been engaged, sites with different thermal and socio-economic characteristics will be selected, developing for each a suitable energy plan. The aim is to conceive a technology level appropriate to the local operation, maintenance and even replication, which furthers the long-term objective of capacity building, economic and social welfare, encouraging young educated people to stay on their homeland. These systems can supply fresh water and supplant oil and firewood which, in addition to environmental and health benefits, reduces the domestic expense and workload on women and girls allowing time for education and enhanced productivity in other activities.

This project perfectly illustrates the sustainable development triangle (Fig. 9.2) and directly addresses by and large, most of the goals of Agenda SDG 2030 and AU Agenda 2063. o. These include (among others) : access to water, clean energy, climate-resilience, developing capacities at individual and institutional levels to engage modular developments and to adapt to further changes, through smart-grid, off-grid, stand-alone systems and processes as well as appliances for productive uses.

The Geothermal Village concept which informs the GV1 project, is illustrated in Fig. 9.1. In this concept, geothermal fluid obtained from moderate-depth boreholes is used first for electricity then in a cascade of increasingly lower temperature for DUGD such as drying of crops/fish/meat, cooking, baking, fish-farms, greenhouses, pasteurising (dairy), pottery, brick kilns, wood timber drying, bathing, washing, supplying drinking water, providing cooling and freezing facilities, eco-tourism based on hot-springs and resorts run by the local population. First investigations (Mariita et al, 2016) show that hundreds of sites along the EARS have geothermal resources appropriate for such developments, each installation allowing modular expansion according to needs. Through LEAP-RE project, European and African entities jointly research and develop the conceptual, engineering and physical tools to support community-based initiatives and develop local capabilities, working through schools, universities, public and private entities, co-operatives CBOs and NGOs. The ambition is to create in Africa the capacities to master the whole chain of basic knowledge, technology management, social organisations and economic capabilities to ensure the maintenance, extension and replication of community-based geothermal projects. Some partners involved in the preparation of this guidebook conceptualised and designed both the Geothermal Village concept and the GeoPower Africa Project (2013-2017) covering Ethiopia, Kenya and Tanzania⁵, under USAID⁶ support, then were engaged in the IRENA⁷ survey on the same subject, and have further been part of the creation and formulation of local civil society organisations and/or associations (HHGCBO and AGAP), mobilisation of SMEs and public research partners, as well as development of partnerships with specialised public institutions (for example ODDEG⁸, EDCL⁹) all of whom are now part of this project (GV1).

Fig. 9.1: Scheme of the Geothermal Village concept with production of geothermal fluids from shallow depths intersecting feeding geological structures of the surface manifestations, and cascade use with electricity and cascade direct uses. (Varet et al., 2014).

The first step in the GV1 project is selecting the most relevant sites. The second step is site feasibility and design. The third step, for which additional support is looked for, will be the construction of demonstrator systems in which 3 suitable Geothermal Village sites along the EARS will be selected. The initiative projects to have model plans for high enthalpy sites in the Eastern Rift and Afar, and medium enthalpy site in the Western and Southern Rifts, representing also the variation in societal context, where the requirements of pastoral indigenous, fishing or agricultural communities each imply a different use of the electricity and thermal water.

The Work Plan (Table 9.2) is based on a 3-year detailed programme, with well-defined tasks and sub-tasks assigned to each partner, always based on Afro-European partnerships. The results of the R&D engaged in the first year will provide the necessary data for engaging the detailed feasibility studies on the sites selected for their relevance to the diversity of the geological and social situations encountered. A joint feasibility frame will be defined and applied in

selected sites in each of the 4 countries (Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda and Djibouti), also involving specialised technical partners depending on the DU options considered. This will be followed by the definition of a proper legal framework (community-based enterprise, co-operative, SEM, PPP, etc), financial arrangement (stakeholders' own funds, grants, soft loans, etc) allowing for the project's implementation, including the process of payment by consumers so as to ensure the sustainable management of the whole device.

9.3.3 The Geothermal Atlas for Africa

After several initiatives to develop a geothermal atlas and data bank on geothermal resources in Africa under UNEP, with the (based in Nairobi, Kenya), and also under AfDB, with the

ICA (based in Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire) in partnership with the EPI, USA., the Geothermal Atlas for Africa (GAA) was launched under the same EU LEAP-RE R&D programme as GV1.

Table 9.3: Definition of existing R&D policy mechanisms for RE deployment
Source: IPCC (2012)

Policy	Definition
Public R&D policies Fiscal Incentives	
Academic R&D funding	Investment monies provided to academics for undertaking creative work to increase stock of knowledge in particular field and use it to devise new applications.
Grant	Funding for RD&D with no repayment requirements. Challenge grants are provided alongside industry commitments, often targeting product innovation or early manufacturing facilities. Contingent grants are loans that do not require repayment unless and until technologies and intellectual property have been successfully utilised.
Incubation support	Assistance to entrepreneurs including business development and raising financing.
National/ International Public Research Centre	Research facility funded by local, national or international government bodies or publicly funded organization
PP P	Arrangement typified by collaboration between the public and private sectors. Can cover delivery of policies, service, technologies and infrastructure.
Prize	Awarded to winning competitors to help finance cost of private R&D, generally used in innovation.
Tax credit	Allows investments in RE R&D to be fully or partially deducted from tax obligations or income.
Voucher scheme	Provides companies access to R&D centres for the purpose of doing research.
Public finance:	
Venture capital	Financing aimed at turning promising research into new products and services, invested independently or with matching private investors.
Soft/convertible loan	Financing instrument available at pre-commercial stage to promote and commercialise RE technologies; often loans are repayable only once technology reaches commercialisation.

⁵<https://www.usaid.gov/sites/default/files/documents/15396/3-233%20GeoPower%20Africa.pdf>;
https://sites.nationalacademies.org/PGA/PEER/PEERscience/PGA_152032

⁶United States Agency for International Development

⁷International Renewable Energy Agency

⁸Office Djiboutien de developpement de l'energie geothermique in Djibouti

⁹Energy Development Corporation Limited in Rwanda

GAA aims to define the origin and location of low to high enthalpy geothermal resources for the development of electricity production, a range of direct heat/cold use applications and water use all over the African continent. This will be achieved by identifying, organising, assessing, classifying and interpreting: (1) geoscientific information (eg. geology, geochemistry, geophysics), (2) technological information (eg. existing power plants, installed capacity), and (3) social aspects with a multi-scale approach (local, regional, continental). Results will be made available by the project through an atlas which will be available both online and in printed form, to enable easy access to relevant information on geothermal resources for scientists, project developers, investors as well as policy and decision-makers.

Geosciences will identify and gather information that allows sub-surface characterisation of the low to high enthalpy geothermal systems in Africa. All relevant existing geological data that will help in characterising the sub-surface and geothermal energy systems will be gathered from existing sources.

Engineering Sciences will enable the comparison of resource availability and the local populations' needs by concentrating on the surface installation and potential usage of the geothermal energy systems.

Social Sciences: The development of geothermal system has to benefit the local population and promote virtuous sustainable development. Socio-economic and best practices analysis will be developed and integrated with the GAA, with the aim of facilitating information availability that will aid geothermal project development and implementation. This information will also be useful from an investor's or project developer's perspective, when considering the most suitable socio-economic contexts for new geothermal investment.

Implementation of the Atlas will make use of all information available from the preceding Tasks to deliver the GAA. Outputs will include identification of the geoscientific knowledge required to successfully identify and develop geothermal systems, factors that enabled the construction of existing installations in place (both for high and low enthalpy), considerations about infrastructural constraints and the social aspects of geothermal development. The project will provide a homogenised overview of the data collected to offer a clear picture of geothermal energy availability on the African continent.

Both GV1 and GAA projects will evolve over 3 years (2021-2023) of their implementation, and will be subject to complementary R&D, answering future calls. This will allow

to enlarge and diversify, whenever necessary, the already rather large circle of African partners involved, drawn from universities, public enterprises and SMEs.

9.4. The need for specific R&D and innovation effort in African public policies

One hopes that the EU-AU initiative, which is planned to be implemented in the long run, will contribute to the consolidation of public policies in the concerned countries in the RE sector in general, in the geothermal energy sector in particular, including DUs answering the specific needs of African communities, especially the off-grid villages and populations.

The IPCC established a list of public R&D sources, to facilitate the support for RE deployment of demonstrations on site, under the form of fiscal incentives and public finance (Table 9.3).

Fiscal incentives include academic R&D funding, grants for demonstrations on sites, incubators support, creation of public research centres, and centres of excellence in particular, PPPs, prizes, tax credit or voucher schemes. Public finances should support venture capital and soft or convertible loans.

Fig. 9.2 describes the various types of technology content and technology transfer between countries in the field of RE as summarised by IPCC (2012): goods, service and design; skills and know-how for operation and maintenance; or knowledge and expertise behind technology. Such concepts could help in backing DUGD if applied in Africa.

More explicitly, Fig. 9.3, also from IPCC (2012) illustrates the efficiency of the linkage between technology development, industry development and market development. The mechanisms that facilitate the inter-play between technology cycle and market cycle allow to reduce the costs of RE production. Owing to this mechanism, solar and wind energy are becoming more and more economical due to the fast increase of their respective markets, a situation not yet reached for DUGD in Africa.

This guidebook aims to contribute to the improvement of this situation by addressing this challenge through the various pertinent information it provides on DUGD.

Fig. 9.2: Different types of technology content in technology transfer between countries (IPCC 2012)

Fig. 9.3: the mutually reinforcing cycles of technology development and market deployment driving down technology costs (IPCC 2012)

CHAPTER 10:

SUPPORTIVE FINANCE

FOR DIRECT USE PROJECTS

10.1 DUGD: A site-specific economy

In a classical HT project, geothermal wells drilled at an average depth of 2,500m, will deliver fluid at 250°C, allowing for the production of electricity by discharge in a turbine of steam under a pressure of 5 bars at least. As shown by the synthesis produced by ESMAP¹ (Table 10.1), the investment for drilling represents a third of the total cost of the production system, and an equal amount for the power plant. The global investment varies from USD 2.8M to USD 5.5 M per MWe installed, and the resulting production cost will range from 0.04 to 0.08 USD/kWh. Table 10.1 provides a breakdown of the costs for the successive phases of development of the projects. The high upfront costs are a common characteristic, until the feasibility stage is reached. As an average, the initial investments at risk reach 13 to 18 per cent.

In the case of DUGD, the variety of business models possible was presented in section 3.4, showing that the economy of these projects cannot be presented as simply as for HT projects where – despite variations from site to site and country to country – general figures can be presented, as the final product, electricity is a standard product of the total project costs.

Despite a lack of sound statistical data, and huge geographic variations (for instance the market for heating buildings that is present in the northern hemisphere whereby, 40 per cent of the total energy consumption of the country in France goes to heating of buildings, does not even exist in sub-Saharan Africa); we can provide some indicative figures in the case of shallow (or close to the surface) resource (see Table 10.2).

Upfront costs are considerably reduced due to lower

exploration expenses in geoscience and reconnaissance drilling. These lower - at risk - initial costs also require lesser feasibility and insurance in particular. Drilling costs for field development drilling will also be much less (about a quarter compared with deep drilling costs) due to reduced depth. The investments devoted to surface geothermal costs will vary according to the applications (like greenhouses, fishponds, milk-processing plants, abattoirs, food-drying devices for fruits, vegetable, grains, meat, fish, etc, washing machines, swimming pools, etc.) but can be essentially manufactured locally, whereas the strict geothermal part (fluid piping, pumping, heat exchangers, injection wells, etc.) will remain comparatively small. However, when electricity production is considered, the equipment (ORC plant) will represent an investment per MWe installed that will be higher than for back-pressure turbines; generally, by a factor of 1.5 to 2, depending on the size of the plant. But given the reduced drilling costs, the economy of the electricity production will remain quite favorable, especially if compared with the diesel-powered plant that the geothermal option will replace.

In these cases of isolated sites not connected to the national grid, the investments to be considered will also include the installation of a mini-grid and distribution pipes for water. A consideration would be to involve other relevant actors at national and/or local regional levels, as suggested in the Kenyan Energy Act (2019).

Despite the extensive possibility for development of DU applications in Africa, the financial resources appear not to be easy to mobilise at present. This is mainly due to the lack of existing references and success stories in the continent, and more basically the lack of knowledge concerning the geothermal resources and the possible applications outside the “mainstream” approach of the

Table 10.1: Indicative costs for geothermal development (generator capacity of 50 MWe). Figures are in USD Millions
Source: ESMAP (2012).

	PHASE/ACTIVITY	LOW ESTIMATE	MEDIUM ESTIMATE	HIGH ESTIMATE
1	Preliminary survey, permits, market analysis. ¹⁶	1	2	5
2	Exploration ¹⁷	2	3	4
3	Test drilling, reservoir evaluation, well testing. ¹⁸	11	18	30
4	Feasibility study, project planning, funding, contracts, insurances etc. ¹⁹	5	7	10
5	Drilling (20 boreholes). ²⁰	45	70	100
6	Construction (power plant, cooling, infrastructure, etc.). ²¹	65	75	95
7	Steam-gathering system and sub-station, connection to grid (transmission). ²²	10	16	22
8	Start-up and commissioning. ²³	3	5	8
	Total	142	196	274
	In USD Million per MW installed	2.8	3.9	5.5

¹Energy Sector Management Assistance Program (World Bank)

Table 10.2: Indicative costs for DUGD including heat and water production as well as electricity (with a 1MWth +100kWe capacity ORC generator in the low figure, and 10MWth+1MWe in the high figure)

Source: ESMAP (2012).

Phase/activity		Low 100kWe 1MWth	Medium 200kWe 5MWth	High 1MWe 10MWth
1	Preliminary survey, permit, social & market analysis	0.1	0.1	0.2
2	Social science and geoscience exploration	0.2	0.3	0.4
3	Test drilling, well testing, reservoir study	0.8	1.2	1.6
4	Feasibility study, planning, funding, insurance, etc.	0.3	0.4	0.5
5	Development drilling	0.0	0.5	1.0
6	Power plant and cascade use devices for DU	0.5	1.0	3.0
7	Mini-grid, heat & water distribution	0.2	0.5	1.0
Total		2.1	4.0	7.7
USD per MWt installed		1.5	1.0	0.7
USD per MWe installed		5.0	4.5	4.0
USD per total MW installed		2.0	1.3	0.7

large-sized plants for electricity production. Owing to these conditions, the first demonstration projects have been engaged or are being studied alongside electricity production plants and projects, as is currently the case in Kenya near most of the geothermal sites that are being developed or have already been established. In countries involved in geothermal development along the EARS, delivering fluids for direct uses, in the form of heat or water, is now part of most HT projects, with the agent in charge of community relations in the company collecting information related to the local demand and being able to offer such solutions.

However, as expressed in the previous chapters, the challenge in Africa for DUGD has also been to have initiatives that facilitate access to the geothermal resources on the land of local populations, such that these often historically marginalised populations can use the resources to produce, process or enhance the value of identified locally available goods for their socio-economic benefit; a situation which would contribute to a more balanced national development than is the case at the moment.

From this perspective, an objective of this guidebook is also to help inform concerned development agencies at local, regional, national and continental level of the potential opportunities offered by DUGD.

In 2019, GreenMax Capital Advisor was contracted by the UNIDO to provide specialised Technical Assistance services to the CTCN in order to identify potential geothermal DU applications in six East African countries – Djibouti, Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania and Uganda. In each country, the

Technical Assistance services aim to inform policy-makers to improve their understanding of opportunities for DU geothermal applications from technical, financial and market viability perspectives, as well as to identify potential sectors and technologies that are best suited to benefit from the utilisation of DU geothermal projects. In addition to supporting rural livelihoods and economic development, this project will also support each country's efforts to advance its climate commitments given the impact of geothermal development on energy sector decarbonisation. Then, in 2021 GreenMax was also contracted by IRENA to design and implement a training program to equip relevant policy-makers and other stakeholders with the necessary knowledge and tools to support the adoption and scale-up of geothermal heat utilisation in the agri-food value chains. This will include cascaded use of residual heat from geothermal power plants and stand-alone DU projects. The key outputs/deliverables of the project include: i) A report highlighting capacity-gaps and making recommendations for capacity building in developing countries; ii) Training material for the deployment of geothermal heat in the agri-food value chains; and iii) Two training/capacity building activities (delivered in English and Spanish) based on guidelines targeting policy-makers and other relevant stakeholders in two regions.

As a result, Excel Sheets were made available for various kind of geothermal applications including fish, fruits, vegetable, rice and pyrethrum-drying, tobacco-curing, tea-processing, chicken hatchery, milk-processing, greenhouses and spas. These allow to develop financial models for DUGD with inputs of figures like: Annual Sales, Annual Revenues, Annual Expenses, Cash Return, Taxes, Payback Year, DSCR etc.

10.2 Funding sources for Africa

10.2.1 International funding

The **GEF** has supported the ARGeo Development Facility programme, through UNEP, in the six Eastern Africa countries in the last several years. Further, it has supported Armenia, Columbia (Macizo Volcanico del Ruiz), Yemen (exploration), Santa Lucia, Indonesia and Philippines as well as Djibouti (Asal-Fialé project). The Facility may also support through grant demonstration projects for DUGD in Africa.

The **CTCN** is the operational arm of the UNFCCC Technology Mechanism, hosted by UNEP and UNIDO. It promotes accelerated transfer of environmentally sound technologies for low carbon and climate-resilient development at the request of developing countries. It provides technology solutions, capacity building and advice on policy, legal and regulatory frameworks tailored to the needs of individual countries by harnessing the expertise of a global network of technology companies and institutions. In September 2019 the CTCN advertised for consultancy services to carry out Technical Assistance for DU applications in Djibouti, Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, Uganda and Tanzania.

The **AfDB** has financed geothermal projects in Kenya (Menengai) and Djibouti (Asal-Fialé) and hosts the SEFA¹ a multi-donor special fund providing catalytic finance to unlock investments in RE and energy efficiency. Its overarching goal is to contribute to access of affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy services for all in Africa, in line with the New Deal on Energy for Africa and SDG 7. It has been spear-heading AfDB's engagement in green mini-grids, paving the way for the first two scale-up programmes in DRC and Burkina Faso. It played a catalytic role in the preparation and financial close of the **Africa Renewable Energy Fund** – one of the first pan-African equity funds for renewable energy – reaching a USD 200 million capitalisation in 2014, and subsequently in establishing the **Facility for Energy Inclusion** – a pan-African debt financing platform for small-scale renewables - which had mobilised USD 250 million by end of 2019. SEFA supports interventions across three strategic priorities: Green Baseload (GBL): increasing the penetration of renewable energy in power systems and delivering alternatives to fossil-fuel baseload generation options; Green Mini-Grids (GMG): accelerating

electricity access to underserved populations through clean energy mini-grid solutions and Energy Efficiency (EE): improving the efficiency of energy services delivered through a variety of technologies and business models, also including clean cooking and pico technologies. The Technical Assistance supports through grants activities that will directly unlock investments. These grants are available to public and private sector entities. Concessional Investment (CI) supports, through Results-Based Financing, loans and equity instruments often blended with AfDB's investments to close viability gaps.

EU-EDF: The EDF from the EU may finance geothermal project studies and development. This has been the case for Bugarama area in Southern Rwanda and nearby Burundi, as well as Gisenyi area along the Western side of Lake Kivu in central-western Rwanda in the years 2005-2007 (Rutagarama & Varet, 2018).

10.2.2 Bilateral and regional funding

Through Technical Assistance programmes, some development partners eg. UNEP-ARGeo- DFID, JICA, USAID and ICEIDA have supported efforts to develop geothermal DU in the region. They can support DUGD by offering Technical Assistance, capacity building, and financial support. The Technical Assistance could also be utilised to help in the identification of high-value applications. The Menengai DU demonstration project has been implemented in the region due to collaboration between GDC and USAID. Through the cooperation, USAID provided Technical Assistance for design and implementation of the project, pre-feasibility studies for some selected DU applications as well as on the job training/mentoring. ICEIDA, on the other hand, financed the procurement of a grain dryer to be installed in the Menengai demonstration site. JICA has supported GDC with capacity building on DU.

USAID also supported a research project on DU perspectives in Kenya, Ethiopia and Tanzania (Mariita et al., 2016) and is considering support for the development of geothermal industrial parks in the region.

The EAGER fund handled by the NSF (USA) supported Uganda to develop pre-feasibility studies for selected DU applications.

¹<https://www.afdb.org/en/topics-and-sectors/initiatives-partnerships/sustainable-energy-fund-for-africa>

A gyser in Lake Bogoria.
Photo credit: Franco Pecchio/flickr

CHAPTER 11:

SPECIFIC ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL DIMENSIONS

11.1 How DUGD differs from classical geothermal projects

One important characteristic of the DUGD, as described in this approach for Africa relates to its specific environmental and social dimension. As a consequence, the way the project will have to be handled with respect to the environmental and social procedures run by the national administrations and the international or bilateral development agencies should differ from large-sized projects, justifying a specific approach and even stronger financial support

For the DUGD of the kind we have described in this guidebook that is basically handled by the local population, it should as such be regarded as a model of environmentally and socially friendly programme. It can be shown, as outlined in the next chapter, (and as already alluded to earlier in this guidebook) that such a programme answers the criteria of sustainability as defined by 12 out of the 17 SDGs.

In classical industrial projects, as is the case for large-sized electricity production, there is a need for an environmental and social impact study, because each project is first conceived by the investor, who is alien to the target ecosystem (natural and human) in which the project is going to be implemented (Onyango, 2020). Therefore, an ESIA is a must in order to take into account, a-posteriori, the way the project which come from outside will affect both the environment and the population living on and around the sites. In particular, compensation measures will be proposed, eventually including RAP (ibid). In the case of DUGD the project is typically endogenous, and is handled by the local population, living in their natural environment and owing to the projects' small size, no adverse environmental impact is really expected. There is therefore no need for an ESIA, as the project - by its design - answers the needs of the local population and is expected to be beneficial to them (ibid). As it is a community-driven demand, it is anticipated that everything else remaining constant, if it would not be beneficial to them, they would not think of having it, meaning they would not come up with it in the first place and so, it would simply not take place (ibid). Similarly, concerning the physical environment, the project will allow to use a natural geothermal resource that will be simply improved (in terms of temperature and flow rate) with respect to existing emergence. The project will therefore improve the natural environment at the same time that it improves the social conditions of the local population, for instance improving the pasture area with the water produced, (which in addition allows for better conditions of life for the domestic animals); reducing the need to cut trees for wood fuel (where that is used to provide energy), consequently reducing deforestation and thus conserving the environment, etc. .

11.2 Project implementation

Once the target local population has been properly informed, convinced of the benefit of the initiative, and decided to embark on a DUGD, two options are left open for the management of the project implementation, development and maintenance:

- Either it is run by the community itself, as a public

property of common interest, directly managed by the community's representatives with the involvement of professional persons that could preferentially come from the community itself, or be engaged from outside if the required expertise is not available within the community.

- Or the project management and running is delegated to a specialised operator chosen by the community. Of course, such operators do not exist yet on the regional market in Africa. Therefore, in both cases, there would be a period of apprenticeship that would be necessary before properly trained personnel are available within the local community. The advantage of this second option would be to progressively develop a man-power capacity that would gain experience from several projects and mutualise the know-how and expertise.

11.2.1 Considerations for the Gender Aspect

The entire process should be made as participative as possible from the very initial stage with attention paid to inclusivity across gender and age throughout the exercise. To promote as much as possible inclusivity, gender intersectionality should inform the engagement procedures and the decisions related to involvement of the community members in the various processes all the way from project conception stage to project implementation and project management (Onyango, 2020). Attention should be paid to relevant context-specific socio-demographic identities and categories whose intersection would have an impact on the levels of individuals' pre-disposition to participate in decisions and processes related to community-based geothermal initiatives, or so to speak, DUGD projects on their land. In the context of the EARV, age, gender, education, social ties and status are some of the issues that would be pertinent to consider in this regard at local community level. Therefore, to ensure as much inclusivity as practical, for studies targeting rural areas (as is expected would most likely be the case with most of the initiatives for DUGD in Africa), a balance in representation across socio-economic status, respective administrative area/village of residence, varied functional literacy levels, social networks (including kinship ties), and other social dynamics issues should be underscored. For initiatives targeting urbanised regions, emphasis should be laid on the same issues, except that the weight on kinship ties should ideally be replaced by attention to representation across the ethnic groups and cultures represented on the site.

Engagement methods that promote optimum participation of all segments of the local population in discussions should be employed. Consequently, depending on the culture of a given population and taking into consideration other factors such as the social dynamics within the population, community meetings may be organised such that there is a mix of community members with varying socio-demographic identities and categories (such as gender, age, education level, social ties, status, etc) in any one meeting. Equally, as a way to further promote, as much as possible, meaningful participation of all the community members in engagement processes, meetings may be organised around the local community members' age-grouping, gender, socio-economic status, profession, economic engagements/activities, geographic location, clan relations (in the case of rural set-ups) and so on.

Ultimately, therefore, the gender component should take into consideration both the aspects of gender roles that could be aligned to DUGD initiatives and gender relations that ideally would be expected to have an influence on the participation of respective member of a given local population in processes related to geothermal development on the land they inhabit (Onyango, 2020).

11.3 Holistic environment

A characteristic of DUGD that should be underlined and understood by policy-makers and all stakeholders is its particular nature, as it implies all levels of the terrestrial ecosystem (Fig. 11.6): geosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere, climate and human culture (social, technical and economic). All these should be understood as a sustainable system entirely and harmoniously integrated in the earth ecosystem.

No other energy production, among renewable sources, rely so fully upon the natural interactions of the different envelopes characterising the planet earth system.

The fossil fuels, coal, oil, natural gas and even uranium are extracted from the geosphere, used in the biosphere by humanity, impacting the climate and depleting these finite resource base in the solid earth. However, this is a typically non-renewable option, for two reasons: the finite nature of the resource and the impact of its use on the earth's climate.

Among the renewables, solar, wind, hydro and biomass resources only imply hydrosphere, biosphere and climate. The geosphere is not contributing and these systems are not stable, as they are victims of the fluctuation and instability of the mobile envelopes of the planet earth.

To this respect, we should remember that the "solid earth" is not a "dead body" on which the other envelopes simply overlay as if it were a neutral surface. In fact, the interior of the earth is also active, and plays a role in the whole earth system, including its most superficial envelopes, with which it constantly interacts (as shown in Fig. 11.1).

Taking the position of using the sustainable resource of solid earth characteristics as an advantage for human being is the best way to accommodate human culture, with its social, technical and economic dimensions. Geothermal energy as a whole, and DUGD in particular, allows this to happen.

11.4 Sustainability and resilience

One of the most important characteristics of geothermal energy in general, and especially DUGD, which should always be underlined is its sustainability. When RE are listed, among policy-makers and in the general public acceptance, solar and wind are normally immediately featured on the list first, followed by hydro and biomass. Geothermal energy is very rarely considered, or even mentioned.

In the cases where geothermal energy is considered, it is frequently to underline the high investments, the high upfront risks, and the large size of the units requiring highly specialised personnel and technologies. Rarely is it to underline the 3 essential factors below:

- The sustainability of the production – and consumption – device
- The fact that any geothermal unit operates best if used constantly, 7 days a week and 24 hours a day.
- The important point that the components of geothermal systems can be fully mastered locally – geology, geophysics, drilling, fluid production, management, distribution, etc – the imported parts being limited.

In addition, never mentioned in RE comparisons is the fact that geothermal systems have the particularity – not shared by other renewables – to allow for the production of a diversified form of energy, from electricity production to heat, cold and even water (and eventually other derived products).

One should also note that geothermal systems being implemented in geologically active regions – volcanically

Fig. 11.1: The place of DUGD projects in the terrestrial envelopes; geosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere and the cultural sphere (social, technical and economic) (J.Varet, Pour une terre durable BRGM, 2000, modified).

and seismically active – allow to contribute – as a social by-product – to the mitigation of these telluric risks. All the geological, geochemical and geophysical approaches to geothermal resources identification, and further management, contribute to a better knowledge of these systems and their related risks. In the long run, the generalisation of geothermal exploitations in these telluric active areas of the planet earth may just finally help to mitigate the risks by a slight puncture of a part of the earth’s energy that is in excess in these active regions of the earth.

An additional consideration concerns the question of climatic resilience. The regions in Africa where geothermal resources are most abundant are the depleted parts of the EARV where the climate is particularly arid, and adversely affected by climate change with longer period of droughts (with eventually no rainfall for successive years) and increased frequent extreme flooding. In such conditions, geothermal simultaneously offers solutions to:

- Mitigation of GHG emissions avoiding the use of fossil fuels.
- Adaptation to climate change in providing better living conditions.
- A resilience to climate change as geothermal provides energy and water independent of the climatic conditions.

DUGD should therefore be considered at the highest position in regards to the solutions that are supported – in sub-Saharan Africa countries in particular (Fig. 11.2) – by the international climate policies, according to which the Southern countries which are not responsible for the climate change should be compensated as victims of the effects for which countries of the North are mainly responsible, at present (Fig. 11.3) and even more if cumulative emissions are considered (Fig. 11.4).

11.5 Inclusion in National Strategic Policies, especially Climate Policies

All reasons and arguments developed above underline the need to include geothermal energy and DUGD in the global and continental development policies: Agenda SDG 2030, AU Agenda 2063 including Paris agreement on Climate action 2015. Further, geothermal energy resource should be considered in the national strategic policies of the concerned countries in Africa. It is one of the aims of this guidebook to contribute to the implementation of such policies in the region.

Referring to Ogola et al. (2011) considering geothermal energy policies (Fig. 11.5), when applied to the case studied in this report, we observe that:

Fig. 11.2: Multi-sector risk in the world – particularly high in sub-Saharan Africa - due to climate change in the +1.5°C IPCC Report 2018.

Fig. 11.3: GHG emissions by country. Note the very limited impact of African countries, particularly the sub-Saharan ones, compared with countries in the Northern hemisphere.

Fig. 11.4: Cumulative CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels and cement by world region from the year 1751 onward. Note the limited part taken by Africa (in blue)

Fig. 11.5: Conceptual framework showing the assessment, implementation and benefits of mitigation-adaptation synergy for geothermal systems (Ogola et al., 2011)

- Whereas DUGD presents a viable option for mitigation and adaptation co-benefits, and being a one-stop shop in most projects, the benefits are not homogenous across all countries and regions in Africa. They are essentially site-specific. As observed above, solutions widely vary depending upon the type of system implemented, itself determined by the geological characteristics of the geothermal resource and the nature of the local population's needs.
- DUGD will directly rely upon the adaptive capacity of the concerned population and the said population's preparedness – through information and education – for social change as well as the legal, institutional and financial policies human resource and -related structures in place at local, regional and national levels.
- The co-benefits created by DUGD for adaptation, mitigation and resilience have the potential of creating direct economic, environmental and social benefits, with the most comprehensive impact on the SDGs compared to any other RE solution (Fig. 11.6) especially when developed with an efficient cascade use device (Fig. 11.7).
- There is an intimate relationship between geothermal and fresh water production. This is a huge advantage for local populations involved in DUGD in water-stressed regions as is found in the EARS (Fig. 11.8). Development of geothermal technologies with cascade use of energy and water allow for short circuit systems that are the most economical for management of both resources.
- Despite the regional and climatic variations, the conceptual framework of DUGD cuts across most regions and types of utilisation schemes. There are a variety of solutions but the approaches and basic principles are the same. We insist in this guidebook on the local solutions using shallow geothermal resources, but we should also remember that many benefits can also arise from the use of the fluids resulting from emissions of a power plant (Fig. 11.9).
- Without proper information, education and training programs, legislation, fiscal incentives, subsidies, guarantees, and tax exemptions to attract investment in DUGD, it will not be possible to really develop this option in Africa despite its attractiveness, at least at the current stage at which demonstration projects are not really available in the continent.

Fig. 11.6: Geothermal energy mitigation/adaptation co-benefits (from Ogola, 2011)

Fig. 11.7: Cascade use of geothermal energy with applications at 3 levels : 1st electricity production through ORC plant at the first level, 2nd production of cold for cooling and eventually freezing at second level, and 3rd other DUs at the third level, including heat application and the use of the fluid itself (pisci-culture, balneotherapy, spas, eco-tourism, etc), and finally, reinjection.

Fig. 11.8: Potential for cascade use of geothermal energy and water in processes relevant in the Central Kenyan Rift Valley and impact on adaptation (Ogola et al., 2012)

Fig. 11.9: General scheme of cascade use of energy for DUGD for a fluid emanating from a geothermal power plant, adapted from Lund by Geoheat centre, Oregon, and Arason (2010).

11.6 DUGD answering Sustainable Development Goals

The UN agreed on 17 development goals to be achieved by 2030, aiming for a sustainable future for all. They address the global challenges, in order to leave no one behind. Handled at community level in Africa DUGD answers most of these goals (12 of them), in the order presented below in Table 11.1.

Table 11.1: Specific economic, environmental and social benefits of DUGD responding to the SDGs as defined by UN.

DUGD No.	SDG No.	Goal	DUGD need answered
1	7	Affordable and clean energy	All energy needs, from direct thermal uses to electricity, including cooling and heating.
2	6	Clean water and sanitation	Water produced directly or from steam condensation. Also powering for ground-water pumping or desalinisation.
3	1	No poverty	The poorest people in concerned countries are living in areas where DUGD is possible.
4	2	No hunger	Famines due to dryness/drought affect communities which could benefit from DUGD solutions.
5	11	Sustainable cities and communities	DUGD offers sustainable energy/water solutions for local cities and communities.
6	13	Climate actions	Communities on low-lands are the most affected by climate change effects, whereas DUGD offers climate-resilient solutions.
7	5	Gender equality	Energy and water provision at household level is the responsibility of women and girls in these communities. Therefore, they are the first beneficiaries of DUGD.
8	3	Good health and well-being	The production of thermal water, allows for bathing and cloth-cleaning as well as health-care and well-being applications.
9	4	Quality education	These developments are possible based on people's education and involvement in the resources knowledge and technology transfer.
10	9	Industry, innovation, infrastructure	Processes implied are innovative, local grid development and the production allows for creative industrial development.
11	8	Decent work and economic growth	The devices are run locally, implying engaging local workers thus local economic growth.
12	10	Reducing inequalities	These are marginalised populations; DUGD reduces social, economic as well as gender-based inequalities.

Top: At Aluto, where volcanic steam rises from cracks in the ground, locals harvest volcanic steam using a network of steel pipes. Steam is trapped and condensed to liquid water safe for drinking.
Photo credit: Friedemann Samrock, ETH Zurich/flickr

Bottom: Local residents in Eburru, Kenya harvesting geothermal steam (Condensate)
Photo credit: Bett/flickr

CHAPTER 12:

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, utilisation of geothermal energy, DUGD in particular, has been done in many developed and developing countries, and can be used in adapting and mitigating the impacts of climate change in both temperate and tropical climates, depending on how it is applied. Unlike most developed countries where DU of geothermal energy has been developed for the benefit of the people, no significant efforts have yet been made in Africa.

Given the exceptionally favorable geological conditions prevailing along the EARS, and in other parts of the continent, and taking into account the inclination for easier appropriation of DUGD by local populations (compared to the classical HT geothermal systems built for electricity production), using shallow, low-to-medium temperature geothermal resources is an option that should really be considered in Africa.

The fact that such development has not yet taken place results from the situation that sites where the conditions are the most favorable – with steam vents available at the surface – are located in remote, eventually arid or even desertic areas, largely able to currently only support economic lifestyles, and by extension; activities revolving mainly around pastoralism, (therefore characterised by adverse conditions not attractive to investors!). This situation has until now, not favored other applications than the simplest options like bathing and cooking or artisanal steam condensing devices, for liquid water production and consumption, handled with simple tools by the local populations.

However, climate change and more severe environmental conditions necessitate an evolution of the way of life of the populations in question, implying adaptation and mitigation to climate change and search for resilience options. Geothermal offers such options as it provides a form of energy which is low carbon, resource-efficient and climate-resilient and which allows a constant production all year-round regardless of surface conditions.

Hence, geothermal opens up a real opportunity for the concerned African populations. The challenge and barrier that remains to be addressed include putting in place clear and coherent as well as harmonised policies at local, regional, national and international levels, as well as means for their implementation.

It is worth noting that since the initial geothermal exploration works were engaged in the EARS (CNR-CNRS, 1967-1976; UNDP, 1970-1972) it has taken several decades, before the development of proper project implementation tools by the relevant entities: (the GEF-funded UNEP ARGeo, ICEIDA, GRMF with AU, AfDB and WB; bilateral agencies; national

entities such as KenGen and GDC in Kenya; recently emulated by other countries like Tanzania with TGDC or Djibouti with ODDEG respectively) and even for the classical HT geothermal developments to now be under consideration for development.

It is now also high time that the kind of shallow geothermal resources discussed in this guidebook are finally made accessible for development in the interest of the concerned local populations - the ones eventually the most exposed and vulnerable to the effects and impact of climate change - hence the ones who should be considered as priority targets by relevant multilateral and bilateral entities working in the domain of geothermal development.

The use of geothermal energy will improve food and water security, reduce drought-related losses, provide alternative sources of income streams through creation of jobs, generate incomes and spur economic growth . DU of geothermal energy in climate change adaptation and mitigation is more efficient if used in a cascade of activities through different temperatures shown in the various cascade schemes. The thermal energy required for processing raw materials within a radius of 50 km of the study area is estimated to be 100 MWth and could be less in a cascade system.

The required energy can be distributed across the target area using two or more wells with a capacity ranging from 150 kWth to 15 MWth per unit depending on the demand and the type of use. We have shown that equipment for drilling normal water wells can also be used in drilling low-to-medium temperature geothermal resources with minor adaptation and professional training to fast-track local utilisation and maximise on the use of local manpower.

The energy can also be sourced from the power plants' waste heat. Some of the processing methods can also be complemented with the use of solar, wind or biogas energy where necessary.

At present, as shown by the IPCC Special Report on Renewable Energy (Fig. 12.1), geothermal power appears among the most competitive options for electricity production, only challenged by hydropower and bioenergy (small-scale CHP and gasification) a situation which is shown to persist into the future (horizon 2030 and 2050).

Even more competitive are identified geothermal DUs, in this case, greenhouse and aquaculture (Fig. 12.2), only challenged by biomass and solar thermal. It can be seen from the figure that geothermal will become even more competitive in the future regardless of the discount rate.

Fig. 12.1: Levelised cost of electricity for commercially available RE technologies at 3.7 and 10 discount rates (IPCC, 2012), showing the high competitiveness of geothermal power production in all cases.

Fig. 12.2: Levelised costs of heat for commercially available technologies at 3.7 and 10 discount rates (IPCC, 2012). Note the high performance of geothermal solutions (with the examples of greenhouses, aquaculture and district heating of ground heat pumps) in all cases.

When CO₂ concentration levels are considered, geothermal is shown to have a minimal contribution to these CO₂ levels. and the growth of global geothermal energy supply should therefore be very fast multiplied by 5 in 2030 with respect to 2020 and by 10 in 2050 (Fig12.3).

Fig. 12.3: Global primary energy supply of geothermal energy. Left: in long term scenarios with colour coding based on categories of atmospheric CO₂ concentration level in 2020. Right: estimate of the potential geothermal energy deployment for electricity (blue) and for DU (orange) applications. (IPCC, 2012)

Geothermal energy, particularly DUGD, is clearly has a promise for a bright future world-wide as shown in Table 12.1 where figures established by IPCC (2012) project figures for geothermal power installed in 2030 and 2050. This is a remarkable growth that should become even more rapid in the case of Africa. This however requires concerted effort given the current low level of development of this sector in the continent.

The success will rely upon the involvement of all concerned actors in the society, whether from the public sector, the private enterprises as well as citizen's contributions and organisations, allowing to establish the best governance scheme which should learn from the most advanced experiences, but be adapted to each country's characteristics. Table 12.2 outlines the factors and participants contributing to a successful RE governance regime.

The objective of this guideline has been to pave the way for such developments, by highlighting the DU perspective to geothermal exploration, development and utilisation in suitable sites in Africa that until now remains unexplored, thus opening up the subject for further debate and hopefully initial action. This is the challenge for the next 30 years or so, in which the transition from fossil fuels to RE should be achieved. Geothermal should play a major role and it is our responsibility to determine this success.

Table 12.1: Potential geothermal deployments for electricity and direct uses in 2020 through 2050 (from IPCC, 2020)

Year	Use	Capacity (GW)	Generation (TWh/yr)	Generation (EJ/yr)	Total (EJ/yr)
2020	Electricity	25.9	181.8	0.65	2.01
	Direct	143.6	377.5	1.36	
2030	Electricity	51.0	380.0	1.37	5.23
	Direct	407.8	1,071.7	3.86	
2050	Electricity	150.0	1,182.8	4.26	11.83
	Direct	800.0	2,102.3	7.57	

Table 12.2: factors and participants contributing to a successful Renewable Energy governance regime (IPCC, 2012)

Dimensions of an Enabling Environment >> Factors and actors contributing to the success of RE policy V V	11.6.2 Integrating policies (national/ supranational policies)	11.6.3 Reducing financial and investment risk	11.6.4 Planning and permitting at the local level	11.6.5 Providing infrastructures, networks and markets for RE technology	11.6.6 Technology transfer and capacity building	11.6.7-8 Learning from actors beyond government
Institutions	Integrating RE policies with other policies at the design level reduces potential for conflict among government policies	Development of financing institutions and agencies can aid cooperation between countries, provide soft loans or international carbon finance (CDM). Long-term commitment can reduce the perception of risk	Planning and permitting processes enable RE policy to be integrated with non-RE policies at the local level	Policymakers and regulators can enact incentives and rules for networks and markets, such as security standards and access rules	Reliability of RE technologies can be ensured through certification Institutional agreements enable technology transfer	Openness to learning from other actors can complement design of policies and enhance their effectiveness by working within existing social conditions
Civil society (individuals, households, nongovernment organizations, unions etc.)	Municipalities or cities can play a decisive role in integrating state policies at the local level	Community investment can share and reduce investment risk Public-private partnerships in investment and project development can contribute to reducing risks associated with policy instruments Appropriate international institutions can enable an equitable distribution of funds	Participation of civil society in local planning and permitting processes might allow for selection of the most socially relevant RE projects	Civil society can become part of supply networks through co-production of energy and new decentralized models.	Local actors and NGOs can be involved in technology transfer through new business models bringing together multi-national companies / NGOs / small and medium enterprises (SMEs)	Civil society participation in open policy processes can generate new knowledge and induce institutional change Municipalities or cities may develop solutions to make RE technology development possible at the local level People (individually or collectively) have a potential for advancing energy-related behaviours when policy signals and contextual constraints are coherent
Finance and business communities		Public private partnerships in investment and project development can contribute to reducing risks associated with policy instruments	RE project developers can offer know-how and professional networks in : i) aligning project development with planning and permitting requirements ; and ii) adapting planning and permitting processes to local needs and conditions Businesses can be active in lobbying for coherent and integrated policies	Clarity of network and market rules improves investor confidence	Financing institutions and agencies can partner with national governments, provide soft loans or international carbon finance (CDM).	Multi-national companies can involve local NGOs or SMEs as partners in new technology development (new business models) Development of corporations and international institutions reduces risk of investment
Infrastructures	Policy integration with network and market rules can enable development of infrastructure suitable for a low-carbon economy	Clarity of network and market rules reduces risk of investment and improves investor confidence		Clear and transparent network and market rules are more likely to lead to infrastructures complementary to a lowcarbon future		City and community level frameworks for the development of longterm infrastructure and networks can sustain the involvement of local actors in policy development

Dimensions of an Enabling Environment >> Factors and actors contributing to the success of RE policy V V	11.6.2 Integrating policies (national/ supranational policies)	11.6.3 Reducing financial and investment risk	11.6.4 Planning and permitting at the local level	11.6.5 Providing infrastructures, networks and markets for RE technology	11.6.6 Technology transfer and capacity building	11.6.7-8 Learning from actors beyond government
Politics (international agreements / cooperation, climate change strategy, technology transfer etc.)	Supra-national guidelines (e.g., EU on 'streamlining', ocean planning, impact study) may contribute to integrating RE policy with other policies	Long-term political commitment to RE policy reduces investors risk in RE projects	Supra-national guidelines may contribute to evolving planning and permitting processes	Development cooperation helps sustain infrastructure development and allows easier access to low-carbon technologies	CDM, Intellectual property rights and patent agreements can contribute to technology transfer	Appropriate input from non-government institutions stimulates more agreements that are socially connected UNFCCC process mechanisms such as Expert Group on Technology Transfer, the Global Environment Facility, and the Clean Development Mechanism and Joint Implementation may provide guidelines to facilitate the involvement of non-state actors in RE policy development

Steaming grounds at Corbetti Geothermal Area, Ethiopia
 Photo credit: Sam Abraham/flickr

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